

Rock–Water Interaction Group
Institute of Geological Sciences,
University of Bern
Baltzerstrasse 1–3, CH-3012 Bern

**GEOLOGICAL SUITABILITY OF THE SWISS MOLASSE BASIN
FOR GAS STORAGE AND GEO-METHANATION:
A LITERATURE STUDY**

**PROJECT USC-FLEXSTORE
WORKPACKAGE 4**

May, 2023

This final version replaces the preliminary versions of 12/2021 and 11/2022.

Authors:

Dr. Daniela B. van den Heuvel, Prof. Larryn W. Diamond

Contributions by Ferdinando Musso Piantelli, Philippos Garefalakis

Conducted within the ERA NET Cofund research project "Underground Sun Conversion FlexStore" (2021–2023), funded by the Swiss Federal Office of Energy.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank Markus Pichler and Wolfdietrich Jilg (RAG, Vienna) for sharing their extensive experience on the operation of geo-methanation at the Lehen site, Austria. We also gratefully acknowledge input from Hannes Konegger and Andreas Loibner (BOKU, Vienna) regarding the living conditions required for methanogens. Lukas Aschwanden, Martin Mazurek and Daniel Traber kindly helped us to find our way around all the geological formations within the Swiss Molasse Basin and, more importantly, through all the available geological data.

We are grateful to Lance Reynolds and Eva Kurmann from Swisstopo (Swiss Federal Office of Topography) for providing data and support regarding GeoMol and its associated temperature model.

We also thank all the partners of the USC-FlexStore project both in Switzerland and Austria for fruitful discussions and for allowing us to introduce them to the Swiss subsurface. We appreciate management support from the coordinators for FlexStore Switzerland, Daniel Sidler and Andreas Kunz (Energie360°, Zurich) and all colleagues of RAG Austria AG.

This work was carried out within the European Underground Sun Conversion FlexStore project (ERA NET Cofund), funded by the Swiss Federal Office of Energy (SFOE) and Energie360° AG (Zurich).

Table of Contents

List of Figures	VII
List of Tables	XVI
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Approach and structure of the report	2
1.2 Aims of the study	2
2 Criteria for geological formations suitable for geo-methanation	4
2.1 Reservoir criteria	4
2.1.1 Geometry: Volume, thickness and depth	4
2.1.2 Temperature and pressure.....	6
2.1.3 Mineralogy.....	7
2.1.4 Porosity.....	7
2.2 In-situ porewater criteria	8
2.3 Permeability and retention criteria.....	8
3 Geological background and sources of information	10
3.1 Brief introduction to the geology of the Swiss Molasse Basin (SMB).....	10
3.2 Knowledge of the subsurface in the SMB.....	14
3.2.1 Ongoing and future data collection campaigns.....	16
3.3 Geological model of the SMB (GeoMol)	19
3.4 Delimitation of geological units based on criteria for successful geo-methanation ..	22
4 Characterisation of individual geological units, hydrogeology and structures	24
4.1 Description of geological units.....	25
4.1.1 Crystalline basement	25
4.1.2 Permo-Carboniferous sediments	25
4.1.3 Lower to Middle Triassic Buntsandstein Group	27
4.1.4 Middle Triassic Muschelkalk Group.....	28
4.1.5 Upper Triassic Keuper Group.....	29
4.1.6 Lower Jurassic (Liassic) deposits	31

4.1.7	Middle Jurassic Dogger Group	33
4.1.8	Upper Jurassic (Malm) sediments	34
4.1.9	Lower (and Upper) Cretaceous sediments.....	36
4.1.10	Lower Oligocene Lower Marine Molasse (UMM)	36
4.1.11	Upper Oligocene to Lower Miocene Lower Freshwater Molasse (USM)	37
4.1.12	Lower Miocene Upper Marine Molasse (OMM)	38
4.1.13	Upper Miocene Upper Freshwater Molasse (OSM).....	39
4.2	Reservoir properties.....	39
4.2.1	Crystalline basement	40
4.2.2	Permo-carboniferous sediments	40
4.2.3	Buntsandstein Group.....	41
4.2.4	Muschelkalk Group	42
4.2.5	Klettgau Formation.....	42
4.2.6	Staffelegg Formation.....	45
4.2.7	Dogger Group.....	46
4.2.8	Upper Jurassic and Cretaceous sediments	46
4.2.9	Lower Freshwater Molasse (USM)	47
4.2.10	Upper Marine Molasse (OMM).....	48
4.2.11	Upper Freshwater Molasse (OSM)	48
4.3	Chemical composition of groundwaters.....	49
4.3.1	Crystalline basement and Palaeozoic sediments.....	49
4.3.2	Deep Mesozoic units.....	50
4.3.3	Shallow Mesozoic units.....	51
4.3.4	Molasse units	51
4.4	Structures in the SMB	52
4.4.1	Fault zones	52
4.4.2	Anticlinal traps	55
4.4.3	Structural subdivision of the SMB.....	56
5	Suitability of geological formations in the SMB for geo-methanation	58
5.1	Ranking scheme.....	58
5.2	Crystalline basement	60
5.3	Pre-Weitenau Formation.....	60
5.4	Dinkelberg Formation	61
5.5	Schinznach Formation (Stamberg Member).....	61
5.6	Klettgau Formation (SBEG Members).....	62
5.7	Staffelegg Formation (Beggingen Member)	63
5.8	Dogger Group (Hauptrogenstein)	63

5.9	Upper Jurassic and Cretaceous limestones	64
5.10	Lower Freshwater Molasse (USM)	64
5.11	Upper Marine Molasse (OMM).....	65
5.12	Upper Freshwater Molasse (OSM)	65
6	Distribution of target formations for geo-methanation in the SMB	66
6.1	Pre-Weitenau Formation.....	66
6.2	Dinkelberg Formation	68
6.3	Schinznach Formation (Stamberg Member).....	70
6.4	Klettgau Formation (SBEG Members).....	73
6.5	Staffelegg Formation (Beggingen Member)	76
6.6	Dogger Group (Hauptrogenstein).....	79
6.7	Etiollets Formation.....	81
6.8	Lower Freshwater Molasse	85
6.9	Upper Marine Molasse	87
6.10	Upper Freshwater Molasse	88
6.11	Uncertainties and significance of delimited aquifers.....	92
6.12	Suitability map for geo-methanation in the SMB	95
7	Establishing feasibility of geo-methanation in the SMB	97
7.1	Properties of gas traps at km-scale	97
7.2	Exploration steps.....	99
7.2.1	Site selection.....	100
7.2.2	Site characterisation and baseline monitoring.....	101
7.3	Creation of an artificial gas cap and medium-term monitoring.....	101
7.4	Typical time schedule for an exploration and gas injection campaign	102
7.5	Typical costs for an exploration and gas injection campaign	102
8	Possible conflicts of use of the subsurface in the SMB	105
8.1	Infrastructure	106
8.2	Potable groundwater	106
8.3	Mineral resources	106
8.4	Hydrocarbons and coal	107
8.4.1	Oil and natural gas.....	107
8.4.2	Coal	108
8.5	Geothermal energy	109
8.5.1	Shallow geothermal: Ground source heat pumps (GSHP)	109
8.5.2	Medium-depth geothermal: Hydrothermal energy	109
8.5.3	Deep geothermal: Enhanced geothermal systems.....	110

8.6	Seasonal storage	110
8.6.1	Aquifer thermal energy storage (ATES)	110
8.6.2	Seasonal storage of natural gas or hydrogen	111
8.7	CO ₂ -sequestration	111
8.8	Disposal of radioactive waste.....	112
8.9	Possible conflict of use vs. chance for joint exploration?.....	112
9	Outlook	115
9.1	Other promising exploration regions.....	115
9.2	Possible further studies to support geo-methanation.....	115
9.3	Open question: Geo-methanation up to 90 °C?	116
10	Summary and conclusions	118
11	References	123
Appendix A	Maps depicting GeoMol horizons in the correct depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation	A-1
Appendix B	Thickness of individual members of the Klettgau and Staffelegg Formations	B-1

List of Figures

Figure 1.1: Schematic depiction of the geo-methanation of H₂ and CO₂ achieved during the Underground Sun Conversion (USC) process (www.underground-sun-conversion.at; December 2021).1

Figure 2.1: Types of gas traps. For geo-methanation, anticlinal or stratigraphic traps are preferred (Encyclopædia Britannica® Online).9

Figure 3.1: Simplified lithostratigraphy of the SMB. Formation names and colours are given according to the recommendations of the Swiss Committee for Stratigraphy (SKS; names in bold type). Names used in older literature are listed in column labelled “Classic”. Both nomenclatures are heavily based on the formations occurring in northern Switzerland (Jordan & Deplazes, 2019) and might not be representative across the entire SMB. Names given in the last column are used in this report (Chapter 4).11

Figure 3.2: Tectonic map of Switzerland and the surrounding areas (modified after Pfiffner, 2021) showing the Jura Mountains (light blue), Swiss Molasse Basin (SMB; yellow) including the Subalpine Molasse (light orange) along the Alpine front and the different zones of the Alps in purple, green and shades of red. Only the area of the SMB will be assessed for its suitability for geo-methanation in this study.12

Figure 3.3: Cross-section from the southern margin of the Jura Mountains (NNW; Bözingerberg) to the Alpine front (SSE, Lake Thun), across the entire SMB along the Biel/Bienne-Bern-Thun line. The Mesozoic strata are shown in orange/pink (Triassic), purple (Lower Jurassic), brown (Middle Jurassic) and blue (Upper Jurassic). They are folded and faulted in the Jura Mountains but relatively undisturbed across the SMB. Above the Mesozoic strata are the Lower Freshwater Molasse (peach colour) and the Upper Marine Molasse (olive green colour). Both increase in thickness from north to south towards the Alpine front. The Molasse sediments are faulted in the subjurassic and subalpine zones.13

Figure 3.4: Map of all the seismic lines shot and wells drilled to > 500 m depth before 2017 within the Swiss Molasse Basin and the adjacent Jura Mountains. Wells drilled since 2017 (Section 3.2) are marked in yellow. Red well markers indicate that the data obtained are not publicly available, while green markers indicate wells where at least some data are publicly available via the federal geoportal (map.geo.admin.ch).	15
Figure 3.5: Exploration maturity of the Swiss Molasse Basin with the ongoing exploration campaigns described in Section 3.2.1 indicated in grey (modified after Chevalier et al., 2010).	16
Figure 3.6: Map of NE Switzerland showing the three potential siting regions Jura Ost, Nördlich Lägern and Zürich Nordost for geological repositories for nuclear waste as investigated by Nagra. Part of the ongoing site selection process was the recent drilling of several deep wells (red) throughout 2020 and 2021 (provided by Nagra, 2021).	17
Figure 3.7: Areas in which the 3D geological model GeoMol (“outer geological perimeter”; in yellow) and the temperature model (“inner geological perimeter”; in red) are defined.	20
Figure 3.8: (a) 3D view towards the West showing the land-surface topography in grey (DEM) and the underlying modelled geological units of the Molasse basin. The surfaces dividing geological units have been clipped along the trace of the A–A’ cross-section, visible in the front of the diagram. (b) A–A’ cross-section view of the horizons. Highlighted by the light brown polygon is the target area that satisfies the required conditions of depth >600 m and $30\text{ °C} \leq T \leq 60\text{ °C}$. (c) 3D clipped view towards the West showing the modelled surfaces of the target bodies, including subvertical fault planes (red). The position of cross-section B–B’ is visible in the front of the diagram. (d) B–B’ cross-section view of the target horizons forming a Top Horizon and a Bottom Horizon of the target area; h represents the vertical distance between the two horizons.....	23
Figure 4.1: Stratigraphic column of the Swiss Molasse Basin (SMB) modified after Chevalier et al. (2010). The first four columns show the age, encountered lithologies and their basin-wide distribution and stratigraphic names based on the valid definition and nomenclature of the Swiss Committee for Stratigraphy (SKS). Column 5 shows the basin-wide variations in thickness. Column 6 identifies regional- to local-scale aquifers (blue) and impermeable seals (= caprocks; orange). Ranges of aquifer porosities and permeabilities measured are shown in column 7 and 8.	26

Figure 4.2: Example of interpreted distribution of Permo-Carboniferous troughs (brown) and high zones (pink) within the crystalline basement (yellow) in the basement of the Swiss Molasse Basin. The large trough in Northern Switzerland, extending into both, southern Germany and France, is the North Swiss Permo-Carboniferous Basin (NSPB). Unpublished map by W. Leu (2008).....	27
Figure 4.3: The five distinct Members of the Schinznach Formation (modified after Pietsch et al., 2016) and their thicknesses. The different rock types are shown in different colours (brown: mudstones/marls, blue: carbonates, partially dolomitised). Only the Stamberg Member is an aquifer; the other members show properties between an aquifer and aquitard.....	29
Figure 4.4: The six distinct Members of the Klettgau Formation (modified after Jordan et al., 2016). The different rock types are shown in different colours (brown: mudstones/marls, yellow: sandstones, blue: limestone, partially dolomitised and orange: evaporites). The Seebi, Gansingen, Berlingen and the sandstones of the Ergolz Member are aquifers, while the rest of the Ergolz and the Gruhalden Member are aquitards. The Belchen Member at the top shows properties between aquifer and aquitard.....	31
Figure 4.5: The eleven distinct Members of the Staffelegg Formation (modified after Reisdorf et al., 2011). The different rock types are shown in different colours (brown: mudstones/marls, yellow: sandstones, blue: limestone, partially dolomitised). Only the Beggingen Member is an aquifer – the other formations show aquitard characteristics.	32
Figure 4.6: Stratigraphic scheme for the Early Dogger Group in the eastern folded Jura (first column) and eastern SMB (second column; Jordan and Deplazes, 2019).	34
Figure 4.7: Paleogeographic map of Switzerland and surrounding areas during the deposition of the USM in the Chattian/Aquitainian, OMM in the Burdigalian and OSM in the Langhian and Serravallian. Note the transition from terrestrial/fluvial to marine and back to terrestrial/fluvial conditions and the conglomerate fans which are active throughout the deposition of the Molasse sediments (modified after Berger et al., 2005).	38
Figure 4.8: Porosity (left) and permeability (right) data for Nagra-TBO wells at Bözberg-1 and-2, Bülach, Marthalen and Trüllikon. Locations of wells shown in Figure 3.6. Individual measurements are shown for three siting regions (◊: Jura Ost, ○: Nördlich Lägern, □: Zürich Nordost). Averages of porosity in each formation in each well are indicated by black horizontal bars. For the permeability data (from hydrotests), lowest estimates (min.	

values) and highest estimate (max.) are plotted. The previously compiled data ranges from Chevalier et al. (2010) are shown in grey boxes.	43
Figure 4.9: Groundwater types in the Molasse units across the SMB (Nagra, 1988).	52
Figure 4.10: Map showing faults present in the SMB as included in the GeoMol model (Section 3.3) at the base of the Cenozoic sediments, i.e. cross-cutting the Mesozoic sediments (Allenbach et al., 2017).	54
Figure 4.11: Map showing faults present in the SMB as included in the GeoMol model (Section 3.3) at the base of the Mesozoic sediments, i.e. originating within the crystalline basement (Allenbach et al., 2017).	54
Figure 4.12: Map showing the fold axis traces of anticlines (solid blue lines) and synclines (dashed blue lines) in the SMB as included in the GeoMol model. The colours indicate the Cenozoic units exposed at the surface (yellow: OSM, green: OMM and pink: USM). The Subalpine Molasse is indicated by the brown striated area along the Alpine front (Allenbach et al., 2017).	55
Figure 4.13: Maps differentiating areas within the SMB and adjacent Jura Mountains based on (A) the types of faults and (B) potential traps. Modified after Chevalier et al. (2010).	57
Figure 6.1: Map of the Pre-Weitenau Formation showing where the Permokarbondrog layer occurs in the correct depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation (all colours) and how this area was further constrained to show areas where Pre-Weitenau deposits are possibly present (dark olive green) or likely present (light olive). The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.	68
Figure 6.2: Delimited Pre-Weitenau Formation. Top map: depth below surface to top of aquifer. Bottom map: vertical thickness of the formation and locations of known faults. The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.	69
Figure 6.3: Map of the Dinkelberg Formation showing where the Muschelkalk layer occurs in the correct depth interval for geo-methanation (all colours) and how this area was further constrained to show area where the Dinkelberg aquifer is present (light olive). The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.	71
Figure 6.4: Delimited Dinkelberg Formation. Top map: depth below surface to top of aquifer. Bottom map: vertical thickness of the aquifer and locations of known faults. Isopachs are modified after Chevalier et al. (2010). The three	

Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.....	72
Figure 6.5: Map of the Schinznach Formation – Stamberg Member showing where the Mus horizon occurs in the correct depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation (light olive). As the Stamberg Member lies at the top of the Schinznach Formation (Asp Member is not considered due to its small thickness), the map does not need to be delimited further. The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.	73
Figure 6.6: Delimited Schinznach Formation – Stamberg Member. Top map: depth below surface to top of aquifer. Bottom map: stratigraphic thickness of the Member and locations of known faults and anticline crest. Isopachs are modified after Adams et al. (2019). The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.....	74
Figure 6.7: Map of the Klettgau Formation with SBEG Members showing where the Keuper layer occurs in the correct depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation (all colours) and how this area was further constrained to show area where sealed Klettgau aquifers are likely present (light olive). In addition, the distribution of all four members with potential reservoir properties in the area of interest is shown (modified after Jordan et al., 2016). The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.	75
Figure 6.8: Delimited Klettgau Formation – S(B)EG Members. Top map: depth below surface to top of formation. Bottom map: locations of known anticline crest and faults within the delimited area. See inset diagram for ranges of stratigraphic thicknesses of the Members. Thickness maps of each aquifer Member are given in Appendix B. The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.....	77
Figure 6.9: Map of the Staffelegg Formation – Beggingen Member showing where the Lias layer occurs in the correct depth interval for geo-methanation (all colours) and how this area was further constrained to show area where the Beggingen Member is likely present (dark olive) The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.	79
Figure 6.10: Delimited Staffelegg Formation – Beggingen Members. Top map: depth below surface to top of formation. Bottom map: stratigraphic thickness of Beggingen aquifer with locations of known faults and anticline crest. A detailed map of the thickness of the Beggingen Member is given in Appendix B. The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.....	80

Figure 6.11: Map of the Hauptrogenstein showing where the Dogger layer occurs in the correct depth interval for geo-methanation (all colours) and how this area was further constrained to show area where Hauptrogenstein is possible (dark olive) and likely (light olive). The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.....82

Figure 6.12: Delimited Hauptrogenstein. Top map: depth below surface to top of formation. Bottom map: stratigraphic thickness of formation and locations of known faults and anticline crest. Isopachs are modified after Chevalier et al. (2010). The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.....83

Figure 6.13: Map of the Etiollets Formation showing where the Upper Malm layer occurs in the correct depth interval for geo-methanation (all colours) and how this area was further constrained to show the areas where the Etiollets Formation is likely present (light olive). The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.....84

Figure 6.14: Delimited Etiollets Formation. Top map: depth below surface to top of formation. Bottom map: stratigraphic thickness of formation and locations of known faults and anticline crest. Thickness information is derived from Jenny et al. (1995) and the newly drilled GGeo-02 well (pers. comm. SIG). The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.....86

Figure 6.15: Map of the Lower Freshwater Molasse (USM) showing where the USM layer occurs in the required depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation (all colours) and how this area was further constrained to exclude the conglomerate-rich facies (yellow). The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.....87

Figure 6.16: Delimited Lower Freshwater Molasse (USM). Top map: depth below surface to top of USM (for details see Figure A.6). Bottom map: vertical thickness and locations of known faults and anticline crest. The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be likely off limits for geo-methanation projects.89

Figure 6.17: Map of the Upper Marine Molasse (OMM) showing where it occurs in the correct depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation (all colours) and how this area was further constrained to exclude the conglomerate-rich facies (yellow). Also differentiated is an area sealed above by the OSM unit at depths deeper than 600 m (light olive). Dark olive shows where the OMM would need to contain sealed aquifers internally, in order to be suitable for geo-methanation. The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.....90

- Figure 6.18:** Delimited Upper Marine Molasse (OMM). Top map: depth below surface to top of OMM (for details see Figure A.7). Bottom map: vertical thickness and locations of known faults and anticline crest. The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.....91
- Figure 6.19:** Map of the Upper Freshwater Molasse (OSM) showing where it occurs in the correct depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation (all colours) and how this area was further constrained to exclude the conglomerate-rich facies (yellow). The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.....92
- Figure 6.20:** Delimited Upper Freshwater Molasse (OSM). Top map: depth below surface to top of OSM (for details see Figure A.8). Bottom map: vertical thickness and locations of known faults and anticline axis. The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.93
- Figure 6.21:** Map showing relative suitability of areas in the Swiss Molasse Basin for geological gas storage under conditions required for USC-FlexStore geo-methanation (greater than 600 m deep, temperature 30–60 °C). Shades of green denote the sum of sealed aquifer formations locally present in the sedimentary stack, each aquifer being weighted by the reciprocal of its quality ranking (1, 2 or 3; Table 5-1). Blue lines show locations of the crests of known elongated dome structures (anticlines) in the subsurface, which may serve as gas traps. Areas distant from blue lines may or may not contain other unknown anticlines. Faults (not shown in this map) may also create gas traps, but less commonly than anticlines. All known faults are shown in the maps of individual reservoir units (maps in this section).95
- Figure 7.1:** An example cross-section of potential gas traps 15 km ENE from Aarau, where Nagra has conducted detailed 3D seismic imaging, coring of deep wells and geological interpretation. The labelled low-angle thrust carries a ramp anticline (Chestenberg) that folds four potential sealed-reservoir units: Schinznach–Stamberg, Klettgau–SEG, Staffelegg–Beggingen and Hauptrogenstein (here the latter is shallower than 600 m depth limit for geo-methanation). The axis and crest of the fold are projected onto the surface, illustrating their relative locations if viewed in a map. Below the thrust, steep normal faults may conceivably create traps in the Dinkelberg Fm. No information is available as to whether these potential traps are closed in the third dimension outside the 2D plane of the diagram, and whether they are tight or leaky for gas. Note vertical exaggeration of scale. Diagram modified after Nagra (2008; Beilage 5.2-14).98

Figure 7.2: Illustration of exploration for a geo-methanation site and creation of a gas cap. (A) Trap structure (an anticlinal fold in this example) is identified in a 3D seismic survey. (B) A well is drilled to demonstrate that the trap contains a porous and permeable saline aquifer sealed by an impermeable caprock, and to test for the presence of natural gas in the trap. (C) In the absence of a natural gas accumulation (as expected in the Swiss Molasse Basin), methane is injected into the trap, displacing the formation water from the pores in the aquifer rock and thereby creating an artificial gas cap.....	100
Figure 7.3: Time-schedule of typical operations to explore for a geo-methanation site and create a gas cap in a favourable trap structure. Modified after Häring et al. (2013).	103
Figure 10.1: Map showing relative suitability of areas in the Swiss Molasse Basin for geological gas storage under conditions required for geo-methanation (greater than 600 m deep, temperature 30–60 °C). Shades of denote the sum of sealed aquifer formations locally present in the sedimentary stack, each weighted by its quality ranking. Future wells drilled through several aquifers have higher likelihood of finding suitable reservoirs. Gas trap structures are essential for successful geo-methanation: blue lines show locations of known elongated dome structures (anticlines) that may serve as traps and are therefore priority exploration targets. Areas distant from blue lines may or may not contain anticlines. Faults may also create gas traps but less commonly than anticlines - see maps in Chapter 6 for fault locations.	121
Figure A.1: Map showing the Permokarbondrog layer in GeoMol trimmed to the correct depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation. This layer was used to create the delimited maps for the Pre-Weitenau Formation in Section 6.1.	A-2
Figure A.2: Map showing the Muschelkalk layer in GeoMol trimmed to the correct depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation. This layer was used to create the delimited maps for the Dinkelberg Formation (Section 6.2) and Schinznach Formation – Stamberg Member (Section 6.3).....	A-3
Figure A.3: Map showing the Keuper layer in GeoMol trimmed to the correct depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation. This layer was used to create the delimited maps for the Klettgau Formation – SBEG Members (Section 6.4).....	A-4
Figure A.4: Map showing the Lias layer in GeoMol trimmed to the correct depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation. This layer was used to create the delimited maps for the Staffelegg Formation – Beggingen Member (Section 6.5).....	A-5

Figure A.5: Map showing the Dogger layer in GeoMol trimmed to the correct depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation. This layer was used to create the delimited maps for the Hauptrogenstein (Section 6.6).....	A-6
Figure A.6: Map showing the Upper Malm layer in GeoMol trimmed to the correct depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation. This layer was used to create the delimited maps for the Etiollets Formation (Section 6.7).....	A-7
Figure A.7: Map showing the USM layer in GeoMol trimmed to the correct depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation. This layer was used to create the delimited maps for the Lower Freshwater Molasse (Section 6.8).	A-8
Figure A.8: Map showing the OMM layer in GeoMol trimmed to the correct depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation. This layer was used to create the delimited maps for the Upper Marine Molasse (Section 6.9).	A-9
Figure A.9: Map showing the OSM layer in GeoMol trimmed to the correct depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation. This layer was used to create the delimited maps for the Upper Freshwater Molasse (Section 6.10).	A-10
Figure B.1: Thickness of Klettgau-Seebi Member from wells drilled in the area of interest and adjoining areas. Line shows westernmost expansion of Seebi Member. Modified after Jordan et al. (2016).	B-2
Figure B.2: Thickness of Klettgau-Berlingen Member from wells drilled in areas adjoining the area of interest. Line shows westernmost expansion of Berlingen Member. Modified after Jordan et al. (2016).	B-3
Figure B.3: Thickness of Klettgau-Ergolz Member (focus on sandy units) from wells drilled in the area of interest and adjoining areas. The Ergolz Member is present across the area studied by Jordan et al. (2016).	B-4
Figure B.4: Thickness of Klettgau-Gansingen Member (only dolomite) from wells drilled in the area of interest and adjoining areas. Line shows easternmost expansion of Gansingen Member. Modified after Jordan et al. (2016).	B-5
Figure B.5: Thickness of Staffelegg-Beggingen Member from wells (◇) drilled in the area of interest and adjoining areas as well as outcrops (○) in the Jura Mountains. Modified after Reisdorf et al. (2011).	B-6

List of Tables

Table 2.1: List of geological criteria for geo-methanation implementation, as used to guide the present study. Each of these criteria is described in detail in Section 2.....5

Table 3.1: Stratigraphic units (c.f. Figure 3.1) and corresponding layers between horizons modelled in GeoMol. As the layers generally represent entire stratigraphic groups comprising several formations, they often contain one or several aquifers and seals in the same unit.21

Table 5.1: Criteria (positive indicators) and SMB geological units screened for geo-methanation implementation. A “y” (for “yes”) indicates that the criterion is fulfilled; “(y)” indicates that the criterion is barely fulfilled or highly uncertain; and “n” (for “no”) indicates that it is not fulfilled. The units are ranked from 1 to 4, where 1 denotes "potentially suitable for geo-methanation" and 4 denotes "likely unsuitable for geo-methanation".59

Table 7.1: Typical costs to plan and explore for a geo-methanation site, to create a gas trap containing 4.5 million m³_{STP} and to monitor its integrity over a 6-year period. Included are one injection/extraction well and two narrow-bore observation wells, all drilled to depths of 2000 m. Based on information provided by Dr. Werner Leu (Geoform Geological Consulting and Studies Ltd., Vevey, Switzerland).104

1 Introduction

This report was written as part of the ERA-Net Cofund project Underground Sun Conversion (USC) FlexStore. Underground Sun Conversion describes geo-methanation whereby green H₂ is produced from renewable energy sources through electrolysis, mixed with industrial waste CO₂ and injected into a reservoir formation in the subsurface. There, in-situ methanogenic organisms thrive and convert the gases to renewable CH₄ and H₂O (Figure 1.1).

Figure 1.1: Schematic depiction of the geo-methanation of H₂ and CO₂ achieved during the Underground Sun Conversion (USC) process (www.underground-sun-conversion.at; December 2021).

Geo-methanation of H₂ and CO₂ has been achieved by the gas storage company RAG (Vienna) at the Lehen site, a small sandstone reservoir near Vöcklabruck in Oberösterreich, Austria. Over the years, the conditions needed for the methanogenic microbes to thrive and produce methane have been investigated at the University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences (BOKU) in the field and in laboratory experiments while RAG investigated the reservoir conditions at the Lehen site.

1.1 Approach and structure of the report

Based on results from the USC project in Austria, the conditions needed for successful, microbially mediated methanogenesis in a geological reservoir could be defined. These findings were combined with experience from international Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) studies regarding the range of reservoir properties that allow injection and retention of gas. Together, they constitute a set of criteria characterising potential reservoirs for geo-methanation, which are described in detail in Chapter 2. Chapter 3 presents the various types and sources of geological information on which the present study is based. This includes the three-dimensional (3D) geological model of the Molasse Basin (GeoMol), which defines the distribution of target formations in the subsurface. The individual lithological units present in the Swiss Molasse Basin (SMB) and their reservoir characteristics are described in detail in Chapter 4. In addition, information is provided on the regional hydrogeology and hydrochemistry as well as structures present in the SMB. In Chapter 5, the list of geological criteria from Chapter 2 is applied to all potential reservoir formations and used to appraise their suitability for geo-methanation. Maps indicating the areas where the most promising formations occur within the correct depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation are shown in Chapter 6. Chapter 7 provides information on possible future exploration for geo-methanation reservoirs, including timelines and estimated costs. As the interest in the subsurface increases, conflicts of use between geo-methanation and other technologies are expected to increase. These potential conflicts are addressed in Chapter 8. Finally, Chapters 9 and 10 give an outlook on potential future work and summarise the findings of the report.

1.2 Aims of the study

The aims of this study are sixfold:

- (1) Define geological criteria required for successful geo-methanation based on reservoir and porewater properties and the likelihood of gas retention.
- (2) Compile relevant information for geological units in the Swiss Molasse Basin (geology, hydrogeology and structures).
- (3) Assess each unit based on the defined criteria. Rank units based on a combination of their suitability for geo-methanation and the level of knowledge of their properties.
- (4) Using the 3D geological model of the Swiss Molasse Basin (GeoMol), delimit areas where the formations occur within the correct depth–temperature interval, including the presence of potential gas trap structures.
- (5) Outline future steps required to establish definitive feasibility of geo-methanation by

testing promising traps for their gas injectivity and retentivity, including the expected duration and costs of an exploration campaign.

- (6) Discuss potential conflicts of use between geo-methanation and other subsurface technologies in the SMB.

2 Criteria for geological formations suitable for geo-methanation

2.1 Reservoir criteria

2.1.1 Geometry: Volume, thickness and depth

The storage volume is a crucial parameter for successful geo-methanation in Switzerland as it defines how much gas can be stored in one site. In this report we refer to gas volumes in their expanded state at the Standard Pressure and Temperature used by the natural gas industry, namely 15 °C and 1 atmosphere (101.325 kPa), abbreviated herein as STP.

Regardless of the reservoir geology, considerations of economic viability set minimum requirements on potential storage volumes for the USC technology. Estimates of the hypothetical storage volume required for feasible implementation of geo-methanation at specific sites have been estimated in Task 5.1 of the current project (OST; report in prep.). These estimates are based on the amount of locally produced excess electricity, on requirements for successful electrolysis to produce H₂, on the range of probable feed-gas ratios between CO₂, H₂ and CH₄, and on the ratio of "process gas" (the theoretical portion of gas that can be generated in the reservoir and produced by geo-methanation) to "cushion gas" (the portion of gas required to maintain pressure and preclude invasion of formation water in the reservoir).

As positive indicators we defined the range from the smallest hypothetical storage volume calculated (4.5 Mio. m³_{STP}; Case 1, KVA Zuchwil) to the largest one calculated for a single site (400 Mio. m³, Case 2, RoR Verbois; pers. comm. Zoe Stadler OST). Larger storage volumes are possible from a technical point of view, e.g., the large-scale natural gas storage site at Puchkirchen (Austria) operated by RAG contains around 860 Mio. m³_{STP} of natural gas. However, larger volumes in the Swiss context would require transporting H₂ and CO₂ from distant locations to the storage site, or running the electrolysis with electricity from the national grid, both of which would significantly increase costs.

Table 2.1: List of geological criteria for geo-methanation implementation, as used to guide the present study. Each of these criteria is described in detail in Section 2.

	Criteria	Positive indicators	Cautionary indicators	Relevant for		
				Micro-bio.	Techn. cons.	Econ. cons.
RESERVOIR	Storage vol.	4.5–400 Mio. m ³ _{STP} ¹	< 4.5 Mio. m ³ _{STP} ¹		x	x
	Thickness	> 5 m	< 3 m		x	
	Depth	> 600 m and in desired T-range	< 600 m or outside desired T-range	x	x	(x)
	Temperature	30 to 60 °C	< 30 or > 60 °C	x		
	Mineralogy	No chlorides	Presence of KCl, high amount of NaCl	x	x	
	Porosity	> 20 vol.%	< 10 vol.%		x	
	Permeability	50 to 3000 mD	< 50 or > 3000 mD		x	
IN-SITU POREW.	pH	6 to 9	< 6 or > 9	x		
	Salinity	30 to 150 g/L > 3 g/L K ⁺	< 30 g/L or > 150 g/L > 10 g/L K ⁺	x	x	
RETENTION	Aquifer type	Porous rock matrix	Fracture or karst		x	
	Caprock/seal	Present & tight; directly above reservoir	Fractured; other formations between reservoir and seal		x	
	Trap struct.	Stratigraphic or anticlinal traps	Fault traps		x	

¹STP = Standard Temperature and Pressure for natural gas: 15 °C, 1 atm (101.325 kPa)

From purely geological considerations, the storage volume of a site depends on several parameters: (a) the volume of the aquifer, (b) the interconnected porosity of the aquifer, (c) the density of the gas mixture at reservoir temperature and pressure, (d) the irreducible water saturation (i.e., the fraction of porosity filled by formation water that cannot be expelled due to capillary forces upon gas injection), and (e) the proportion of the total pore space in the reservoir that can be reached by injecting gas from a well (whether vertical or horizontal). Parameters (a) to (c) represent the theoretical capacity of gas injection while (d) and (e) are typically combined as a numerical storage coefficient (Chevalier et al., 2010). To obtain the theoretically effective storage capacity (i.e., the storage volume of interest), the theoretical capacity is multiplied by a suitable value of the storage coefficient (typically on the order of 5%),

which has been empirically determined for each of numerous sedimentary rocks by the oil industry (IEA-GHG, 2009).

When determining the aquifer volume, a crucial factor is the thickness of the formation. The experience by RAG suggests that, from a purely technical standpoint, the geo-methanation-technology can be implemented even if the reservoir is only 1 m thick (e.g., Speicher Lehen). While such a thin reservoir is sufficient for a test site, thicker units, preferentially > 5 m, are desired to achieve economically viable volumes of gas. In order to increase the area of contact between the injection wellbore and the formation, a section of the well can be drilled parallel to the lateral extent of the reservoir formation (e.g. horizontally), as is done routinely throughout the world in commercial gas fields. This was done at the large-scale natural gas storage site Puchkirchen, where the reservoir is only 14 m thick. Thus, each well has a nearly 1 km long horizontal section completed with pre-perforated liners to increase the area of contact and reduce the number of wells required for economic operation of the site.

Both porosity of the formation and the density of the gas mixture depend on the depth of the storage formation. As the injected gases are much more mobile than formation water, a minimum depth of 600 m below surface is defined to ensure that the gases can be retained adequately, provided that the reservoir is capped by a suitable sealing formation. This 600 m depth is based on empirical observations of successful gas storage projects, including the Puchkirchen site. The maximum depth value for geo-methanation is not defined by gas-retention considerations, but instead by the depth where the reservoir temperature exceeds that at which methanogens can flourish (see below).

2.1.2 Temperature and pressure

Temperatures generally increase with depth into the Earth, therefore the in-situ temperature of any given reservoir formation is closely linked to its depth. Temperature has a marked effect on the activity of microbes. Based on microbial experiments done as part of the investigations at the Lehen site, an optimal temperature window of 45 ± 15 °C was identified for methanogenesis. However, it is likely that successful microbial methanogenesis is also possible at temperatures up to 90 °C, as extremophile methanogens are known to exist in the subsurface. The understanding of these microbes and the conditions under which they thrive are currently poorly constrained. For the present initial appraisal of the potential of the SMB for geo-methanation we thus only considered the temperature interval 30 to 60 °C, for which ample experimental data is available from BOKU.

Fluid pressure, whether of the injected gas or the existing formation fluid, also depends

on the depth of the reservoir. However, no positive or cautionary indicators are listed in Table 2.1. This is because the quantitative and qualitative effects of pressure variations on microbes are still unknown. Long-term tests at the Lehen site conducted during 2021 suggest that a reduction in pressure inside the formation had an invigorating effect on the microbial consortium. At present it is unclear if the increase in microbial activity was directly caused by the pressure variations or by the movement of formation water into and out of the reservoir rock and wells in response to the pressure fluctuations. From a purely economic standpoint, drilling to greater depths is costly and high in-situ pressures require more energy for compression and injection of the gases. However, no calculations of economically critical or ideal pressures have been conducted yet and therefore pressure is currently not listed in the table of criteria for geo-methanation suitability.

2.1.3 Mineralogy

The mineralogy of the reservoir primarily affects the composition of the formation water and is in turn affected by changes in water composition due to dissolution of the injected gases. The first aspect is of concern in reservoirs capped by or containing evaporite rocks. The sulphate minerals (e.g., anhydrite CaSO_4 and gypsum $\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) and halide minerals (e.g., halite NaCl , sylvite KCl) present in such evaporites have high aqueous solubilities and result in an in-situ porewater that is unfavourable to microbial activity (Section 2.2). The second aspect is that injection of CO_2 typically acidifies the porewater with which it comes into contact. Any calcite or other carbonate minerals in the reservoir may therefore undergo slight degrees of dissolution, which may enhance permeability. As the amount of carbonate dissolution is small, it is unlikely to cause mechanical instabilities in the reservoir rock.

2.1.4 Porosity

Knowledge of the connected (gas-accessible) porosity of a formation is crucial to calculate its storage capacity. However, the value of the porosity provides little information on how easy it is to inject or extract fluids from the formation. Therefore, positive and cautionary indicators for permeability were defined as well. The experience of RAG shows that permeabilities of as little as 50 mD are sufficient for injection of gas into a reservoir. They also found that values of over 3000 mD were disadvantageous, especially in siliciclastic reservoirs, as the high injection/extraction rates led to mechanical erosion and disaggregation of the reservoir rock near the wellbore.

2.2 In-situ porewater criteria

While the reservoir is filled with gas in a geo-methanation scenario, there will always be a residual amount of original formation water present (termed the irreducible water saturation) present. This residual water is essential to the success of the geo-methanation technology, because all the microbial processes take place in this water film and thus its composition has a marked effect on microbial activity. A key factor is the pH of the water. Microbes are relatively sensitive to acidic or alkaline pH and only thrive under more or less neutral conditions (pH = 6 to 9). They are also sensitive to certain ions in solution. Investigations at Lehen showed that microbial activity stopped once the well was flushed with a KCl solution such that a concentration of potassium of 10 g/L was reached. Apparently, the inhibiting effect is due to the high concentration of the potassium ion itself, rather than to the increase in salinity, as potassium renders membrane transport into the microbe cells less effective. The toxicity of potassium for certain methanogens was investigated by Chen and Cheng (2007). They found that at concentrations > 3 g/L potassium, the efficiency of methanogenesis significantly decreased.

Besides the potassium concentration, overall salinity has an effect on microbial activity as well. Previous studies have reported an upper limit of 150 g/L for bio-methanation (Strobel et al., 2020). The cautionary limit of < 30 g/L was chosen as this concentration is the limit between a brackish and a saline groundwater. Saline groundwaters are otherwise preferred for geo-methanation as they have no potentially conflicting uses as drinking or process water.

2.3 Permeability and retention criteria

The gas mixture that forms during geo-methanation operations (consisting of H₂, CO₂ and CH₄) is extremely buoyant and has low viscosity. These properties render the gas highly mobile in the subsurface. However, successful geo-methanation requires the gas mixture to remain at or close to the injection well in order to facilitate maximum extraction of the newly formed methane. The reservoir thus needs to consist of a porous rock matrix for gas storage, rather than a network of fractures and/or karst features. While the latter often show the desired high permeabilities, they are highly heterogeneous and show a large contrast in transport properties between the rock matrix and the fractures. Gas injected into such an aquifer will be transported nearly exclusively along the fractures, resulting in a highly erratic shape of the storage plume. This causes issues in retention and recovery of the product methane.

To ensure storage periods of several months and to trap the cushion gas over decades, the reservoir requires a caprock. This acts as a seal to prevent advective escape of the gases towards the surface. Such a caprock must not only be mechanically intact (i.e., unfractured)

but also impermeable to gases (CO_2 , CH_4 and H_2). It also needs to be directly above/surrounding the reservoir in question in order to ensure that the injected gases and produced methane remain at or near the injection site. For relatively flat lying or continuously dipping formations, hydrodynamic trap structures are needed to prevent the gases from migrating laterally away from the injection and production wells as this can occur even under small hydraulic gradients and in only slightly inclined strata. Stratigraphic and anticlinal traps (Figure 2.1) are preferred. Fault traps are also suitable if the faults are impermeable (e.g. due to clay fillings) and the offset places the reservoir formation against a sealing rock formation (Figure 2.1). However, many faults are highly permeable (e.g. little to no fillings). Even if the presence of a fault can be deduced, e.g. from seismic surveys, its permeability can normally only be determined by hydraulic testing from nearby wells.

Figure 2.1: Types of gas traps. For geo-methanation, anticlinal or stratigraphic traps are preferred (*Encyclopædia Britannica® Online*).

3 Geological background and sources of information

3.1 Brief introduction to the geology of the Swiss Molasse Basin (SMB)

The oldest rocks in Switzerland belong to the crystalline basement. Within the basement, small pull-apart basins filled with Late Palaeozoic sediments (304 to 252 Ma old) can be found. Together, they are covered by sediments deposited during the Mesozoic era (Triassic to Cretaceous periods). In the Triassic (252 to 201 Ma ago), sandstones, dolomites and evaporites were deposited under fluvial to shallow marine and sabkha-type conditions. During the Jurassic (201 to 145 Ma ago) and Cretaceous (145 to 65 Ma ago), the area we know as Switzerland today was covered by a sea with water depth (and thus depositional conditions) changing over time. The resulting deposits are therefore a relatively heterogeneous succession of carbonates, shales and claystones and are often laterally variable due to syn-sedimentary tectonic activity. Overall, the thickness of the Mesozoic sediments ranges from 200 to 1000 m (Figure 3.1).

Sedimentation was largely interrupted when the Alpine orogeny started during the Upper Cretaceous (ca. 40 Ma ago). The continental collision led to an overall uplift of the area and the erosion of the Lower Cretaceous and/or Upper Jurassic sediments. The weight of the growing mountain chain bent the European plate downwards, creating the North Alpine Foreland Basin (NAFB) along the northern edge of the Alps between Savoy (France) in the west and Linz (Austria) in the east. To the north, a gentle bulge where the Jura Mountains would start forming at a later stage developed. The part of the NAFB located within modern day Switzerland is the Swiss Molasse Basin (SMB; Figure 3.2), which underlies the relatively flat midlands (also known as the Swiss Plateau) between the Alps and the Jura Mountains. The SMB is roughly 300 km long from west to east. In the Geneva area, it is only 30 km wide (Geneva Basin GGB). Towards the east, the width increases and in the area of Lake Constance, the SMB is about 80 km wide.

Figure 3.1: Simplified lithostratigraphy of the SMB. Formation names and colours are given according to the recommendations of the Swiss Committee for Stratigraphy (SKS; names in bold type). Names used in older literature are listed in column labelled “Classic”. Both nomenclatures are heavily based on the formations occurring in northern Switzerland (Jordan & Deplazes, 2019) and might not be representative across the entire SMB. Names given in the last column are used in this report (Chapter 4).

In this basin, clastic sediments (primarily sandstones, mudstones and conglomerates) were deposited in two megacycles, each recording the transition from a transgressive (marine) to a regressive stage (terrestrial, freshwater). The overall thickness ranges from a few hundred meters in the NE of Switzerland to around 5500 m in the SE. The Molasse deposits at the southern margin of the SMB (approx. 5–20 km from the Alpine front) are folded and thrust, and

are referred to as the Subalpine Molasse. The more distal Molasse sediments are flat-lying and denoted as the Plateau Molasse (Kuhlemann & Kempf, 2002). They have seen relatively little deformation. Nevertheless, they are cut by numerous faults and fault zones as well as folded into anticlines.

Figure 3.2: Tectonic map of Switzerland and the surrounding areas (modified after Pfiffner, 2021) showing the Jura Mountains (light blue), Swiss Molasse Basin (SMB; yellow) including the Subalpine Molasse (light orange) along the Alpine front and the different zones of the Alps in purple, green and shades of red. Only the area of the SMB will be assessed for its suitability for geo-methanation in this study.

Underneath these Molasse deposits, the Mesozoic strata are present, dipping towards the SW at around 3-4° (Figure 3.3). They were compacted during burial but remained relatively unaffected by deformation or metamorphic overprint. Only along the southern edge of the Jura Mountains they are folded and faulted (Subjurassic Zone). In addition, there are important corridors of major and locally active strike-slip faults (e.g. near Fribourg) that cross the basin in N-S trends and often crosscut the Tertiary and some or all of the Mesozoic sediments (c.f. Figures 4.11 and 4.12). However, between these deformed zones, large volumes of the sedimentary rocks appear to be intact and hence potentially of interest for gas storage.

The situation is very different for the Mesozoic sediments making up the Jura Mountains (Figure 3.2 and 3.3). From 10 to 3 Ma, the main stage of the Folded Jura Mountain formation was taking place. During this time, the Upper Triassic to Jurassic/Cretaceous sediments were sheared off the older underlying rocks along the ductile evaporitic deposits of Middle to Upper Triassic age (= décollement horizons) and bent into large-scale folds. This led to the

formations becoming dissected by faults and fracture networks. These structures cut across formation boundaries, and hence reduce the volumes and retentivity of any potential reservoirs for gas storage. We therefore excluded the Jura Mountains in this first appraisal for the geological potential of the Swiss subsurface for geo-methanation.

Figure 3.3: Cross-section from the southern margin of the Jura Mountains (NNW; Bözingenberg) to the Alpine front (SSE, Lake Thun), across the entire SMB along the Biel/Bienne-Bern-Thun line. The Mesozoic strata are shown in orange/pink (Triassic), purple (Lower Jurassic), brown (Middle Jurassic) and blue (Upper Jurassic). They are folded and faulted in the Jura Mountains but relatively undisturbed across the SMB. Above the Mesozoic strata are the Lower Freshwater Molasse (peach colour) and the Upper Marine Molasse (olive green colour). Both increase in thickness from north to south towards the Alpine front. The Molasse sediments are faulted in the subjurassic and subalpine zones.

The rocks making up the Alps today (Figure 3.2) have seen even more substantial deformation. In addition, many of the formations have been buried to great depths during the Alpine orogeny and their texture and mineralogy has been modified by metamorphism. This resulted in rocks with very low matrix porosities and permeabilities and abundant faulting and fracturing. Some of these fracture networks are known to permit water flow over many kilometres and even to ~10 km depth (Diamond et al., 2018). The rocks of the Alpine domain are thus unsuitable for the injection, extraction or storage of fluids, and are excluded from further discussion.

In view of these regional-scale geological features, our study focuses exclusively on the SMB. This region represents a large potential target area, and it underlies the most intensely

populated and industrialized area of Switzerland, a coincidence that favours commercial implementation of geo-methanation schemes.

3.2 Knowledge of the subsurface in the SMB

Exploration for oil and gas has been underway at fluctuating levels of activity since 1912. Between the mid-1950s and 2010, some 32 deep (> 500 m) exploration wells were drilled and more than 8'500 km of seismic lines were shot across the SMB (Figure 3.4; Lahusen, 1992; Leu, 2012). However, only a small gas field (74 Mio. m³) was found and exploited in Entlebuch (Vollmayr and Wendt, 1987). Many unproductive wells nevertheless showed hydrocarbon shows at different geological levels, e.g. oil shows in the Staffelegg and Klettgau Formations (primarily in central and eastern Switzerland) and gas shows in the USM, throughout the Jurassic strata and in the Muschelkalk Group (Leu, 2012 and references therein). These shows are of great interest as they identify formations potentially acting as reservoirs.

The lack of commercial production means that the acquired well data are the main asset of the investors, and so access to the majority of the data is still restricted. Some of the available subsurface data from petroleum exploration, primarily thickness, porosity and permeability values, have been compiled as part of a first appraisal of the SMB for CO₂ sequestration in deep saline aquifers (Chevalier et al., 2010).

Besides oil and gas exploration, the subsurface of the SMB has primarily been investigated as part of the search for a deep geological repository for radioactive waste by the National Cooperative for the Disposal of Radioactive Waste (Nagra). The first extensive exploration program was conducted in the 1980s and consisted of extensive seismics and 6 deep wells in Northern Switzerland (eastern end of the Tabular Jura to the Zürich Unterland). The exploration was later extended east into Canton Schaffhausen and Zürcher Weinland with more seismics and an additional deep well as the focus shifted from the crystalline basement as a potential host formation to the Opalinus Clay. Besides the data collected from the deep wells, Nagra also compiled detailed information from shallower wells, tunnels as well as outcrops in the Tabular and easternmost Folded Jura. Together this lead to a detailed understanding of the different lithologies, their lateral and vertical distribution as well as their mineralogical and chemical composition and petrophysical properties in Northern Switzerland. The most up to date compilation of this information is given in Jordan & Deplazes (2019).

Figure 3.4: Map of all the seismic lines shot and wells drilled to > 500 m depth before 2017 within the Swiss Molasse Basin and the adjacent Jura Mountains. Wells drilled since 2017 (Section 3.2) are marked in yellow. Red well markers indicate that the data obtained are not publicly available, while green markers indicate wells where at least some data are publicly available via the federal geoportal (map.geo.admin.ch).

In the last decade, the subsurface has also received renewed attention in relation to the transition from fossil to renewable and green energies (e.g. geothermal, thermal energy and gas storage, CCS) and for underground civil engineering projects (e.g. tunnel construction). Several new deep wells have been drilled for a range of projects (mostly geothermal). However, similarly to the oil and gas exploration in the last century, most of the data was collected by private companies and is not publicly available. To improve the situation, all projects (co-) funded by the federal administration since the late 2000s have to supply some geological data to Swisstopo. Some of the publicly available information can be found via the federal geoportal (map.geo.admin.ch). However, there is at present no coherent format for the data obtained. In addition, it is unclear if all of the data has been made publicly available and, for more recent projects, when the data will be made available.

Based on all of these exploration campaigns and projects, Chevalier et al. (2010) defined three classes of exploration maturity within the SMB (Figure 3.5): Largely unexplored areas (red) with very little information available, areas with moderate density of well and seismic data (yellow) and the best explored areas with comparatively abundant information in the NE of the SMB, the central part between Fribourg and Olten, and the Lausanne–Yverdon area. In

these well explored areas, the geology (i.e. which lithologies are present and the depth intervals they occur at) are well constrained due to seismics. In addition, these areas contain most of the wells drilled for exploration (petroleum, nuclear waste disposal and geothermal) and where data is, at least partially, publicly available. These areas are thus the most favourable regions for future projects as the higher degree of understanding of the subsurface reduces the exploration risk.

Figure 3.5: Exploration maturity of the Swiss Molasse Basin with the ongoing exploration campaigns described in Section 3.2.1 indicated in grey (modified after Chevalier et al., 2010).

3.2.1 Ongoing and future data collection campaigns

As previously discussed, only exploration related to the disposal of radioactive waste and the energy transition have been conducted in Switzerland in recent years. Currently two major exploration campaigns as well as multiple smaller ones are ongoing with the same purpose (Figure 3.5).

Site investigation for the geological disposal of radioactive waste

This exploration campaign focuses on the geology of the Mesozoic strata in NE Switzerland and it is being conducted by the Swiss National Cooperative for the Disposal of Radioactive Waste (Nagra). The focus of the campaign is the highly impermeable Opalinus Clay and the surrounding strata (“Rahmengesteine”), especially the Lower Jurassic and Upper Triassic aquifers. The campaign includes extensive exploration (2D and 3D seismic surveys) and drilling of eight new deep wells (TBO wells) in 2020/21 in three siting regions (from east to west): Zürich Nordost, Nördlich Lägern and Jura Ost (Figure 3.6). For each well, the entire Mesozoic section was cored and data on mineralogy, structures and hydrogeology were collected. All data will be made publicly available. So far, the Data Reports are available for 5 out of 9 wells

(Nagra, 2021a, 2021b, 2021c, 2022a, 2022b). The remaining reports will be published over the course of the next year.

This exploration campaign is relevant to our project, as Northern Switzerland now represents the area of the SMB and the adjacent Jura Mountains which has been studied most extensively. This strongly reduces the exploration risk for any potential geo-methanation project. In addition, the Tertiary Molasse sediments in the studied areas are absent/thin resulting in most of Mesozoic and even some of the Palaeozoic strata to fall within the required depth-temperature range for geo-methanation. This increases the number and type of potential target reservoirs substantially. On the downside, it is unclear whether or not additional deep wells will be granted permit within the studied siting regions in the next few decades (operation of final disposal facility not expected before 2050). In early September 2022 Nagra announced that Nördlich Lägern has been chosen as the area most suitable for a final repository. However, the other two regions will be kept as reserves in case future investigations at Nördlich Lägern reveal problematic conditions or the construction and safe operation of a final repository.

Figure 3.6: Map of NE Switzerland showing the three potential siting regions Jura Ost, Nördlich Lägern and Zürich Nordost for geological repositories for nuclear waste as investigated by Nagra. Part of the ongoing site selection process was the recent drilling of several deep wells (red) throughout 2020 and 2021 (provided by Nagra, 2021).

Geothermal exploration in the Geneva Basin

This exploration campaign focuses on the suitability of the entire geology of the Geneva Basin (Quaternary to Palaeozoic deposits; Figure 3.5) for the production of geothermal energy and/or seasonal storage of thermal energy. The exploration is led by the regional energy provider Services Industriels de Genève (SIG) in close cooperation with the Canton du Genève and has been ongoing since the 2010s. For production of hot water, the main targets are the karstified

and fractured Cretaceous and Jurassic limestones. For thermal energy storage, the Upper Jurassic Reef Complexes of the Etiollets Formation are of primary interest as they represent spatially constrained reservoirs (c.f. Section 4.1.8). The exploration campaign involved extensive 3D seismics (results expected 2023) and the drilling of two new deep wells (2018 and 2019) with additional wells currently being planned (2024/2025). The results from the exploration campaign will become publicly available in the near future as they are funded by the Federal Office of Energy. However, when and what the data will include exactly, is currently unknown.

Early on in the program, a PhD thesis was commissioned with the aim to describe and quantify the reservoir properties of the Mesozoic sediments and their distribution in the GGB (Rusillon, 2017). This is of interest for our project as any formation with suitable reservoir properties for geothermal energy production or seasonal energy storage is likely also suitable for geo-methanation - provided it lies within the required depth–temperature interval. The Geneva Basin lies outside the area of both, the geological and temperature models of the SMB. The formations present were thus not included in the maps shown in Chapter X. However, after northern Switzerland, the GGB is probably the best studied area of the SMB. We have therefore included some information on the reservoir formations identified by Rusillon (2017) to the relevant section of Chapter 4.

Thermal energy storage – pilot project *Geospeicher Forsthaus*

Another formation currently under investigation in the framework of thermal energy storage is the Lower Freshwater Molasse in the Bern area (Figure 3.5). Drilling for the pilot project *Geospeicher Forsthaus* led by Energie Wasser Bern and GeoEnergie Suisse is ongoing (started in mid-October 2022). Within the framework of the pilot project, an investigation into the distribution of channel sandstones in the Bern area is ongoing. The results will be made available as an MSc thesis in early 2023. The results of the actual pilot project will also be made publicly available. However, it is currently unclear what kind of data will be available and when.

For our project, the *Geospeicher* project is of great interest. The chosen reservoirs are the laterally confined sandstones of the Lower Freshwater Molasse which are also a potential target for geo-methanation if present in the correct depth–temperature interval. Unfortunately the investigations done within the *Geospeicher* project only cover a relatively small area at shallower depth (max. 500 m) and no new geophysical data will be collected. However, the Tertiary Molasse formations are generally less well studied than the Mesozoic strata and therefore any additional information is of importance in order to assess their reservoir characteristics. In summary, these new exploration campaigns are providing us with a wealth of additional

data – especially on the petrophysical properties of the formations investigated. The data, as far as it has been made available until now, is included in Figure 4.1

The major issue with the ongoing exploration campaigns is that they are all situated in regions of the SMB which are already relatively well studied (green areas in Figure 3.5). They thus do not help to better constrain the large swathes of unexplored or poorly explored areas of the SMB which makes assessing the potential of the entire SMB for a new technology such as geo-methanation difficult. It also potentially leads to increased conflicts with respect to subsurface use as all applications (e.g. geo-methanation, geothermal, heat storage, CCS) will focus on these increasingly well-explored areas where the geological risk is reduced. This can only be avoided if exploration into the red and yellow areas shown in Figure 3.5 is increased. We are currently only aware of two planned exploration campaigns in the SMB - one for geothermal energy in the Canton of Thurgau and one for CCS in the Canton of Aargau. Both campaigns are situated within the green areas in Figure 3.5 and thus fail to increase the overall exploration maturity of the SMB.

3.3 Geological model of the SMB (GeoMol)

Despite the incomplete exploration of the SMB, a 3D geological model has been developed over the last 10+ years (Allenbach et al., 2017). The model is based on a reinterpretation of the *Seismischer Atlas des Schweizer Molassebeckens* (Sommaruga et al. 2012) and profiles from numerous wells. It contains 12 stratigraphic horizons (Table 3.1), covering the entire lithostratigraphy shown in Figure 3.1. The area of the SMB within which GeoMol is defined, is shown in Figure 3.7 (orange line). For the purpose of the present USC-FlexStore project we refer to this as “outer geological perimeter”, e.g. where geological information is available in 3D.

Due to the uncertainties of the underlying data and the large distances over which data has to be interpolated, GeoMol does not represent an accurate depiction of the geology of the SMB. For example, most of the geological horizons included in GeoMol consist of more than one formation and often formations with good (= aquifer) and bad reservoir properties (= seals) are contained within a single horizon (Table 3.1). In addition, in some horizons lateral transitions between formations exist (e.g. Hauptrogenstein to Brown Dogger within the *Dogger* horizon). These are also not considered in GeoMol. In order to subdivide these horizons and determine the distribution of individual formations of interest, additional studies were taken into considerations. The most important ones are (in order of publication): Chevalier et al. (2010) for the distribution of the Hauptrogenstein and the thickness of the Buntsandstein, Reisdorf et al. (2011) for information on the Staffelegg Formation and Jordan et al. (2016) for the Klettgau

Formation.

Figure 3.7: Areas in which the 3D geological model GeoMol (“outer geological perimeter”; in yellow) and the temperature model (“inner geological perimeter”; in red) are defined.

GeoMol also contains a valuable temperature model which represents the interpolation of temperature measurements based on purely conductive heat transport. The data are available as a 3D model as well as various 2D horizons. Among the latter are several isotherms, two of which were used in this study (Section 3.4). The area within which the temperature model is defined is shown in Figure 3.5 (red perimeter). For the USC-FlexStore project we refer to this as the “inner geological perimeter”. It is equal to the area in which the occurrence of potential aquifer formations in the correct depth-temperature interval for geo-methanation was delimited (Section 3.4).

Besides the different geological horizons and the temperature model, GeoMol also includes around 500 faults (normal, reverse and strike-slip). Many of the faults included are relatively small-scale (a few km) and only represented by a single plane. However, other fault zones extend over 20 to 30 km and consist of a complex geometry including different branches (e.g. flower structures) and were simplified for modelling purposes. No synclines/anticlines are included in GeoMol as of yet. However, some structures are included in the maps of the final report of the GeoMol project (as fold axis trace; Allenbach et al., 2017).

Table 3.1: Stratigraphic units (c.f. Figure 3.1) and corresponding layers between horizons modelled in GeoMol. As the layers generally represent entire stratigraphic groups comprising several formations, they often contain one or several aquifers and seals in the same unit.

Stratigraphic unit (see Chapter 4)	Layers in GeoMol			Formations contained in layer (aquifer/aquitard)
	Layer	Top horizon	Bottom horizon	
Upper Freshwater Mol.	OSM	TFels	TOMM	OSM (sandst., congl./mudst.)
Upper Marine Mol.	OMM	TOMM/TFels ¹	TUSM	OMM
Lower Freshwater Mol.	USM	TUSM/TFels ¹	BKän	USM (sandst., congl./mudst.)
Lower Marine Mol.	Not included in model			-
E./L. Cretaceous sedim.	Kreide	BKän	TUMa	Goldberg to Narlay Fm
U. Jurassic sediments	Ob. Malm	TUMa/BKän ²	TLMa	10+ formations, among them the Etiolltes Fm
	Unt. Malm	TLMa	TDo	Wildegge Fm., Bärschwil Fm.
M. Jurassic Dogger Group	Dogger	TDo	TLi	Ifenthal Fm. Hauptrogenstein „Brauner Dogger“ Klingnau Fm. Passwang Fm Opalinus Clay
L. Jurassic deposits	Lias	TLi	TKeu	Staffelegg Fm. (Beggingen Mb. and 10 others)
U. Triassic Keuper Group	Keuper	TKeu	TMus	Klettgau Fm. (Ergolz/Gansingen/Berlingen/Seebi/Gruhal-den/Belchen Mb.) Bänkerjoch Fm.
M. Triassic Muschelkalk Group	Muschelkalk	TMus	BMes	Schinznach Fm. (Stamberg Mb. and 4 others) Zeglingen Fm.
L. to M. Triassic Buntsandstein Group	Combined with Muschelkalk			Kaiseraugst Fm. Dinkelberg Fm.
Permo-Carboniferous sediments	Permo-karbon-trog	BMes	BPK	Weitenau Fm. Pre-Weitenau Fm.
Crystalline basement	BMes/BPK		n/a	No formations differentiated

¹Where overlying Molasse units have been eroded.

²Where Lower Cretaceous limestones have been eroded in the eastern SMB.

Unfortunately, GeoMol does not contain any information on the properties of the geological formations such as mineralogy or porosity and permeability. This information is only available from analysis of samples from or close to the surface and samples/measurements

from deep wells. The data are often highly variable, and so far, nobody has attempted to interpolate the properties between different boreholes and include them in the model. The only exception is the Stamberg Member of the Schinznach Formation where Aschwanden et al. (2019) compiled data from numerous wells to provide extrapolated porosity and permeability data across the SMB. For this study, we primarily relied on the compilation done by Chevalier et al. and the data from new exploration campaigns (Section 3.2.1).

3.4 Delimitation of geological units based on criteria for successful geo-methanation

Each potential sealed aquifer evaluated in Table 3.1 corresponds to a 3D rock body in the subsurface. A primary aim of this study is to delimit the geographical extent of these bodies and quantitatively estimate their depths and thicknesses. The locations of any major faults that transect the bodies must also be identified. Fold axis traces shown by Allenbach et al. (2017) were assumed to be relevant for all formations above the Triassic décollement horizons. Digital delimitation of the target bodies was carried out on a copy of the GeoMol 3D dataset, made available by Swisstopo.

A digital model of the rock body representing each of the horizons was extracted from GeoMol based on the following criteria: (a) must lie deeper than 600 m below the surface and (b) lie between the 30 °C and 60 °C isotherms (Figure 3.8, light brown polygons). A tailored workflow was developed for this study using a query tool in MoveTM software (Petex, v.2019.1). Steps in this process are shown in (Figure 3.8). The resulting delimited bodies and any cross-cutting faults in GeoMol were exported as ZMAP files with a 200 m grid resolution, then imported into a geographic information system software package (ESRI's ArcGis, v.10.8) for further mathematical manipulations. The distances between the upper and lower bounding surfaces of each body were calculated with the 3D Analyst tool 'Raster math' (Figure 3.8d), permitting integration of the enclosed rock volume, and yielding vertical thickness maps of each body at 200 m spatial resolution. The map views for each horizon from GeoMol (Appendix A) represent the starting point to further constrain the areas of interest to geo-methanation. As shown in Table 3.1, GeoMol only contains the main geological units of the SMB and not each formation/member. Therefore, the maps obtained do not show the true extent of the aquifer but a larger area, often including the seal and/or a second aquifer. To display only the formations of interest, the maps were delimited further based on information on thickness and/or lateral transitions between formations and/or members (Section 6).

Figure 3.8: (a) 3D view towards the West showing the land-surface topography in grey (DEM) and the underlying modelled geological units of the Molasse basin. The surfaces dividing geological units have been clipped along the trace of the A–A' cross-section, visible in the front of the diagram. (b) A–A' cross-section view of the horizons. Highlighted by the light brown polygon is the target area that satisfies the required conditions of depth >600 m and $30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \leq T \leq 60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. (c) 3D clipped view towards the West showing the modelled surfaces of the target bodies, including subvertical fault planes (red). The position of cross-section B–B' is visible in the front of the diagram. (d) B–B' cross-section view of the target horizons forming a Top Horizon and a Bottom Horizon of the target area; h represents the vertical distance between the two horizons.

4 Characterisation of individual geological units, hydrogeology and structures

The first step in the appraisal of the Swiss Molasse Basin for geo-methanation is a description of the formations present in the subsurface of Switzerland (incl. Jura Mountains). The stratigraphic column in Figure 4.1 shows all lithological units present in the SMB from the crystalline basement and Permo-Carboniferous, up through the Mesozoic strata (Early Triassic to Early Cretaceous) to the younger Tertiary (Oligocene–Miocene) units. The figure is modified after the study of Chevalier et al. (2010), where the same units were assessed for their potential for geological CO₂ sequestration. The litho- and chronostratigraphic names were adapted based on the recent *Lithostratigraphic Lexicon of Switzerland* (<http://www.strati.ch>) established as part of the HARMOS project (Strasky et al., 2016) and summarised by Jordan and Deplazes (2019). These names are derived from the lithostratigraphy of northern Switzerland. While these descriptions are applicable to the deposits of the northern to central SMB, they are not necessarily transferable to the deposits further south (close to the Alpine front) or in the western part of the SMB. However, better information on the deposits in these areas are not available.

The lateral variations in thickness of the formations are displayed schematically by divergent lines in column 5 of Figure 4.1. The Tertiary units show regional variations in facies and thickness along the short axis of the SMB (N–S line), while the Mesozoic strata show variations along the long axis of the SMB (E–W line). However, local variations in thickness are common due to localised erosion or structures being active during deposition. Similarly, many formations contain a number of different facies deposited coevally. These facies variations are described in the text below and, for some units indicated in column 4 of Figure 4.1.

The information below was compiled from Chevalier et al. (2010), Allenbach et al. (2017), Jordan and Deplazes (2019) for central to NE Switzerland and Rusillon (2017) for the Geneva area unless other references are given.

4.1 Description of geological units

4.1.1 Crystalline basement

The crystalline basement consists of three types of lithologies: the Altkristallin (polymetamorphic ortho- and paragneisses partially of Proterozoic age), Caledonian and Variscan granitic intrusions as well as Palaeozoic sediments (see Section 4.1.2). The crystalline lithologies underlie the entire SMB and are exposed in the Black Forest/Vosgeses as well as the external massifs of the Alps (e.g. Aarmassif). Underneath the northern SMB, the basement has been studied in detail as it has initially been targeted as a potential host rock for the final radioactive waste repository. However, most of the basement is to some extent hydrothermally altered and fractures are abundant (e.g. Thury et al., 1994). Some of these fractures are known to originate in the basement but penetrate the entire sedimentary stack (Figure 3.3). Many of the fracture zones act as discrete water-conducting features, some bringing basement fluids close to the surface (see Section 4.3.1).

4.1.2 Permo-Carboniferous sediments

Within the crystalline basement, numerous basins or troughs opened at the end of the Variscan orogeny across Central and Western Europe (McCann et al., 2006). Nearly 20 such Permo-Carboniferous troughs (PCT) of varying sizes have been postulated across the SMB (Figure 4.2) based on seismic data or the occurrence of small reservoirs of natural gas (e.g. Entlebuch; Vollmayr and Wendt 1987). Additional PCTs in the GGB area have been suggested more recently (Moscariello, 2019, Pullan & Berry, 2019) based on seismo-stratigraphy and oil-geochemistry.

They are all small en-echelon pull-apart basins trending SW–NE. So far only one of these troughs has been confirmed by drilling. The North Swiss Permo-Carboniferous Basin (NSPB) is about 10–20 km wide and more than 100 km long, running ENE–WSW from Upper Swabia (Germany), across the NE corner of the SMB, under the Jura Mountains to the Ajoie district (France). The trough is filled by around 1500 m of sediments of Upper Pennsylvanian (Uppermost Carboniferous) to Upper Permian age. The older Carboniferous strata represent the deposits from an anastomising river system. They consist of multiple fining upward cycles representing the transition from channel facies (pebble conglomerate to coarse sandstones) to clay-rich floodplain deposits.

*Petrophysical properties reported together for Klettgau and Staffelegg Fm. in Chevalier et al. (2010) due to assumed hydraulic connection between the two aquifers. Our compilation suggests that the two should be treated individually. However, data from Chevalier et al. (2010) not available individually. Recent TBO data suggest similar porosities for both formations but permeabilities up to 250 mD for Klettgau Fm. while permeabilities in Staffelegg Fm are several orders of magnitude lower.

Figure 4.1: Stratigraphic column of the Swiss Molasse Basin (SMB) modified after Chevalier et al. (2010). The first four columns show the age, encountered lithologies and their basin-wide distribution and stratigraphic names based on the valid definition and nomenclature of the Swiss Committee for Stratigraphy (SKS). Column 5 shows the basin-wide variations in thickness. Column 6 identifies regional- to local-scale aquifers (blue) and impermeable seals (= caprocks; orange). Ranges of aquifer porosities and permeabilities measured are shown in column 7 and 8.

Individual channel deposits range from the decimetre scale to a maximum of 8.5 m. These fluvial deposits are only present in the centre of the trough. At Weiach they are over 570 m thick but they are assumed to be up to 3 km thick further south. As these Upper Carboniferous deposits have only been encountered in two boreholes, a unique stratigraphic formation has not been defined and they are grouped as Pre-Weitenau Formation.

The overlying Permian Weitenau Formation consists of alluvial fan deposits (breccias and conglomerates). On top of this relatively coarse-grained sequence, fine-grained strata were deposited under arid to semi-arid playa conditions. In some areas this playa succession is covered by the deposits of a second, younger alluvial fan. In total, the Weitenau Formation is likely up to 300 m thick. Overall, the lateral extension of the Permian deposits is much greater than that of the Carboniferous sediments with the Permian deposits largely resting directly on the crystalline basement. This suggests renewed tectonic activity and subsidence, this time related to the collapse of the Variscan mountain chains (McCann et al., 2006).

Figure 4.2: Example of interpreted distribution of Permo-Carboniferous troughs (brown) and high zones (pink) within the crystalline basement (yellow) in the basement of the Swiss Molasse Basin. The large trough in Northern Switzerland, extending into both, southern Germany and France, is the North Swiss Permo-Carboniferous Basin (NSPB). Unpublished map by W. Leu (2008).

4.1.3 Lower to Middle Triassic Buntsandstein Group

The Buntsandstein Group is a stratigraphic group consisting of the Dinkelberg Formation (Jordan, 2016). It is made up of a quartz-rich sandstone deposited by aeolic-fluvial processes in a semi-arid climate. After deposition, the sand was affected by pedogenetic processes that formed nodules of chalcedony and anhydrite, and partial replacement by kaolinite. During

early diagenesis, cementation by quartz and clay minerals occurred and the sulphate nodules redissolved.

The existence of the Buntsandstein Group has been confirmed by drilling along the northern edge of the SMB, wedging out along a line Langenthal–Zürich–Stein am Rhein. In addition, it has been encountered in several wells across the Greater Geneva basin (Do Couto et al., 2021). The average thickness in the SMB is in the range of 10 to 30 m but the formation can be over 100 m underneath the Jura Mountains in NW Switzerland.

4.1.4 Middle Triassic Muschelkalk Group

The Middle Triassic Muschelkalk Group consists of three formations (from bottom to top): Kaiseraugst, Zeglingen and Schinznach Formations (Jordan, 2016).

The base of the Middle Triassic Kaiseraugst Formation in NE-Switzerland consist of a clay-bearing quartz sandstone, similar to the sandstones of the underlying Dinkelberg Formation. Its thickness varies from a few meters up to 60 m locally but is probably around 35 to 40 m on average. Above, or where this basal sandstone is missing, the upper part of the Kaiseraugst Formation consists of dolomitic or calcareous lime- and mudstones including sand lenses (formerly known as “Wellengebirge”). These were deposited in a shallow marine basin. It is likely that the shallow marine basin did not extend to the area of today’s GGB and that the Kaiseraugst Formation is absent. Over time, the shallow marine basin dried out, leading to the deposition of the Zeglingen Formation in a sabkha-type environment. This formation contains gypsum, anhydrite and halite (NaCl) but no sylvite (KCl) (Waber et al., 2014). It was formerly known as “Anhydritgruppe”. In the southwest of the SMB (incl. GGB), the Zeglingen Formation is 150 m thick but towards the NE the thickness decreases to 40 m.

The Schinznach Formation (Pietsch et al., 2016; Adams and Diamond, 2019; Figure 4.3) consists of limestones and, depending on the amount of terrestrial input, marls deposited on a shallow marine carbonate platform. It ranges from 50 to 85 m on average but can reach a thickness of over 100 m. The older members (Leutschenberg, Kienberg and Liedertswil) are calcareous limestones with a thickness of 20 to 60 m. The overlaying Stamberg Member is a dolomitised limestone (formerly known as Trigonodus Dolomite) of 20 to nearly 40 m thickness. This is followed by the marly deposits of the Asp Member (≤ 15 m). Similar members were described in the GGB suggesting that the Schinznach Formation was also deposited across the entire SMB. The variation in thickness of the Middle Triassic formations is due to tectonic activity along pre-existing structures and/or erosional events during.

Members of the Schinznach Fm.

	Asp Mb.	4-15 m	
	Stamberg Mb.	20-40 m	
	Liedertswil Mb.	2-25 m	
	Kienberg Mb.	14-22 m	
	Leutschenb. Mb.	4-10 m	

Figure 4.3: The five distinct Members of the Schinznach Formation (modified after Pietsch et al., 2016) and their thicknesses. The different rock types are shown in different colours (brown: mudstones/marls, blue: carbonates, partially dolomitised). Only the Stamberg Member is an aquifer; the other members show properties between an aquifer and aquitard.

All three formations have been defined in northern Switzerland. However, in the western SMB and especially the GGB it is unclear if all three formations are still present (Rusillon, 2017, Do Couto et al., 2021).

4.1.5 Upper Triassic Keuper Group

The Upper Triassic Keuper Group consists of the Bänkerjoch and Klettgau Formations (Jordan et al., 2016). The Bänkerjoch Formation represents a succession of gypsum and anhydrite, sometimes in alternation with shales and dolomites, formerly known as the “Gipskeuper”. The formation was deposited under (semi)arid conditions in the Germanic Basin. Evaporitic salina to sabkha-type environments were dominant. However, the fossil content in some dolomite and sandstone beds indicate occasional and short-lived marine conditions. The Bänkerjoch Formation is not currently subdivided into individual members and beds. However, a series of marker beds have been observed in most borehole and outcrop sections, suggesting a degree of lateral continuity and homogeneity. In the westernmost SMB, the formation additionally contains massive halite deposits. This suggests that while in the east marine to terrestrial salina or sabkha environments dominated, in the GGB further west a marine connection to the Tethys was present during the Late Triassic.

The formation increases in thickness from 40 m in the NE to about 100 m near Olten and to 150 to 200 m in the SW of the SMB. In the west, these values represent reconstructed depositional thickness values (Sommaruga et al., 2017). Absolute thickness of nearly 1400 m

were observed in several areas. This is due to structural repetition related to the décollement of the Mesozoic strata during the folding of the Jura Mountains. The décollement horizon at the base of the SMB is generally located in salt-rich layers: In W-SW of Switzerland it is primarily located within the Keuper evaporites while in E-NE it occurs in the Muschelkalk anhydrite group (Section 4.4; Sommaruga et al., 2017).

The Klettgau Formation replaces what was formerly known as “Sandsteinkeuper” in northern Switzerland. Further west, coeval deposits are more indicative of evaporitic conditions. They have not yet been assigned a stratigraphic name, however, they are no longer part of the Klettgau Formation. The time span over which the Klettgau Formation was deposited was characterised by several changes in the environment and long periods of non-deposition or erosion. The overall thickness of the Klettgau Formation ranges from 30 to 75 m, and can be subdivided into six members (from bottom to top; Figure 4.4):

- Ergolz Member (formerly “Schilfsandstein” and “Untere Bunte Mergel”; 6-23 m thick): Playa deposits at the base overlain by fluvial deposits from meandering to anastomosing rivers with fine- to medium-grained sandstones (channel facies) embedded in claystone to dolomitic marls (floodplain deposits). The two facies are heterogeneously distributed across the northern SMB.
- Gansingen Member (formerly “Gansinger Dolomite”; 0-7 m thick): Dolomite layer deposited during a marine transgression. Post-depositional dissolution lead to mouldic porosity and cavernous sections in some areas. Lateral transition into Berlingen Member in the Lake Constance area.
- Berlingen Member (formerly “Sandlagen” or “Kieselsandstein”; < 10 m thick): Medium- to coarse-grained sandstone indicating deposition close to the Vindelician High. Concurrent with deposition of the Gansingen Member further west.
- Gruhalde Member (formerly “Obere Bunte Mergel” or “Knollenmergel”; 3-20 m): Predominantly playa-type dolomitic deposits with some fluvial, coarse-grained sandstones. West of Zürich, the Seebi Member is contained within the Gruhalde Member, splitting it into a lower and upper section.
- Seebi Member (formerly “Stubensandstein”; 1-24 m thick): Medium-grained to coarse-grained fluvial sandstones and conglomerates as well as sandy dolomites. Common in the NE of Switzerland. Transition into Gruhalde Member further west.
- Belchen Member (formerly “Rhät”; 0-6 m thick): Quartzitic sandstones with shaly interlayers overlain by marls and claystones with intercalated sandy layers. Deposited in a brackish estuarine to shallow marine environment.

The Belchen Member was also identified in the GGB. Out of the other members only the Ergolz, Gruhalde and Gansingen Members are potentially occurring in the western part of the SMB. The lithologies described by Rusillon (2017) match the composition of these three members: marls, mudstones and dolomite. Their combined thickness is around 20 m which is lower than in Northern Switzerland (30 to 75 m). While the deposits in the GGB are similar to the Klettgau Formation, the formation is officially only defined east of the line Basel-Solothurn (Jordan, 2016). For the remainder of this study, we will focus on the area investigated by Jordan (2016) as outside of this perimeter, nearly no data on the Klettgau Formation are available.

Figure 4.4: The six distinct Members of the Klettgau Formation (modified after Jordan et al., 2016). The different rock types are shown in different colours (brown: mudstones/marls, yellow: sandstones, blue: limestone, partially dolomitised and orange: evaporites). The Seebi, Gansingen, Berlingen and the sandstones of the Ergolz Member are aquifers, while the rest of the Ergolz and the Gruhalden Member are aquitards. The Belchen Member at the top shows properties between aquifer and aquitard.

4.1.6 Lower Jurassic (Liassic) deposits

During the Lower Jurassic (formerly known as Liassic), conditions returned to shallow marine with a strong input of terrigenous material in the central to northern part of today's SMB. The resulting deposits are a highly heterogeneous, siltstone-marl-dominated sedimentary succession with some intercalated limestones and sandstones. In Northern Switzerland, these deposits are combined to form the Staffelegg Formation (Reisdorf et al., 2011). The formation is only defined between the River Doubs – Mount Weissenstein in the west and the Randen Hills in the east. In the easternmost SMB, depositional conditions were different due to the effect of Tethian rifting, leading to deeper basins where primarily marls were deposited. Coevally, limestones and clay-rich units were deposited in western Switzerland. Only the Staffelegg Formation in northern and eastern Switzerland have been investigated in detail and been given a stratigraphic name so far. Therefore, we will focus on this formation for the rest of the section.

The Staffelegg Formation (25 – 50 m) can be subdivided into rocks of Sinemurian age, which make up over 90% of the Staffelegg Formation in Eastern and Central Switzerland, and younger (Pliensbachian and Toarcian) deposits comprising 70% of the Staffelegg Formation in Western Switzerland. One of the older Sinemurian units is the arenitic limestone of the Beggingen member, formerly known as “Arietenkalk”. It is up to 8+ m thick and shows an erosive base, often with a fossil-rich conglomerate or breccia layer, sometimes even Fe-ooids. Thin, intercalated mudstones and marly layers are common as well as interfingering with the calcareous sandstones or sandy limestones of the Weissenstein Member where present (Figure 4.5). Many of the younger members of the Staffelegg Formation are rich in marls and mudstones, suggesting that they are relatively impermeable.

Members of the Staffelegg Fm.

Figure 4.5: The eleven distinct Members of the Staffelegg Formation (modified after Reisdorf et al., 2011). The different rock types are shown in different colours (brown: mudstones/marls, yellow: sandstones, blue: limestone, partially dolomitised). Only the Beggingen Member is an aquifer – the other formations show aquitard characteristics.

The change in depositional environment from shallow marine to deeper basins is reflected by the variable thicknesses of the Lower Jurassic sequence in GeoMol. The model indicates a maximum thickness of sediments of 900 m in the Geneva area. There is a strong decrease across the Canton of Vaud to the central and eastern SMB where the Lower Jurassic is generally less than 50 m thick. Only in this area have the Lower Jurassic deposits been studied well enough to have been assigned a formation name (Staffelegg Formation). Further west the deposits (despite their substantial thickness), are very poorly characterised and thus not included in further evaluation of the Lower Jurassic of the SMB.

4.1.7 Middle Jurassic Dogger Group

The lower part of the Middle Jurassic (Dogger) is the so-called Opalinus clay. It was deposited in a shallow sea from very fine-grained terrigenous detritus. The resulting claystone contains thus layers with higher and lower sand contents. Overall however, it is a very homogeneous, 80 to 150 m thick and laterally continuous formation present across the SMB.

The overlying Middle Dogger strata are very complex as they represent rapid facies changes due to changes in sea level and syn-sedimentary tectonic activity. This results in a relatively large number of different formations (laterally and vertically) deposited in a relatively short time interval. Across the entire basin shallow marine conditions prevailed and detrital input was limited. In the westernmost part of the SMB, primarily limestone and calcareous shales were deposited. These formations have so far not been given an official name and very little data is available. They are therefore not discussed further.

In the central to eastern SMB, the lowermost formation of the Middle Jurassic is the Passwang Formation. It represents a succession of brownish sandy marls, limestones and Fe-oolites deposited in a marine basin with low sedimentation and ubiquitous hardground formation. It is in the range of 40 to 65 m thick. Towards the east the Passwang Formation transitions into the "Murchisonae-Oolith" Formation (sandy marls and claystones, marly limestones and iron oolites; MO in Figure 4.6), the "Wedelsandstein" Formation (silty to fine-grained sandy argillaceous marl; WS in Figure 4.6) and the earliest sections of the "Humphriesi-Oolite" Formation (HO in Figure 4.6).

Above the Passwang Formation, a marked facies transition from west to east can be observed. In the central to western part of the SMB an oolite limestone was deposited on a barrier in a tide-dominated, shallow sea (= Celtic facies). These deposits are known as the Hauptrogenstein. East of the line Gansingen – Schinznach, an off-barrier assemblage developed (= Swabian Basin facies; "Brauner Dogger") where the sedimentation of marls dominated as the basin was deeper and saw more terrigenous input from nearby islands (Klingnau Formation and transition to the "Humphriesi-Oolite" and the "Parkinsoni & Württembergica Schichten" further east; Figure 4.6). The transition between the different facies was not constant over time but shifted laterally due to local changes in circulation as well as variable subsidence rates of different areas within the basin. This resulted in interfingering of the limestones of the Hauptrogenstein with the marls of the Klingnau Formation. The Hauptrogenstein can be up to 110 m thick while the Klingnau Formation shows a maximum of 50 m and the "Humphriesi-Oolite" and the "Parkinsoni & Württembergica Schichten" are generally less than 15 and 35 m thick, respectively.

Figure 4.6: Stratigraphic scheme for the Early Dogger Group in the eastern folded Jura (first column) and eastern SMB (second column; Jordan and Deplazes, 2019).

Above the Hauptrogenstein/Klingnau Formation/“Parkinsoni & Württembergica Schichten”, the Ifenthal Formation (western to central SMB; folded Jura) and Variansmergel and Wutach Formations (eastern SMB) were deposited. The formations consist of an alternation of marl and argillaceous limestones followed by predominantly Fe-oolitic limestone and Fe-oolites. Similarly to the Passwang Formation, they represent deposition in a marine basin with starving sedimentation due to reduced clastic input. The Ifenthal Formation is 0.7 to 60 m thick while the Variansmergel Formation reaches a maximum of 12.5 m and the Wutach Formation only 5 m. According to Allenbach et al. (2017), the entire Dogger sequence ranges from 40 to 600 m in thickness, increasing from southwest to northeast.

4.1.8 Upper Jurassic (Malm) sediments

The Upper Jurassic (Malm) is subdivided into a large number of formations as the depositional environment changed substantially from west to east and over just a few millions of years. The lithologies were deposited on the so-called Jura Platform, a mostly shallow marine carbonate platform. The platform was bordered by a number of topographical highs further north and east (London-Brabant, Rhenisch and Bohemian Massif) as well as southwest (Massif Central), providing siliciclastic input. To the north east and south west, the platform was bordered by deeper marine troughs (Paris and Helvetic basins). Below, trends observed in the eastern SMB/Jura Mountains (Cantons of Schaffhausen/Aargau) as well as the Geneva Basin will be summarised briefly. For a detailed overview of formations present in the north (east) to central

SMB/Jura Mountains see the compilation from Gygi (2013) while the formations in the French Jura are described in detail in Meyer (2000).

In eastern Switzerland, the depositional sequence starts with the Wildegg Formation. Its base consist of a thin sequence of marly limestones deposited during the transgression to the deep Effingen Member basin (Birmensdorf Member). The overlying remainder is made up of the Effingen Member, a thick sequence of marls and some shaly limestones deposited rapidly in the deep basin due to increased terrigenous input. The Wildegg Formation is relatively homogeneous and decreases in thickness from 750 to around 10 m from west to east. During the remainder of the Upper Jurassic, a thick sequence of micritic limestones often with intercalated marly sequences was deposited in more open marine conditions (Swabian Basin facies – Villigen and Schwarzbach Formations as well as the informally named “Felsenkalke/Massenkalke”). The Upper Jurassic limestones in the eastern SMB are around 150 to 300 m thick, decreasing to 50 m in the central SMB.

In western Switzerland, the Upper Jurassic can equally be subdivided into two sequences. A bottom sequence (no formal name given but commonly called “combe oxfordienne”) composed of marl-rich limestones (250 to 450 m) followed by pure carbonates (100 to 450 m; Etiollets and Twannbach Formations). The dark grey, bioclastic marly limestones to marls represent typical pelagic deposits, suggesting that deeper open-marine conditions prevailed during the Oxfordian. In the early Kimmeridgian, the depositional environment changed to a shallow platform setting (Celtic facies) where syndimentary active structures dissected the platform into a number of local highs (where patch reefs formed) and depressions (lagoons). In this highly variable environment, the so called Etiollets Formation was deposited. It can be subdivided into four subunits: (1) Calcaire de Tabalcon, a bioclastic packstone which is often dolomitized and represents the reef front deposits, (2) Calcaires récifaux, boundstone and pack/grainstones rich in reef-building organisms (e.g. corals, sponges and microbial crusts) representing the patch reef bodies and peri-reef deposits, (3) Calcaires plaquetés, laminated wackestones representing the lagoonal deposits between the patch reefs and (4) Calcaires de Landaize, oolitic grainstones, representing back-reef and beach deposits. As the positions of the topographic highs shifted over time, the resulting sequence is highly heterogeneous with a large variability of concomitant facies both laterally and vertically. During the Tithonian, water depth decreased further and a micritic limestone recording tidal influence (e.g. algal mats and desiccation cracks) was deposited (Twannbach Formation).

Based on surface outcrops, the north-eastern-most occurrence of the Etiollets Formation are along a line from St. Cergue in the Jura Vaudois to Gland (Lac Léman). Further (north)east, only the Twannbach Formation is encountered. All formations of Upper Jurassic

age in the western SMB are several hundred meters thick and reach a maximum of nearly 1200 m in the area of Lausanne.

The Upper Jurassic limestones became exposed during the Lower Cretaceous onset of the Alpine orogeny, either before deposition of Cretaceous limestones or after their deposition and subsequent erosion. This resulted in extensive karstification of the surface. Some of these karst pockets were later filled by Eocene clastic deposits of the Siderolithic Group (Jordan & Deplazes, 2019).

4.1.9 Lower (and Upper) Cretaceous sediments

The Lower Cretaceous deposits still largely consist of platform limestones. However, thicker marly limestone intervals become more abundant. The entire sequence can be subdivided into ten formations: Goldberg, Pierre-Châtel, Vions, Chambotte, Vuache, Grand-Esserts and Gorges de l'Orbe, Vallorbe and Perte du Rhône Formations as well as the Upper Cretaceous Narlay Formation (see Strasser et al., 2016 for details). The succession of limestones and marls suggests cyclic variations of environmental conditions in relatively shallow water caused by period sea-level changes. Overall, two cycles of evolution from very shallow to more open marine conditions can be observed. In addition to these two large-scale cycles, the common lateral and vertical facies heterogeneities indicate rapid changes of sedimentary environments and ecological conditions through space and time.

The Cretaceous deposits can be up to 560 m thick. However, they are missing in the eastern half of the SMB (to the east of the line Biel/Bienne – Thun), either because they were never deposited or because they were eroded during uplift in the Upper Cretaceous/Lower Paleogene (onset of the Alpine orogeny). In western Switzerland, the Perte du Rhône and Narlay formations are also largely absent or occur as clasts in Eocene and/or Molasse deposits (Rusillon, 2017). The uplift and subsequent erosion also resulted in extensive karstification of the Cretaceous deposits. Some of these karst pockets were later filled by Eocene clastic deposits of the Siderolithic Group (Jordan & Deplazes, 2019).

4.1.10 Lower Oligocene Lower Marine Molasse (UMM)

The UMM was deposited under marine conditions, resulting in a sequence of clay-rich marls and intercalated sandstones. It is up to 150 m thick. However, its occurrence is restricted to the area immediately to the north of the Alpine front and the deposits taper out north of the line Lausanne – Bulle – Thun.

4.1.11 Upper Oligocene to Lower Miocene Lower Freshwater Molasse (USM)

In the USM, three lithotypes are encountered: a) conglomerates, b) sandstones and c) silt- and mudstones. The conglomerates are present in the proximal realm along the Alpine front. They are mostly clast-supported and massively bedded. Individual beds (a few meters thick) are often amalgamated into conglomerate units of several hundred meters thickness. Individual intercalated sandstone layers and isolated lenses of mudstones are present and while laterally extensive, often only a few meters thick. The deposits are interpreted as river channel deposits of multiple radial alluvial fans whose positions remained relatively stable throughout the deposition of the USM (Figure 4.7).

The majority of the sandstones and mudstones were deposited away from the Alpine front in the more distal areas of the SMB. Sandstone deposits are mostly medium- to coarse-grained (approx. 0.3–2 mm), forming individual (2 – 8 m) or amalgamated beds of up to 50 m. Their lateral extent is uncertain but when uninterrupted, these bodies can extend over hundreds of meters as they sandstones were deposited primarily in river-channels. The mudstones occur as beds up to several meters thickness but more commonly alternating with thin beds of sand- and siltstones. They represent overbank or floodplain deposits of the same alluvial rivers (Figure 4.7; Platt & Keller, 1992).

The USM can be subdivided into two main stages (Berger et al., 2010). During the older stage (USM-I; Lower Chattian), a thick sequence (40 to 800 m) of variegated marls with only few intercalated channel sandstones was deposited across the entire basin. In the eastern SMB this lowest stage is missing as sedimentation only started during the Middle Chattian (Berger et al., 2005). In the western SMB, an important decrease in clastic supply resulted in the deposition of lacustrine sediments (freshwater limestones and gypsiferous marls) during the Upper Chattian. During the Upper Aquitanian (USM-II), marl-rich sequences were deposited along the Jura Mountains as well as in the area of the eastern alluvial fans. In the other areas of the SMB, sandstones became more prevalent. At the top of the USM-II, a thick marly sequence can be found in eastern Switzerland (“Oberaquitanen Mergelzone”) and in the Subjuristic Zone (“Obere Bunte Molasse”). The USM-II was eroded to the west of Lausanne. However, in the remaining SMB it can be up to 1 km thick (Berger et al., 2005). Overall the thickness of the USM is highly N-S dependent. Along the foot of the Jura Mountains, the USM is only a few meters thick, while it reaches around 1500 m in the Plateau Molasse and up to 4000 m in the Subalpine Molasse. A younger stage (USM-III) is similar in appearance to the USM-II but was deposited coevally to the OMM during the Burdigalian transgression.

Figure 4.7: Paleogeographic map of Switzerland and surrounding areas during the deposition of the USM in the Chattian/Aquitainian, OMM in the Burdigalian and OSM in the Langhian and Serravallian. Note the transition from terrestrial/fluviatile to marine and back to terrestrial/fluviatile conditions and the conglomerate fans which are active throughout the deposition of the Molasse sediments (modified after Berger et al., 2005).

4.1.12 Lower Miocene Upper Marine Molasse (OMM)

Similarly to the USM described above, three lithotypes can be encountered in the OMM: a) conglomerates, b) sandstones and c) silt- and mudstones. The conglomerates represent deposition in deltaic fans extending from the Alpine front into the shallow sea which had formed in the SMB at the beginning of the Burdigalian. Compared to the USM, fewer conglomerate fans were active and they extended less far into the basin (Figure 4.7). Similarly to the USM, sand- and mudstones are intercalated in these formations.

The dominant lithotype within the OMM is sandstone with more or less frequent and thick mudstone layers, depending on the position within the basin and time (Strunck & Matter, 2002). Sandstones are generally amalgamated and form units of several tens of meters. The OMM is subdivided into two stages (Figure 4.8), OMM-I and -II (Berger et al., 2010). OMM-I encompasses the classical “Sense-Formation” (western SMB) and “Lucerne-Formation” (eastern SMB), characterized by large-scale amalgamations of sandstones with mudstone interbeds. OMM-II encompasses the classical “Belpberg-Formation” (western SMB) and “St. Gallen-Formation” (eastern SMB), consisting of sandstone-rich sequences as well as sandstone-mudstone alternations. The lateral variation within these two formations is relatively high.

The thickness of the OMM ranges from around 900 m along the Alpine front to only a few tens of meters along the foot of the Jura Mountains. It slightly increases in thickness from west to east. Due to uplift during the late stages of the Alpine orogeny, the OMM has been eroded to the west of Lausanne and close to the Jura Mountains.

4.1.13 Upper Miocene Upper Freshwater Molasse (OSM)

In the OSM, three lithotypes are encountered: a) conglomerates, b) sandstones and c) silt- and mudstones. The conglomerates are present in the proximal realm along the Alpine front. They are mostly clast-supported and massively bedded. Individual beds (a few meters thick) are often amalgamated into conglomerate units of several hundred meters thickness. Individual intercalated sandstone layers and isolated lenses of mudstones are present and while laterally extensive, often only a few meters thick. The deposits are interpreted as river channel deposits of multiple radial alluvial fans (Napf, Hörnli and Bodensee) whose positions remained relatively stable throughout the deposition of the OSM (Figure 4.7). During periods of low sedimentary input, the fluvial sediment became increasingly more fine-grained and lakes and swamps developed, leading to the deposition of lacustrine marls and limestones as well as coal beds. Such a unit forms the base of the OSM (OSM-I). It was followed by a period with periodically higher sedimentary input which led to an increase in the abundance of channel sandstones, alternating sequences of sandstones and marls and an overall decrease in lacustrine and swamp deposits (OSM-II). Compared to the USM, the OSM is often more marly and less sandstone-rich (only about 10%; Gander, 2004). The lower abundance of sandstones likely results in a lower lateral and vertical interconnectedness of sandstones.

The thickness of the OSM decreases from around 1500 m along the Alpine Front to less than 400 m in the distal parts of the basin.

4.2 Reservoir properties

In the stratigraphic column (Figure 4.1), units are coloured according to their reservoir properties: Aquifers are blue, indicating that porosity and permeability are sufficient to allow for the injection/extraction of a fluid. Seals are orange and are characterised by petrophysical properties which do not allow for any substantial movement of fluid. Units in white show properties between an aquifer and a seal and are not considered further.

In the following section, the reservoir properties of all potential reservoirs (blue) are discussed. In addition, the properties of the overlying unit and (where this unit is not a seal)

the next formation with known good sealing properties are discussed. We also list where additional data has been compiled or measured in recent years to expand the understanding of the reservoir properties of individual formations. The main source of new data is the Nagra TBO campaign (Section 3.2.1). So far, 5 out of 9 reports have been published (Nagra, 2021a, 2021b, 2021c, 2022a, 2022b). Where no new data was added, the values are identical with the ones reported in Chevalier et al. (2010).

4.2.1 Crystalline basement

The crystalline basement is a fractured aquifer with a bimodal distribution of petrophysical properties. The intact rock matrix is relatively impermeable (10^{-13} to 10^{-9} m s⁻¹) while fracture zones can be water-conducting with hydraulic conductivities of up to 10^{-4} m s⁻¹ (Stober & Bucher, 2007). Different types of veins suggest that the basement has a long history of circulating hot fluids and individual fault zones can extend over large vertical and horizontal distances.

The basement is sealed by the low-permeability floodplain-deposits of the Pre-Weitenau Formation or the playa-deposits of the Weitenau Formation, depending on which formations are present. Where no Palaeozoic deposits are present and the basement is overlain directly by Triassic sediments, the crystalline basement is likely hydraulically connected with the Buntsandstein aquifer. No new data on the crystalline basement was obtained from any of the recent/ongoing exploration campaigns.

4.2.2 Permo-carboniferous sediments

Within the crystalline basement, Permo-Carboniferous troughs are present. Unfortunately, little to no petrophysical data are available for the Palaeozoic units and therefore assessing the reservoir properties of these lithologies is difficult. Similarities in the depositional environment of the Pre-Weitenau channel sandstones to the channel sandstones of the Klettgau Formation (Section 4.1.5), USM (Section 4.1.11) and OSM (Section 4.1.13) suggest that these units could act as local to regional porous-matrix aquifers.

Similarly to other formations where channel sandstones are present within fine-grained floodplain deposits (e.g. Klettgau Formation or USM/OSM), the Pre-Weitenau Formation can be described as small-scale reservoirs directly embedded in a potential seal unit. However it is difficult to assess the quality of the seal as the petrophysical properties of the floodplain deposits and the lateral extent of the individual channel sandstone bodies and their

connectivity are unknown. If the floodplain deposits do not possess adequate sealing properties, the channel sandstones in the top of the Pre-Weitenau Formation, if they are directly overlain by the Permian playa deposits, might still represent suitable reservoirs.

Another option within the NSPB are the alluvial fan deposits of the Permian Weitenau Formation which are likely sealed by the slightly younger playa deposits. Both are distributed across a larger area compared to the Carboniferous deposits. However, no petrophysical data are available for these units and thus their suitability as aquifers and seals respectively cannot be assessed. They are therefore not considered any further.

Very little porosity data and no new permeability data was obtained for the Weitenau Formation as part of the TBO campaign.

They fall within the range reported by Chevalier et al. (2010; Figure 4.9). No new data on the Pre-Weitenau Formation was collected.

4.2.3 Buntsandstein Group

The Buntsandstein Group shows laterally variable cementation by quartz and clay minerals. This results in highly variable porosities between 3 and 18 vol.% with an average around 10 vol.%. The same is observed for permeabilities with values ranging from 0.5 to 400 mD with an average of around 200 mD. The Buntsandstein Group thus represents a good porous-matrix aquifer of regional extent. The lowermost unit of the Kaiseraugst Formation in the eastern part of the SMB (area of Lake Constance) is also a quartz sandstone. Its thickness varies from a few meters up to 60 m locally. The petrophysical properties are similar to the Buntsandstein and vary according to the clay content of the formation. Due to their similarities and presumed hydraulic connection, the two sandstones are treated as one composite aquifer and the term "Buntsandstein" is used for both.

The Kaiseraugst Formation is directly overlying the Buntsandstein Group. The heterogeneous succession of dolomites, limestones and marls is not considered an overall good seal. Locally, mudstone- and marl-rich sequences might seal the Buntsandstein well. However, where more carbonaceous deposits prevail, the sealing properties are questionable. The data from the GGB suggest that in the westernmost SMB the Kaiseraugst Formation is missing and that the Buntsandstein Group is directly overlain by impermeable evaporites (Zeglingen Formation?). It is therefore possible that the Buntsandstein Group is well sealed in the western SMB but less so in northern and eastern Switzerland. Unfortunately, no information on where the Kaiseraugst Formation is tapering out laterally is available.

Very little porosity data and no new permeability data was obtained for the Dinkelberg

Formation as part of the TBO campaign but they fall within the range reported by Chevalier et al. (2010; Figure 4.9).

4.2.4 Muschelkalk Group

Within the Muschelkalk Group, only part of a single member shows aquifer properties: The Stamberg Member which extends across, at least, the entire northern part of the SMB from the GGB to Lake Constance (Section 4.1.4). Partial dolomitisation of the Stamberg Member resulted in high porosities of around 20 vol.%. Matrix permeabilities are very low throughout most of the SMB (< 60 mD) owing to progressive compaction upon deeper burial towards the Alpine Front. However, in the north of the basin, values of up to 1000 mD have been measured (Aschwanden et al., 2019a). This strong increase is due to sub-regional dissolution of diagenetic anhydrite nodules (Aschwanden et al., 2019b), small-scale karstification and fracturing around faults, resulting in an increase of hydraulic transmissivity of several orders of magnitude (10^{-3} to 10^{-7} m² s⁻¹). In these areas, the Stamberg Member represents a promising (sub)regional aquifer.

In the GGB very low porosities (< 2 vol.%) and permeabilities (approx. 5 mD) have been reported (Rusillon, 2017). It has to be assumed that these are values for the entire Middle Triassic (i.e. including some evaporitic deposits) and not specifically from the Stamberg Member. The Stamberg member is well-sealed by the evaporites of the Bänkerjoch Formation, especially in western Switzerland where the Bänkerjoch Formation additionally includes salt formations.

Additional porosity and permeability data for the Stamberg Member were collected from each of the new TBO wells. They all fall within the range reported by Chevalier et al. (2010; Figure 4.9), confirming the good reservoir properties of the formation.

4.2.5 Klettgau Formation

A hydraulic connection between the sandstones of the Klettgau Formation and the arenitic limestones of the Beggingen member of the Lower Jurassic Staffelegg Formation has been assumed in previous studies. This is probably linked to numerous good oil shows in both, the Klettgau and Staffelegg Formations (Leu, 2012). This is why Chevalier et al. (2010) report porosity and permeability values for the members of the Klettgau Formation and the Beggingen Member of the Staffelegg Formation together (5 to 15 vol.% and 0.5 to 100 mD). However, the presence of the marly Gruhalde Member near the top of the Klettgau Formation suggest that this link is potentially only established locally or not at all. For the remainder of this study, the two units are therefore treated as small, unconnected aquifers.

Figure 4.8: Porosity (left) and permeability (right) data for Nagra-TBO wells at Bözberg-1 and-2, Bülach, Marthalen and Trüllikon. Locations of wells shown in Figure 3.6. Individual measurements are shown for three siting regions (◇: Jura Ost, ○: Nördlich Lägern, □: Zürich Nordost). Averages of porosity in each formation in each well are indicated by black horizontal bars. For the permeability data (from hydrotests), lowest estimates (min. values) and highest estimate (max.) are plotted. The previously compiled data ranges from Chevalier et al. (2010) are shown in grey boxes.

The Klettgau Formation is highly heterogeneous, consisting of six members, several of which show lateral transitions into one another from west to east. However, data on the porosity and permeability values of each member are lacking as data is often reported as “Klettgau Formation”/“Sandsteinkeuper” rather than identifying/reporting the member the analysis was done on. Therefore, the assessment of which members are (not) suitable as reservoirs will be based on lithological consideration as well as the number of water samples reported for each unit, assuming that a high number of samples positively correlates with permeability.

The marly sections of the Klettgau Formation (oldest Ergolz Member and the entire Gruhalde Member) are likely the units with least suitable reservoir properties. This is confirmed by the absence of water samples from these members as reported by Waber et al. (2014). The lithologies of the Gansingen (dolomite with mouldic porosity – similar to the Stamberg

Member of the Schinznach Formation) and the Belchen Member (sandstone) suggest good reservoir properties. However, only very few water samples could be taken from these units which suggests that permeability of these units is too low for the injection/extraction of a fluid. On the other hand, the sandstones of the Ergolz, Seebi and Berlingen Members are assumed to show good reservoir properties, based on the numerous water analyses taken from these samples. The members of the Klettgau Formation showing reservoir properties will be called SBEG Members for the remainder of the report.

Sealing can be assessed for each of the potentially suitable reservoirs (from bottom to top):

- Ergolz Member: As channel sandstones embedded in floodplain deposits, they potentially represent small-scale, sealed reservoir bodies. However, similarly to the sandstones of the Pre-Weitenau Formation, the properties and distribution of the two lithotypes are poorly characterised.
- Gansingen and Berlingen Member: Sealed by a 2 – 20 m thick marly interval (lower Gruhalde Member). Due to the unknown sealing properties of the marls, a thicker sequence is preferential.
- Seebi Member: Where present, the sandstones are surrounded by the Gruhalde Member (below: 2 – 20 m, above: 5 – 30 m) and thus likely relatively well sealed.

The members of the Klettgau Formation showing seal properties will be called EGh Members for the remainder of the report.

Additional porosity and permeability data for the Klettgau Formation were collected from each of the new TBO wells (Figure 4.9). However, the data was only assigned to the Klettgau Formation rather than a specific member. The new data suggest that the porosity range given by Chevalier et al. (2010) can be extended upwards to 19 vol.% while the permeability has to be extended downwards to include values as low as $5e-7$ mD. The reason for this very low value, which several orders of magnitude lower than the previously reported minimum, is the method by which it was derived. Permeability data can be obtained from drill core samples by drilling out small subcores called “plugs” (\varnothing 2.5 cm) and then analysing their permeability in the laboratory. This is the most common method in the exploration for oil and gas and how most of the permeability data reported by Chevalier et al. (2010) were obtained. While this gives an accurate number, the value only refers to a small volume of rock rather than the entire formation. In addition, plugs are generally drilled from relatively homogeneous sections of the rock, i.e. avoiding large pores or fractures to ensure representability of the sample. In reality however, these features are often the ones affecting, even controlling the permeability of the entire formation. This is especially true in rocks with relatively low matrix

porosity and permeability such as carbonates. The more reliable data on formation permeability is thus derived from packer tests. For such a test, a tool is inserted into a well which allows to temporarily seal off a depth interval hydraulically. The pressure within the interval is then increased/reduced by injection/pumping and the time required for the pressure to return to formation conditions is measured. This allows to test the permeability of a formation over several meters and thus include the effect of large(r) scale features such as large pores and/or fractures avoided when measuring plugs. The values obtained in this way are generally higher than the permeability obtained from plugs and also more representative of the entire formation. For highly heterogeneous sequences however, a test interval often contains different lithotypes, e.g. sand- and mudstone. This will result in measured permeability values which are often lower than the plug permeability. The difference between the new permeability data and the plug permeabilities reported by Chevalier et al. (2010; Figure 4.9) is therefore not surprising.

4.2.6 Staffelegg Formation

Similarly to the Klettgau Formation, data on the porosity and permeability values of each member are lacking as data is often reported as “Staffelegg Formation”/“Lias” rather than identifying/reporting the member the analysis was done on. Therefore, the assessment of which members are (not) suitable as reservoirs will be based on lithological consideration as well as the number of water samples reported for each unit, assuming that a high number of samples positively correlates with permeability.

Besides the Beggingen (and possibly Weissenstein Member), all other lithologies are marl-dominated, suggesting poor reservoir qualities. Previous work done in Northern Switzerland had identified the Beggingen Member as an aquifer. However, in the most recent compilation there are only very few groundwater analyses reported from the Staffelegg Formation (Waber et al., 2014). This suggests that the Beggingen Member is either heterogeneously distributed or does not show aquifer properties everywhere.

As described previously, the younger members of the Staffelegg Formation are rich in marls and mudstones, suggesting that they are relatively impermeable and could act as a seal the Beggingen/Weissenstein Member. Despite the possible sealing properties, the lateral discontinuity of most members and the overall highly heterogeneous nature of the formation makes its hydraulic properties unpredictable and thus rather unreliable as a regional-scale seal. At the same time, the heterogeneity potentially assumedly for stratigraphic traps to have formed.

Additional porosity and permeability data for the Staffelegg Formation were collected from each of the new TBO wells (Figure 4.9). However, the data was only assigned to the Staffelegg Formation rather than a specific member. The new data suggest that the porosity range given by Chevalier et al. (2010) can be extended upwards to 19 vol.% while the permeability has to be extended downwards to include values as low as $5\text{e-}7$ mD (see Section 4.2.5 for explanation).

4.2.7 Dogger Group

Within the Dogger Group, only the Hauptrogenstein is a well-known porous-matrix aquifer. Both, the fore- and backshoal deposits further west and east are mudstone-dominated. Besides matrix porosity (often related to partial particle dissolution), the Hauptrogenstein likely includes some fractures and karst features, especially in the Jura Mountains where it is locally used as a main aquifer (e.g. Neuchâtel and La Chaux-de-Fonds). It shows porosities of up to 18 vol.% and, at least in these areas, high permeabilities (no data found). Its petrophysical properties in the SMB however are only poorly constrained. It is therefore uncertain if the unit shows high enough porosities and permeabilities to be suitable as a reservoir formation in the area of interest.

In case the petrophysical properties are promising, the overlying Ifenthal Formation is relatively impermeable but also highly heterogeneous. Its suitability as a regional-scale seal is therefore uncertain and would need to be investigated in detail. In the east where the Hauptrogenstein transitions to the Klingnau Formation, some of the limestones might be locally sealed by marls of similar age due to interfingering (stratigraphic trap).

Additional porosity and permeability data for the Dogger Group were collected from each of the new TBO wells (Figure 4.9). Except for the siting region Jura Ost, the newly collected data is from the off-barrier assemblage of north western Switzerland. For the poorly characterised Hauptrogenstein, 21 new porosity measurements were obtained (5.6 to 19 vol.%) and a single hydrotest (ca. 0.1 mD) was done.

4.2.8 Upper Jurassic and Cretaceous sediments

The Upper Jurassic limestones are characterised by a lower permeability in the rock matrix and higher permeabilities where karst features are present. This results in the formation being an important local aquifer in some areas of the Jura Mountains with a mean hydraulic transmissivity of 10^{-6} m² s⁻¹ in undisturbed and 10^{-5} m² s⁻¹ in fractured zones in NE Switzerland. In

the southwest, these values are an order of magnitude higher. Additional porosity and permeability data for the Upper Jurassic were collected from several of the new TBO wells (Figure 4.9). They fall within the porosity range reported by Chevalier et al. (2010; Figure 4.9A). However, the new permeability data indicated that higher (over 20 mD) and lower ($4e-5$ mD) permeabilities than previously compiled are possible (Figure 4.9B).

In the western SMB an additional reservoir can be found – the Etiollets Formation (Rusillon, 2016). The reservoir properties of these bodies are controlled primarily by the depositional facies but also post-depositional processes (e.g. compaction, fracturing) play an important role in generating and destroying porosity and permeability. The porosity ranges from 1 to 25 vol.% and (formation) permeabilities up to 100 mD. The porosity is primarily inter- and intraparticle porosity but fractures are common. Due to the contrast in mechanical stability the reef complexes are more strongly fractured than the surrounding lithologies. Many fractures are therefore very small and do not likely represent major fluid pathways linking the reservoir with other formations above and below.

The Cretaceous limestones show similar characteristics of a karst aquifer with a less permeable rock matrix but highly permeable karst conduits. Due to the similarities between these two aquifers and the lack of seal in between, it is assumed that they act as a combined aquifer where the Cretaceous is present.

The Upper Jurassic (or Lower Cretaceous limestones where present) are sealed by the mudstones of the Lower Marine Molasse or, where absent, the Lower Freshwater Molasse. In areas where the USM is dominated by sandstones, a hydraulic connection between the Mesozoic limestones is inferred based on hydrochemistry (Section 4.34).

Additional porosity and permeability data for the Upper Jurassic limestones were collected from most of the new TBO wells (Figure 4.9). The freshly determined porosity values fall within the range reported by Chevalier et al. (2010). The new permeability values on the other hand allow to extend the upper end of the range from 1 to 22 mD.

4.2.9 Lower Freshwater Molasse (USM)

The reservoir properties of the USM are highly heterogeneous and strongly depend on the lithotypes in question. The conglomerates deposited in the proximal realm likely show suitable reservoir properties (elevated porosity and permeability) based on their depositional history but no quantitative data is available. In addition, they are poorly/not sealed as they are directly overlain by more conglomerates from the later stages of Molasse deposition. They are therefore not considered as potential reservoir for geo-methanation.

In the more distal areas of the SMB, intercalations of sandstones (filling of paleo-channels) and mudstones (floodplain deposits) are typical. The petrophysical properties are strongly dependant on the architectural element in question (Platt & Keller, 1992). The channel sandstones show average porosities of nearly 20 vol.% and permeabilities of up to 500 mD. These values decrease for the other architectural elements composed of fine-grained sandstones (14 vol.% and 5 mD) or silt- and mudstones (both 8 vol.% and near 0 mD). The USM therefore represents numerous small aquifers embedded in a seal. Depending on the age of the USM, the ratio between sand- and mudstones differs, suggesting that intervals with more aquifer than seal properties (primarily USM-II) and vice versa (primarily USM-I) are present within the same formation and, potentially even of the same age just in different areas. No data on the Molasse units were collected during the recent Nagra-TBO project.

4.2.10 Upper Marine Molasse (OMM)

The Upper Marine Molasse (OMM) is considered a good regional porous-matrix aquifer with porosities of 5 to 20 vol.% and permeabilities of up to 650 mD. The OMM-I is more sandstone-rich and thus likely the better aquifer compared to the OMM-II where sandstone layers are abundant but often only a few meters thick. At the same time, OMM-II could fulfil the role of a seal if mudstones are abundant and thick. Where the OMM-II is absent or where it is more sand-rich, the marly sections of the distal Upper Freshwater Molasse (OSM) could act as a seal. No data on the Molasse units were collected during the recent Nagra-TBO project.

4.2.11 Upper Freshwater Molasse (OSM)

Similarly to the USM, the OSM is characterised by very heterogeneous reservoir properties, depending on the architectural element studied. The conglomerates and sandstones of the alluvial fans are porous and permeable. However, they are not generally sealed. Sandstones deposited as river-channels on the other hand, especially in areas rich in marly floodplain deposits and lacustrine sediments (such as in between the two alluvial fans), could present adequate reservoir formations. Unfortunately, only a very small amount of petrophysical data is available for the OSM. Gander (2004) estimates the porosity of OSM sandstones to be in the range of 5 to 10 vol.% and reports permeability values from 0.01 to (rarely) 100 mD. No data on the Molasse units were collected during the recent Nagra-TBO project.

4.3 Chemical composition of groundwaters

This section provides information on the chemical composition of groundwaters in the individual aquifers identified in Section 4.1. Instead of reporting the complete composition for each groundwater only the simplified chemical type of the water is given. In order to do this, chemical analyses in mol/L or mg/L are converted to meq/L and subsequently to meq% (for cations and anions individually). In order to be included in defining the water type, a cation or anion needs to make up 30 or more meq.% (Waber et al., 2014). In addition to water types, total dissolved solid (TDS) concentrations and pH values are also reported.

The section is subdivided into the following sections

- Pre-Triassic units: crystalline basement and infill of the PCT troughs
- Deep Mesozoic units of the Triassic and Lower Jurassic
- Shallow Mesozoic (Middle Jurassic to Cretaceous)
- Molasse units (UMM, USM, OMM, OSM)

The subdivision of the Mesozoic units into deep and shallow parts reflects the presence of the excellent seal of the Middle Jurassic Opalinus clay (\pm marly sections of the Lower Jurassic Staffelegg Formation), which hydraulically isolates the deeper and shallower units across the SMB (Waber et al., 2014).

The data for the Mesozoic and Molasse units are primarily compiled from Waber et al. (2014), who subdivided the groundwaters for each unit into shallow (0 to 100 m deep) and deep (> 100 m) waters. For this report, only deep waters are considered as depths < 100 m are not suitable for geo-methanation (Table 2.1). Data on groundwater composition in the crystalline basement, PCTs, Dinkelberg Formation and Cretaceous limestones are compiled from Chevalier et al. (2010). The large number of new groundwater data from the shallow and deep aquifers of Northern Switzerland collected within the framework of the Nagra TBO program were not included in this compilation as data processing and interpretation was still ongoing at the time of writing.

4.3.1 Crystalline basement and Palaeozoic sediments

The groundwaters in the crystalline basement in the north-east of the SMB generally show low salinities (< 2 g/L) due to meteoric water infiltration from the Black Forest area where the basement is exposed. Only scant data are available for basement groundwaters elsewhere in the basin, and it is likely that their salinities strongly increase away from the infiltration zone. The waters are of general Na–Cl or Na–SO₄-types.

No groundwater data are available for the Palaeozoic sediments. However, high salinities analysed in the crystalline basement in the immediate proximity of the NSPB indicate highly saline brines being present within the Palaeozoic sediments.

4.3.2 Deep Mesozoic units

These units are older than the Middle Jurassic Opalinus clay and include all aquifers of the Triassic units as well as the Beggingen Member in the oldest part of the Staffelegg Formation.

In the Buntsandstein aquifer, the salinity of the groundwaters is generally below 0.4 g/L. However, where a hydraulic connection is established with the basement (i.e. where Permian sediments are absent), mixing with more saline groundwaters from the basement may increase the salinity substantially.

The Stamborg Member of the Schinznach Formation contains brackish to saline waters of Na-SO₄⁻, Ca-SO₄⁻ or Na-Cl-types with highly variable TDS values between 0.7 and 115 g/L. Generally, an increase in TDS with increasing depth is observed. The waters with the lowest TDS values are present in the NE of the SMB where relatively recent infiltration of meteoric water from the Black Forest area occurred. The pH values are also variable, ranging from 6 to 7 in equilibrium with the reservoir formation. For most groundwaters there is little evidence of mixing with waters from other sources. Only for the Na-Cl-type waters, the high TDS values suggest mixing with a deep, saline fluid originating from the crystalline basement or PCT troughs.

The heterogeneous Klettgau Formation contains several water-bearing sandstone formations. They all contain Na-SO₄⁻ and Na-Cl-type waters. The former shows TDS values of 10 to 16 g/L and pH of 7.1 to 7.3. They are equilibrated with respect to the carbonate and sulphate minerals present in the Klettgau formation. There is also contribution from dissolution of NaCl (from the overlying Bänkerjoch Formation) or marine porewater. The Na-Cl-type waters are more highly mineralised with TDS values between 13 to 60 g/L (no pH data available). For these waters, contributions of NaCl dissolution or an evaporated seawater are inferred. Both water types have been isolated from meteoric infiltration for 10⁴–10⁵ years. Most known groundwater samples were derived from the Seebi and Berlingen Members with a smaller number of samples from the Gansingen and Ergolz Members.

For the limestones of the Beggingen Member, only few water measurements from eastern Switzerland are available. The groundwaters are highly mineralised Na-Cl-type waters with TDS values of 19 to 46 g/L. No pH values have been reported. They are old waters of marine origin, likely in equilibrium with the reservoir formation.

4.3.3 Shallow Mesozoic units

These units are younger than the Middle Jurassic Opalinus clay and include the carbonate aquifers of the Hauptrogenstein as well as the Upper Jurassic and Lower Cretaceous limestones.

The Middle Jurassic Hauptrogenstein contains groundwaters of Ca–HCO₃⁻, Ca–HCO₃⁻–SO₄⁻ and Na–HCO₃⁻-types. They are weakly mineralised (TDS: < 1 g/L) and show pH of 7 to 7.5. They are young waters (residence times of a few years) but already in equilibrium with calcite and some also dolomite.

In the Upper Jurassic limestones, the groundwaters are predominantly highly mineralised Na–Cl-waters (TDS: 4 to 10 g/L) with pH of 6.8 to 7.9. They represent a water in equilibrium with the aquifer minerals containing a sea-water component, either originating from the deposition of these limestones or from the marine Molasse units above.

Where the Cretaceous limestones are present, a hydraulic connection with the Upper Jurassic limestones underneath is assumed. Therefore the groundwater composition should be similar. However, no data were compiled for the Cretaceous so far.

4.3.4 Molasse units

The aquifers of the Molasse units are primarily porous-matrix aquifers (e.g. sandstones). The groundwater composition shows a vertical stratification which is only partially controlled by the lithological boundaries between the four formations (Figure 4.10).

Within the OMM and OSM, dilute waters of Ca–Mg–HCO₃⁻-type (TDS: < 0.5 g/L) and more concentrated waters of Na–HCO₃⁻ (TDS: < 1.5 g/L) or Na–[HCO₃⁻/SO₄⁻/Cl⁻]-types (TDS: 1 to 4 g/L) dominate. The different composition compared to the shallow waters can be explained by more extensive interactions with the minerals present, especially cation exchange on clays. For some waters, mixing with connate water can be inferred. All of these deep waters show pH values in the range of 6.8 to 7.9. In the older USM, Na–Cl-type waters are additionally encountered at greater depth. These waters show highly variable TDS values of 2 to 30 g/L (increasing values with increasing depth) and pH of 7.6 to 8.5. All deep groundwaters show residence times of more than 10 000 years.

The deep Molasse waters and the Upper Jurassic limestone groundwaters are very similar and suggest basin-wide flow across the Cenozoic–Mesozoic boundary at least over thousands of years.

Figure 4.9: Groundwater types in the Molasse units across the SMB (Nagra, 1988).

4.4 Structures in the SMB

The information in this chapter is largely based on the final GeoMol report (Allenbach et al., 2017). GeoMol has incorporated around 500 structures (normal fault, reverse fault, strike-slip) fault within the SMB. In reality, the number of faults is substantially higher. There is also some information on the presence of synclines/anticlines in the GeoMol report, despite them being not included in the model (as fault axis trace).

4.4.1 Fault zones

Fault zones have the potential to either act as preferential pathways for fluid circulation or, if tight, to act as fault traps (Figure 2.1). Therefore, simply stating that fracture zones are present or absent is not enough to assess their effect on the fluid retention potential of a given formation/area. However, almost no data on the permeability of different faults within the SMB are available. This section will therefore only provide information on the types and distributions of faults.

Types of faults

The Swiss Molasse Basin is positioned between two mountain chains, the Jura Mountains to the north and the much higher Alps to the south. Both are the result of the Alpine orogeny starting around 80 Ma ago with the main orogenic phase around 40 Ma ago. This reactivated numerous older Palaeozoic lineaments in the basement, leading to faults that cross-cut the entire Mesozoic and partially also the Tertiary strata to reach the surface (Pfiffner et al. 1997).

Normal faults are generally oriented in NE–SW direction (parallel to the Alpine Front). They offset the entire Mesozoic strata by up to 400 m. Another set of normal faults is present in NE Switzerland and is related to the North Swiss Permian Basin (NSPB). These faults show an ENE–WSW orientation. A third set of normal faults, oriented N–S, is present in eastern Switzerland. Reverse faults show a general orientation of NE–SW to ENE–WSW and are generally located within the Subalpine Molasse (see below). Strike-slip faults show three orientations and different relative movement: NNW–SSE (sinistral) > WNW–ESE (dextral) > NNE–SSW (sinistral). They are generally steep and cross-cut to entire Ceno- and Mesozoic stack, either terminating in the Triassic evaporites or even the crystalline basement. Towards the surface, they often split into branches, resulting in complex flower structures.

Distribution of faults

The distributions of faults at the base of the Cenozoic strata (i.e. cross-cutting the Mesozoic sediments) and the base of the Mesozoic strata (i.e., originating in the basement) are shown in Figures 4.10 and 4.11. These structures are included in the GeoMol model of the SMB (Section 3.3).

The density of faults is highest along the southern edge of the SMB in the Subalpine Molasse where zones show a kilometre scale spacing (Figures 4.11 and 4.12). The fault zones are primarily located within the Tertiary strata, NW–SE oriented and steep at the surface and flatten out at depth. In the underlying Mesozoic sediments, normal or reverse faults delimited by strike-slip faults (flower structures) are expected. In some areas these structures are tight and act as fault traps (e.g. natural gas occurrence in Entlebuch; Vollmayr and Wendt 1987).

The central part of the SMB further north is less affected by faulting (Figures 4.10 and 4.11). However, the abundance and type of faulting drastically changes from west to east. In the area of Geneva and Vaud, large-scale strike-slip faults are abundant (< 1 fault/km), some of which originate in the basement. In the Fribourg–Bern area, faults are still relatively abundant but the fault zones are generally shorter and normal faults are much more abundant. In addition, not even the largest scale faults (i.e. Fribourg Fracture Zone) originate in the basement. Further east the density of structures decreases (< 0.1 fault/km) before it increases again in the St. Gallen area (Allenbach et al., 2017).

The Subjurrassic Zone along the northern edge of the SMB (Figures 4.10 and 4.11) again shows a higher abundance of faults (primarily reverse faults) compared to the central SMB. They are oriented NE–SW to ENE–WSW and crosscut primarily the Mesozoic strata, generally terminating inside the Tertiary units. The faults are interpreted to originate either in the basement or in the Triassic detachment horizon.

Figure 4.10: Map showing faults present in the SMB as included in the GeoMol model (Section 3.3) at the base of the Cenozoic sediments, i.e. cross-cutting the Mesozoic sediments (Allenbach et al., 2017).

Figure 4.11: Map showing faults present in the SMB as included in the GeoMol model (Section 3.3) at the base of the Mesozoic sediments, i.e. originating within the crystalline basement (Allenbach et al., 2017).

4.4.2 Anticlinal traps

The SMB contains numerous anticlines. They are especially abundant in the western part of the SMB between Lausanne and Bern and along the foot of the Jura Mountains (Figure 4.12). In the Tertiary Molasse units of the SMB they are low amplitude, large-scale folds (primarily in the Fribourg–Bern area). In the Mesozoic strata, similar folds occur beneath the Subalpine Molasse (line St. Gallen–Luzern–Entlebuch) or related to shallower mega-anticlines (Essertines, Cuarny, Hermrigen, Berlingen–Kreuzlingen). The Subjuristic Zone shows a series of narrow and high amplitude anticlines.

Figure 4.12: Map showing the fold axis traces of anticlines (solid blue lines) and synclines (dashed blue lines) in the SMB as included in the GeoMol model. The colours indicate the Cenozoic units exposed at the surface (yellow: OSM, green: OMM and pink: USM). The Subalpine Molasse is indicated by the brown striated area along the Alpine front (Allenbach et al., 2017).

These folds are all due to the Alpine orogeny, more precisely the folding of the Jura Mountains. This explains why only formations above the décollement horizon (dashed red line in Figure 3.3), along which the Mesozoic strata were displaced north-westwards, are affected by folding. In the west, the décollement horizon is located in the evaporites of the Keuper Group, such that the deeper lying Muschelkalk and Buntsandstein Groups are not folded. Further east, the décollement horizon is located within the evaporites of the deeper Muschelkalk Group. Thus, only the underlying Buntsandstein and Palaeozoic sediments are not

folded (Sommaruga et al., 2017).

Several of these structures have been investigated as potential hydrocarbon reservoirs or within the framework of gas storage (e.g. Tschugg). However, no data are available as to whether these anticlines indeed represent suitable traps.

4.4.3 Structural subdivision of the SMB

Based on the above description of the structures present in the SMB, Chevalier et al. (2010) defined three types of faulted areas and four areas where trap types can be inferred (Figure 4.13). These large scale areas were then rated according to their suitability for long-term gas storage (e.g. carbon sequestration) from unsuitable (red) to moderately suitable (yellow to light green) and highly suitable (dark green). The same subdivision can be applied to the current screening of the SMB for geo-methanation.

For the faults (Figure 4.13A), the three areas defined were: (1) Areas with a high density of faults, a majority of faults cutting across the entire sedimentary stack to reach the surface, fault zones which are active as evidenced by recent movements (e.g. earthquakes) or permeable as evidenced by ascending deep formation waters; (2) areas where faults are present but generally do not reach the surface, giving the possibility of buried fault traps at depth; and (3) areas with little evidence of faulting. Highly suitable is only the central to eastern SMB, away from both the Subalpine Molasse and the Subjuristic Zone. However, fractures in other areas can act as fault traps if they are sealed, as evidenced by the only natural gas occurrence in Switzerland at Entlebuch. Unfortunately, there are little to no data to assess which faults and fractures are tight. Therefore, staying clear of heavily fractured areas may be more advisable for geo-methanation applications.

For the traps, the following four categories could be identified: (1) Areas without known traps, characterised by strata dipping openly southwards from the base of the Jura Mountains towards the Alpine front; (2) intact sedimentary compartments between steeply dipping fault planes mainly at the Palaeozoic–Triassic transition below the Jura Mountains or in the Mesozoic and Lower Tertiary units in some areas of the SMB (e.g. Kreuzlingen, Pfaffnau or Essertines–Yverdon); (3) overthrust duplex structures within and below the Subalpine Molasse (e.g. triangle zone of Eastern Switzerland) and lower Mesozoic units in some areas of the SMB (e.g. north of Lindau or south of Pfaffnau); and (4) various anticlinal structures as shown in Figure 4.13. While these anticlines could potentially act as traps (Figure 2.1), several are dissected by fractures (c.f. Figure 4.11). Whether this favours fluid retention or leakage is uncertain. Similarly, the structure of the triangle zone (marked with stippled pattern in Figure

4.12) is poorly constrained. It is therefore difficult to assess the actual potential of this area for gas storage.

Figure 4.13: Maps differentiating areas within the SMB and adjacent Jura Mountains based on (A) the types of faults and (B) potential traps. Modified after Chevalier et al. (2010).

5 Suitability of geological formations in the SMB for geo-methanation

5.1 Ranking scheme

In this section the suitability of the various geological units as reservoirs for geo-methanation is evaluated. The evaluation is based on the positive and cautionary indicators in Table 2.1, which are applied to the reservoir, porewater and retention criteria compiled in Section 4. Each formation is then rated from 1 to 4 according to the following scheme:

- *Rank 1 – Potentially suitable lithology for geo-methanation with trap structures locally present/likely.*
- *Rank 2 – Potentially suitable lithology for geo-methanation but poorly constrained, limited distribution or uncertain regarding gas retention properties (seal/traps).*
- *Rank 3 – Potentially suitable lithology for geo-methanation but very poorly constrained and not very abundant, implying a high exploration risk.*
- *Rank 4 – Unsuitable for geo-methanation due to fractured/karstified nature.*

The ranking (Table 5.1) is primarily based on geological criteria such as the regional distribution and extent of the aquifer formations (lateral and vertical), the heterogeneity within the unit, petrophysical properties (porosity and permeability), the type of aquifer (porous vs. fractured and/or karstified), and the presence of possible traps (Figure 2.1) to ensure gas retention. The extent of knowledge on the various formations in the SMB highly variable. Certain formations have received more attention over the years in the context of exploration for petroleum, selection of a site to store radioactive waste, and geothermal energy. Others remain largely unstudied and their properties much more uncertain. Thus, the state of knowledge directly affects exploration risk, and hence it is taken into account in the ranking.

Table 5.1: Criteria (positive indicators) and SMB geological units screened for geo-methanation implementation. A “y” (for “yes”) indicates that the criterion is fulfilled; “(y)” indicates that the criterion is barely fulfilled or highly uncertain; and “n” (for “no”) indicates that it is not fulfilled. The units are ranked from 1 to 4, where 1 denotes “potentially suitable for geo-methanation” and 4 denotes “likely unsuitable for geo-methanation”.

	Crystalline basement	(Pre-)Weitenau Fm.	Dinkelberg Fm.	Schinz. Fm. (Stamb.Mb.)	Klettgau Fm. (SBEG Mbs.)	Staffellegg Fm. (Beg. Mb.)	Hauptrogenstein	Up. Jur./Lower Cret. Limest.	Up. Jur. Etiollets Fm.	Lower Freshwater Molasse	Upper Marine Molasse ⁵	Upper Freshwater Molasse
Rank	4	3	1	1	2	3	2	4	3	2	2	2
Extent & heterogeneity of aquif. ¹	reg (h)	loc (h)	reg (l)	reg (l)	loc (h)	reg (h)	reg (l)	reg (h)	loc (h)	loc (h)	reg (l)	loc (h)
Thickness: > 5 m	y	y	y	y	y	(y)	y	y	?	(y)	y	(y)
Porosity ² : > 20 vol.%	n	?	n	y	n	n	n	n	y	n	(y)	?
Porosity ³ : > 10 vol.%	n	?	y	y	y	y	y	n	y	y	y	?
Permeability: 50 to 3000 mD	y	?	y	y	y	y	?	n	n	y	y	?
Aquifer type: Porous matrix	n	y	y	(y)	y	y	y	n	(y)	y	y	y
Caprock: Present & tight	(y)	y	(y)	y	y	(y)	(y)	(y)	(y)	(y)	(y)	(y)
Trap structures ⁴	f	s	f	a/f	a/f/s	a/f	a/f/s	a/f	s	a/f/s	a/f/s	a/f/s

¹reg. = regional extent; loc. = local extent; h = highly heterogeneous with respect to lithological distribution and/or distribution of water-conducting features; l = low degree of heterogeneity with respect to lithological distribution and/or distribution of water-conducting features. All formations are heterogeneous when it comes to the distribution of petrophysical properties (porosity and permeability) as evidenced by the spread of the values in Figure 3.1.

²Positive indicator for porosity given in Table 2.1. ³Cautionary indicator for porosity given in Table 2.1.

⁴a = anticlinal traps possible, f = fault traps possible, s = structural trapping (due to different lithotypes present in the same formation/member). ⁵For the purpose of creating the combined map of potential reservoirs for geo-methanation (Figure 9.1), the areas where the OMM is likely sealed by the overlying OSM (light olive area in Figure 6.15) was ranked as 1.5 while the remaining OMM was ranked as 2.

In Section 2.2, the porewater criteria (salinity and pH) are discussed. Based on the data compiled in Section 4.3, all formations fall within the range of suitable TDS and pH conditions. It has been shown that there is an increase in TDS with increasing depth and in several formations, deep brines reach TDS values in the range of 100–150 g/L. It is therefore possible that waters with TDS > 150 g/L are present at greater depths. However, at such depths, temperatures are higher than 60 °C and thus nominally unsuitable for geo-methanation. Nevertheless, such brines might be encountered at much shallower depths if upwelling occurs along faults. This is evidenced in NE Switzerland by multiple occurrences of thermal water at the surface (e.g. Baden, Zurzach). Even in these systems, the origin and upwelling of thermal waters is poorly understood. It is likely that other, blind systems (with no surface manifestation) are present. However, no data are available that allow entire regions to be discarded based on these grounds. In-situ porewater criteria will thus not be discussed for individual formations.

5.2 Crystalline basement

The crystalline basement has several positive properties. It represents a huge volume as it underlies the entire SMB and extends to great depths. The permeabilities of the water-conducting features are high, even if the maximum values of fracture-porosity are only slightly above the cautionary value of 10 vol.%. However, as a fracture-based aquifer, it is not suited for geo-methanation. In addition, the crystalline basement is only sealed beneath the Permo-Carboniferous troughs, otherwise a hydraulic link to the overlying Buntsandstein aquifer exists as evidenced by high salinity brines (typical for crystalline rocks) found in the Buntsandstein within the deep SMB. However, these nominally suitable areas lie at great depths (several km) and therefore outside the desired temperature range for geo-methanation.

Assessment: Rank 4 – Unsuitable for geo-methanation due to fractured nature, lack of seal in most areas and, where potentially sealed, being too deep.

5.3 Pre-Weitenau Formation

The Carboniferous sandstones of the Pre-Weitenau Formation represent very local, small-scale reservoirs of porous sandstones. The thickness of individual sandstones is at most 8.5 m but the entire Carboniferous sequence is locally up to 3000 m thick.

The hydraulic properties of these sandstones and their distribution are currently only very poorly constrained. If gas injection were possible, the gases would be retained by stratigraphic trapping as the sandstones are surrounded by impermeable floodplain deposits. In

addition, fault-bounded traps are potentially present. Anticlinal traps are not expected as the Pre-Weitenau Formation is located below the décollement horizon of the Jura Mountains.

Assessment: Rank 3 – Potentially suitable lithology for geo-methanation but very poorly constrained and not very abundant, implying a high exploration risk.

5.4 Dinkelberg Formation

The Dinkelberg Formation is a laterally extensive porous reservoir in northern Switzerland. It is present across the SMB but wedges out along a line Langenthal – Zürich – Stein am Rhein. The thickness of the formation ranges from 0 to 30 m inside the perimeter of the *T*-model.

The quartz sandstones of the Buntsandstein show suitable petrophysical properties, but lateral variations are common and large. The seal (or lack thereof) is a primary concern with respect to the suitability of the Dinkelberg Formation. There is a hydraulic connection with the underlying crystalline basement in areas where no Permian deposits are present. In addition, the overlying Kaiseraugst Formation shows characteristics between an aquifer and a seal. In order to avoid the loss of injected fluids into these rocks but also laterally along the gently southward dipping Dinkelberg Formation, trap structures would need to be located. As anticlinal traps are unlikely due to the formation's position below the Jura décollement horizon, fault traps are mandatory for gas storage. An ideal situation would be a normal-fault compartment in which the Dinkelberg sandstone is sealed up-dip by the very tight, stratigraphically younger Zeglingen Formation.

Assessment: Rank 2 – Potentially suitable lithology for geo-methanation but presence of trap structures uncertain.

5.5 Schinznach Formation (Stamberg Member)

The Stamberg Member of the Schinznach Formation is a laterally very extensive and relatively thick (around 20 m) reservoir formation.

The dolomite shows suitable porosity and permeability values along the northern margin of the SMB where subvertical fractures enhance the permeability of the formation up to 1000 mD. Further south and hence at greater depths, values of only 20 mD have been measured.

The overlying Bänkerjoch Formation represents an extensive, low-permeability seal. However, similarly to the Buntsandstein, the up-dip migration potential of gases injected into the porous and gently southward dipping formation is high. Therefore, trap structures would

be needed for successful geo-methanation. Due to the position of the Schinznach Formation above the Jura décollement horizon in north-eastern Switzerland, anticlinal traps are expected, especially close to the northern edge of the SMB. In addition, fault traps are possible.

Assessment: Rank 1 – Potentially suitable lithology for geo-methanation with anticlinal trap structures likely.

5.6 Klettgau Formation (SBEG Members)

While the Klettgau Formation is a laterally extensive formation present across northern Switzerland, it is comprised of several members, some of which have more restricted geographical distributions. The four aquifer members of interest are abbreviated as SBEG. The sandstone aquifer of both, the Seebi and Berlingen members occurs exclusively in the eastern portion of the study area. In contrast, the Ergolz Member is present across the SMB (where the Klettgau Formation is defined). However, the position of the Ergolz sandstone layers within the otherwise largely impermeable mudstones is uncertain. All of these members are thick enough to be suitable for geo-methanation. The Gansingen Member, on the other hand, is only a few meters thick and is present only in north-western Switzerland.

For none of the individual members are porosity and permeability data available. There are some promising values available for the Klettgau Formation as a whole and positive indicators from previous studies where the properties of the Klettgau Formation were reported in combination with the Staffelegg Formation (Figure 4.1).

All four members are likely sealed by the mudstone layers of the Ergolz Member near the base of the Klettgau Formation and by the mudstones in the Gruhalden Member near the top (EGh Members). However, in some areas a hydraulic connection between the Klettgau Formation and the overlying Beggingen Member of the Staffelegg Formation has been postulated. If true, this would suggest that some of the members are locally not well sealed.

As the Berlingen, Gansingen and Seebi Members interfinger with other members laterally (Figure 4.6), stratigraphic traps are likely present. Such traps are also likely in the Ergolz Member, where the permeable sandstones are surrounded by largely impermeable floodplain deposits. As the Klettgau Formation is situated above the Jura décollement, anticlinal traps are likely as well. In addition, faults cross-cutting the Klettgau Formation are known, suggesting that fault traps are a possibility, especially where the offset along a fault places a reservoir member next to a sealing member (whether in the Klettgau Fm., the overlying mudstones of the Staffelegg Fm, or the underlying Bänkerjoch evaporites).

Assessment: Rank 2 – Potentially suitable lithology for geo-methanation but poorly constrained petrophysical properties.

5.7 Staffelegg Formation (Beggingen Member)

The Beggingen Member is a laterally extensive reservoir, present across the area of northern Switzerland where the Staffelegg Formation is defined. It is, however, rarely more than 5 m thick.

The petrophysical properties are generally reported for the entire Staffelegg Formation rather than for its individual members. The reported values thus likely underestimate the reservoir properties of the Beggingen Member. However, the lack of groundwater data from the Beggingen Member suggests that the formation behaves as an aquifer only locally.

The younger members of the Staffelegg Formation are highly heterogeneous and likely do not represent a laterally extensive seal. In some areas there is additionally a postulated hydraulic connection to the underlying Klettgau Formation. This could render the formation locally unsuitable for geo-methanation, despite fault-bounded and anticlinal traps likely being present.

Assessment: Rank 3 – Potentially suitable lithology for geo-methanation but thin and with low permeability. Retention quality uncertain.

5.8 Dogger Group (Hauptrogenstein)

The Hauptrogenstein occurs only in the central to western SMB, between Brugg and Echallens. It is up to 110 m thick and is known to be a good aquifer in the Jura Mountains. However, within the SMB the characteristics are less favourable (porosity is ≤ 18 vol.% and permeability < 0.2 mD ($n = 1$)). As the petrophysical properties are unlikely to be constant throughout the ≤ 110 m thick formation, strata with adequate porosity and permeability could nevertheless be present at many intervals.

The sealing capacity of the overlying Ifenthal Formation is uncertain. Further east, the Variansmergel and Wutach Formations are likely better seals. The most suitable traps for geo-methanation from a lithological point of view are in the north-eastern SMB where the Hauptrogenstein interfingers with the marl-rich and relatively impermeable Klingnau Formation. In addition, anticlinal and fault-bounded traps are a possibility.

Assessment: Rank 2 – Potentially suitable lithology for geo-methanation but poorly constrained. Very thick. Stratigraphic, fault-bounded and fold trap structures likely.

5.9 Upper Jurassic and Cretaceous limestones

For the purposes of ranking, these units are best divided into the following three: Upper Jurassic limestones, Upper Jurassic reef complexes (Etiollets Formation) of westernmost Switzerland, and Lower Cretaceous limestones.

The Upper Jurassic limestones are a very thick, laterally extensive unit. However, the karst nature of the aquifer means that it is unsuitable for geo-methanation. Where the Lower Cretaceous deposits are present above the Upper Jurassic limestones (west of Biel/Bienne), no seal is present and the two formations are hydraulically connected. In the eastern part of the SMB, the Jurassic limestones are likely sealed by the fine-grained deposits of the USM.

Assessment: Rank 4 – Unsuitable for geo-methanation due to karstified nature and lack of seal in eastern SMB.

The Upper Jurassic reef complexes (Etiollets Formation) represent porous reservoirs uniquely occurring in westernmost Switzerland. Unfortunately, their distribution is poorly constrained and average thickness for such reef complexes is unknown but assumed to be in the range of several meters.

The porosities of up to 25% and permeabilities up to 100 mD indicate suitable properties for geo-methanation. As they represent porous bodies in largely tight limestones, stratigraphic trapping is likely. However, many of the surrounding limestones are fractured and/or karstified locally. Detailed assessment of sealing properties would thus be required during exploration.

Assessment: Rank 3 – Potentially suitable lithology for geo-methanation but very poorly constrained and not very abundant, implying a high exploration risk. Retention quality uncertain.

The Lower Cretaceous limestones are a very thick, laterally extensive unit. However, the karst nature of the aquifer means that it is unsuitable for geo-methanation. The Lower Cretaceous is likely sealed by the fine-grained deposits of the USM.

Assessment: Rank 4 – Unsuitable for geo-methanation due to karstified nature.

5.10 Lower Freshwater Molasse (USM)

The sandstones of the distal USM are present across the entire SMB. While the individual sandstone layers are only in the meter- to decametre range, the overall thickness of the USM is high

(mostly >200 m). This means that any exploration well is likely to encounter at least some sandstone layers with adequate reservoir properties. However, lateral variations in lithologies and petrophysical properties are common and not well constrained. The degree of interconnectedness between the sandstones is also unknown. On the one hand, well-connected sandstones create a larger reservoir volume. On the other hand, they possibly allow the injected gases to migrate away from the injection site, especially if the connection is up-section.

The marly sequences within the USM can range from decimetres to around 50 m. They become more abundant towards the top of the USM. In addition, the older USM-I is more marl-rich, suggesting that at the top and in the lower sections, the USM might be better sealed. Anticlinal and fault-bounded traps are a possibility.

Assessment: Rank 2 – Potentially suitable lithology but geometries and distribution of sandstones not well constrained. Retention quality uncertain.

5.11 Upper Marine Molasse (OMM)

The sandstones of the OMM are present across the entire central to eastern SMB. Within the OMM-I, the sandstones are meters to decametres thick while in the OMM-II they are intercalated with mudstones at the m-scale. In both cases, the petrophysical properties are likely suitable for geo-methanation.

Where the sandstones of the OMM-I are overlain by the OMM-II, the reservoir might be sealed. However, in order to ensure retention of the gas in the monoclinical unit, anticlinal or faults traps need to be targeted. Another option for a sealed reservoir is the top of the OMM-I, where the distal, mud-rich deposits of the overlying OSM facilitate retention.

Assessment: Rank 2 – Potentially suitable lithology but retention quality uncertain.

5.12 Upper Freshwater Molasse (OSM)

This unit is assessed as being very similar to the USM (Section 4.1.11). However, the OSM contains fewer sandstones and more mudstones, increasing exploration risk. In addition, the OSM is not capped by a distinct sealing unit. However, the abundant fine-grained strata interlayered with the sandstones of the OSM are likely to act as internal seals, able to trap any injected fluids.

Assessment: Rank 2 – Potentially suitable lithology but geometries and distribution of sandstones not well constrained. Retention quality uncertain.

6 Distribution of target formations for geo-methanation in the SMB

Map projections of the ten formations that are ranked 3 or higher have been extracted from GeoMol, as described in Section 3.4. These base maps, showing where the formations occur in the required depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation, are shown in Appendix A.

In the following sections, the geographical areas indicated in the base maps are further reduced so that they represent only the areas where the target formation/members likely have aquifer properties. Justifications for these reductions are discussed in the text and illustrated in a set of criteria maps. Final maps of the delimited areas are presented, showing four features that are useful in planning drilling campaigns and in estimating gas-storage volumes: contours of depth below the Earth's surface, contours of true vertical thickness of the aquifer formations (insofar as this is possible for complex formations), the locations of folds known or suspected to affect the aquifer, and the locations of faults known to cut through the top of the aquifer.

In general, the geographical areas where the target aquifers occur in the final delimited maps can be readily understood by considering the gentle, largely monotonic 3–4° dip of all the units towards the southeast. Thus, the Mesozoic units, which are stratigraphically the lowest of those under consideration, fall within the required depth–temperature interval (>600 m deep, 30–60 °C) only in a relatively narrow strip along the southern edge of the Jura Mountains. Further towards the southeast they rapidly sink to depths where the rocks are at temperatures above 60 °C. The Molasse sedimentary rocks, on the other hand, lie higher up in the stratigraphy and they are extremely thick. Consequently, they fall within the required depth–temperature interval over a large part of the central and southern SMB, overlying the deeply buried Mesozoic units.

6.1 Pre-Weitenau Formation

The Pre-Weitenau Formation is contained within the *Permokarbondrog* layer of GeoMol (Table

3.1). Rather than being defined across entire modelled area, the layer appears only in the area of Aarau – Laufenburg – Benken – Winterthur, part of the so-called Northern Swiss Permian Basin (NSPB; Allenbach et al., 2017). Based on our work, the *Permokarbondrog layer* occurs within the depth–temperature interval suitable for geo-methanation in the area of Brugg – Bülach – River Thur in NE-Switzerland, with two other small areas near Aarau and southeast of Brugg (Figure A.1). This area is smaller than the area where the NSPB is defined in the model. Thus, the outline shown is constrained by the depth–temperature requirements rather than by limits of the GeoMol model (with a possible exception just south of Schaffhausen: the relatively straight edge of the delimited area could indicate that this is an artificial edge introduced by the definition of the *Permokarbondrog layer* in GeoMol). It is therefore possible that the area where the Pre-Weitenau Formation occurs in the correct depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation could be extended to the edge of the GeoMol model further northeast.

In Section 4.2.2, we identified the sandstones of the Carboniferous Pre-Weitenau Formation as the only reservoir of interest (sealed by the Permian Weitenau Formation). In order to delimit the map in Figure A.1 to only show the distribution of the Pre-Weitenau Formation, the following steps were taken:

- (1) Exclude areas where the *Permokarbondrog layer* is less than 150 m thick as this is the minimum thickness of Permian deposits reported and the older Carboniferous deposits are thus absent in these areas.
- (2) Identify areas where the *Permokarbondrog layer* is between 150 and 300 m thick as cautionary areas. The maximum thickness reported for the Weitenau Formation is 300 m. In this area it is likely but uncertain that the Pre-Weitenau Formation is present in the correct depth–temperature interval.

The remaining delimited area is shown in Figure 6.1. It extends along a narrow strip from east of Brugg via Bachs and Eglisau to the Rafzerfeld (all Canton of Zürich). In this area, the Pre-Weitenau Formation is assumed to be in the right depth–temperature interval and thus potentially suitable for geo-methanation. The depth to the top of the formation and its thickness in the right depth–temperature interval are shown in Figure 6.2. The deposits lie at a depth of 1150 to nearly 1400 m and show a thickness of up to 400 m. These maps were constructed from the depth and thickness maps in Appendix 1 by (a) increasing the depth values by 150 m to account for the exclusion of the Permian Weitenau deposits and (b) reducing the thickness values by the same number. As the Permian has been shown to be up to 300 m thick, the depth and thickness values represent minimum and maximum values, respectively.

Several fault zones are contained within this area, especially along the southern edge of the Pre-Weitenau perimeter east of the River Glatt. Two additional large-scale fault zones

are present north east of Brugg and across the Rafzerfeld. The least disturbed area is in the easternmost part of the Canton of Aargau. No anticlines are shown in Figure 6.2B as the Pre-Weitenau Formation is located underneath the décollement horizon for the Jura Mountains (Section 4.4).

Figure 6.1: Map of the Pre-Weitenau Formation showing where the Permokarbondrog layer occurs in the correct depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation (all colours) and how this area was further constrained to show areas where Pre-Weitenau deposits are possibly present (dark olive green) or likely present (light olive). The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.

6.2 Dinkelberg Formation

The Dinkelberg Formation is contained within the *Muschelkalk* layer of GeoMol (Table 3.1) which also contains the Kaiseraugst, Zeglingen and Schinznach Formations. Based on our work, the *Muschelkalk* layer occurs within the desired depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation from Oensingen along the *T*-model perimeter to the border with Germany east of Schaffhausen (northern edge) and Langenthal – Lenzburg – Spreitenbach – Bülach – Eglisau – Marthalen – Diessenhofen along the southern edge (Figure A.2).

Figure 6.2: Delimited Pre-Weitenau Formation. Top map: depth below surface to top of aquifer. Bottom map: vertical thickness of the formation and locations of known faults. The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.

In Section 4.2.3, we identified the sandstones of the Dinkelberg Formation as a reservoir of interest (sealed by the Kaiseraugst/Zeglingen Formation). In order to delimit the map in Figure A.2 to show only the distribution of the Dinkelberg Formation, the area of the *Muschelkalk layer* was superimposed with the area where the *BMes horizon* (base Mesozoic, directly exported from GeoMol) is present in the correct depth–temperature interval. As the Dinkelberg Formation is the oldest Mesozoic unit, its base coincides exactly with the *BMes horizon*.

The remaining delimited area is shown in Figure 6.3. It extends along a narrow strip from Baden via Würenlingen to Rekingen and then follows the northern edge of the *T*-model perimeter all the way to south of Thayngen. In the south, it extends both south and north of Lägern and follows the line of Glattfelden – Eglisau – Marthalen – Benken – Diessenhofen. In addition, a small area around Birr was identified. In these areas, the Dinkelberg Formation is assumed to be in the right depth–temperature interval and thus potentially suitable for geo-methanation. The depth to the top of the formation and its thickness in the critical depth–temperature interval are shown in Figure 6.4. The deposits lie at depths of 800 to 1400 m below the surface. This matches the depths of the *BMes horizon* as the Dinkelberg Formation is only up to 30 m thick. The isopach map shown is modified after Chevalier et al. (2010).

Several fault zones are situated within the delimited area, especially within the central part. To the west of Aarau and in the western Zürcher Weinland, largely unfaulted areas are likely to occur. No anticlines are shown in Figure 6.2B as the Pre-Weitenau Formation is located underneath the décollement horizon for the Jura Mountains (Section 4.4).

6.3 Schinznach Formation (Stamberg Member)

The Schinznach Formation is situated at the top of the *Muschelkalk layer* in GeoMol (Table 3.1) which also contains the Dinkelberg, Kaiseraugst and Zeglingen Formations. Based on our work, the *Muschelkalk layer* occurs within the desired depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation from Oensingen along the *T*-model perimeter to the border with Germany east of Schaffhausen (northern edge) and Langenthal – Lenzburg – Spreitenbach – Bülach – Eglisau – Marthalen – Diessenhofen along the southern edge as well as two small areas around Solothurn and between Biel/Bienne and La Neuville (Figure A.2).

In Section 4.2.4, we identified the dolomitic Stamberg Member as the only reservoir of interest within the Muschelkalk Group (sealed by Bänkerjoch Formation; Figure 6.5). It is located near the top of the Schinznach Formation. Only the Asp Member (which is < 15 m thick; Jordan & Desplazes, 2019) separates the Schinznach Fm. from the overlying Bänkerjoch Fm.

The top of the *Muschelkalk* layer was therefore assumed to correspond to the top of the Stamberg Member and the outline shown in Figure A.2 directly represents the area where the Stamberg Member is present in the correct depth–temperature interval (Figure 6.5).

Figure 6.3: Map of the Dinkelberg Formation showing where the Muschelkalk layer occurs in the correct depth interval for geo-methanation (all colours) and how this area was further constrained to show area where the Dinkelberg aquifer is present (light olive). The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.

The depth to the top of the formation and its thickness within the correct depth–temperature interval are shown in Figure 6.6. The aquifer lies at depths of less than 800 to 1200 m. These values were taken directly from Figure A.2. The thickness of the Stamberg Member ranges from 25 to just over 30 m. The isopach map is modified after Adams et al. (2019).

Faults are present across the entire area of interest. Where faults are bordered by folds in the maps, the faults are mostly thrusts and the folds are mostly the accompanying ramp anticlines. In the eastern sector the indicated faults are steep strike-slip structures flanked by subvertical fracture networks.

Figure 6.4: Delimited Dinkelberg Formation. Top map: depth below surface to top of aquifer. Bottom map: vertical thickness of the aquifer and locations of known faults. Isopachs are modified after Chevalier et al. (2010). The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.

Figure 6.5: Map of the Schinznach Formation – Stamberg Member showing where the Mus horizon occurs in the correct depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation (light olive). As the Stamberg Member lies at the top of the Schinznach Formation (Asp Member is not considered due to its small thickness), the map does not need to be delimited further. The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.

6.4 Klettgau Formation (SBEG Members)

The SBEG Members of the Klettgau Formation are contained within the *Keuper layer* of GeoMol (Table 3.1), which also contains the older Bänkerjoch Formation. Based on our work, the *Keuper layer* occurs within the required depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation from just east of Wangen a. A., along the T-model perimeter to the border with Germany near Dörfingen SH (northern edge) and from west of Langenthal – Oftringen – Lenzburg – Spreitenbach – Bülach – Andelfingen – Schlattingen along the southern edge as well as a small area between Biel/Bienne and Saint-Blaise (Figure A.3).

In Section 4.2.5, we identified the Ergolz, Gansingen, Berlingen and Seebi Members as potential reservoirs (sealed by the Ergolz/Gruhalden Member of the Klettgau Formation). The following steps were taken to delimit the map in Figure A.3, such that it shows only the distribution of the members of interest:

- (1) Exclude areas outside the area in which the Klettgau Formation is defined (Jordan et al., 2016), as it is unclear whether or not the Klettgau Formation is still present there.

Figure 6.6: Delimited Schinznach Formation – Stamberg Member. Top map: depth below surface to top of aquifer. Bottom map: stratigraphic thickness of the Member and locations of known faults and anticline crest. Isopachs are modified after Adams et al. (2019). The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.

- (2) Exclude areas along the northern edge of the area of interest as well as in the Olten area where the top of the formation is outside of the required depth–temperature interval (purple in Figure A.3). In these areas the Klettgau Formation is only <30 to 40 m thick (Jordan et al., 2016) and thus likely partially missing.

The remaining delimited area is shown in Figure 6.7. It is largely identical with the non-delimited area except that the area around Lake Biel has been excluded as well as several small areas along the northern edge of the *T*-model perimeter. In the delimited area, the Klettgau Formation is assumed to be in the right depth–temperature interval and thus potentially suitable for geo-methanation.

Figure 6.7: Map of the Klettgau Formation with SBEG Members showing where the Keuper layer occurs in the correct depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation (all colours) and how this area was further constrained to show area where sealed Klettgau aquifers are likely present (light olive). In addition, the distribution of all four members with potential reservoir properties in the area of interest is shown (modified after Jordan et al., 2016). The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.

In order to obtain more information on the distribution of individual members, the facies maps drawn by Jordan et al. (2016) were included in our delimited map (Figure 6.7). The Ergolz Member is present across the entire area of interest, while the Gansingen Member is missing in the north-easternmost area. The coeval Berlingen Member only occurs in the Lake

Constance area and thus lies outside the desired depth–temperature range. The Seebi Member is restricted to the north-eastern corner of the area of interest. Throughout the area shown in Figure 6.7, two potentially suitable reservoir members are therefore expected to be present (Ergolz + Gansingen/Seebi Member). In addition, in the area between Weiach-Neerach-Bülach and Rheinau-Flaach, all three members are present.

The depth to the top of the Klettgau Formation and its thickness in the correct depth–temperature interval are shown in Figure 6.8. The deposits lie at a depth of 600 m along the northern margin of the strip-like area to just over 1200 m along its southern margin. As the Klettgau Formation lies just below the *T_{Keu} horizon*, these depth values were taken directly from Figure A.4. The thickness of the overall Klettgau Formation in the area of interest ranges from around 30 to nearly 50 m (Jordan et al., 2016). The thickness of individual members is rather variable (inset diagram in Figure 6.8). In order to obtain more detailed thickness information, data from a number of different wells (SEAG, old Nagra wells, new Nagra TBO wells, etc.) were compiled for each of the potential reservoir members. In the area of interest, the sandstones of the Ergolz Member are 3 to 16+ m thick, the Gansingen Member 2 to 7 m and the Seebi Member 3 to 24 m (Appendix Figures B.1 to B.4).

Faults are present across the entire area of interest. As is the case for the underlying Stamberg aquifer, many of the faults in the maps are bordered by folds. In these cases the faults are mostly thrusts and the folds are mostly the accompanying ramp anticlines. In the eastern sector the indicated faults are steep strike-slip structures flanked by subvertical fracture networks.

6.5 Staffelegg Formation (Beggingen Member)

The Beggingen Member of the Staffelegg Formation is contained within the *Lias layer* of Geo-Mol (Table 3.1), along with the remainder of the Staffelegg Formation. Based on our work, the *Lias layer* occurs within the required depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation from just east of Wangen a. A., along the *T*-model perimeter to the border with Germany near Dörfingen SH (northern edge) and from west of Langenthal – Oftringen – Lenzburg – Spreitenbach – Bülach – Andelfingen – Schlattingen along the southern edge, as well as the area around Lake Biel and a small area around Solothurn (Figure A.4).

Figure 6.8: Delimited Klettgau Formation – S(B)EG Members. Top map: depth below surface to top of formation. Bottom map: locations of known anticline crest and faults within the delimited area. See inset diagram for ranges of stratigraphic thicknesses of the Members. Thickness maps of each aquifer Member are given in Appendix B. The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.

In Section 4.2.6, we identified the Beggingen Member as a potential reservoir (sealed by the remainder of the Staffelegg Formation). In order to delimit the map in Figure A.4 to only show the distribution of the member of interest, the following steps were taken:

- (1) Exclude areas west of Biel/Bienne as the literature defining the Staffelegg Formation (Reisdorf et al., 2011) specifically warns against extrapolating west of Biel/Bienne. In the east, another small section lies outside the study area of Reisdorf et al. (2011). However, well data are available from this area, allowing us to extrapolate the presence of the Staffelegg Formation.
- (2) Identify areas where the top of the formation is outside of the required depth–temperature interval (purple in Figure A.4). These are classified as cautionary areas for geo-methanation. In these areas the Staffelegg Formation is < 30 to about 45 m thick (Reisdorf et al., 2011). As the Beggingen Member lies at the bottom of the Staffelegg Formation, it is likely present in the correct depth–temperature interval in these areas, but its presence there is not guaranteed.

The remaining delimited area is shown in Figure 6.9. It is largely identical with the non-delimited area except that the area around Lake Biel has been excluded. In the delimited area, the Klettgau Formation is assumed to be in the required depth–temperature interval and thus potentially suitable for geo-methanation.

In order to obtain more information on the distribution of the Beggingen member, data from a number of different wells (SEAG, old Nagra wells, new Nagra TBO wells, etc.) were compiled. It appears to be present across the entire Staffelegg Formation. However, its thickness only ranges from 1 to 8+ m (Figure B.5).

The depth to the top of the Beggingen Formation and its thickness in the correct depth–temperature interval are shown in Figure 6.10. The deposits lie at a depth of 600 m along the northern margin of the delimited area to just over 1200 m along the southern margin. Although the Beggingen Member does not lie at the top of the Staffelegg Formation, the remainder of the formation (< 30 to about 45 m thick; Reisdorf et al., 2011) is too thin to be resolved from the base maps in Appendix A (in which the distance between depth contours = 50 m).

Faults are present across the entire area of interest. As is the case for the underlying Stamberg and Klettgau aquifers, many of the faults in the maps are bordered by folds. In these cases the faults are mostly thrusts and the folds are mostly the accompanying ramp anticlines. In the eastern sector the indicated faults are steep strike-slip structures flanked by subvertical fracture networks.

Figure 6.9: Map of the Staffelegg Formation – Beggingen Member showing where the Lias layer occurs in the correct depth interval for geo-methanation (all colours) and how this area was further constrained to show area where the Beggingen Member is likely present (dark olive) The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.

6.6 Dogger Group (Hauptrogenstein)

The Hauptrogenstein is contained within the *Dogger layer* of GeoMol (Table 3.1). The layer contains a large number of formations, none of which, other than Hauptrogenstein, show aquifer properties. Based on our work, the *Dogger layer* occurs within the desired depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation from a few small areas in the Jura Vaudois to an extensive area at Éclepens, along the T-model perimeter to east of Solothurn (northern edge) and from Éclepens via Fey to Orbe – Yverdon-les-Bains – Mt. Vully – Aarberg – Büren a.A to Solothurn. A second extensive area starts east of Wangen a. A., along the GeoMol perimeter to the border with Germany near Dörflingen SH (northern edge) and from west of Langenthal – Zofingen – Seon – Dietikon – north of Winterthur – Stein am Rhein along the southern edge (Figure A.5).

Figure 6.10: Delimited Staffelegg Formation – Beggingen Members. Top map: depth below surface to top of formation. Bottom map: stratigraphic thickness of Beggingen aquifer with locations of known faults and anticline crest. A detailed map of the thickness of the Beggingen Member is given in Appendix B. The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.

In Section 4.2.7, we identified the Hauptrogenstein as a potential reservoir (possibly sealed by the overlying formations of the Dogger Group). In order to delimit the map in Figure A.5 to only show the distribution of the member of interest, the following steps were taken:

- (1) Exclude areas in the western and eastern SMB where the Hauptrogenstein is not present based on its occurrence in maps shown in Chevalier et al. (2010).
- (2) Identify areas where the top of the Upper Malm outside of the required depth–temperature interval (purple in Figure A.5), and classify them as cautionary areas. In these areas the top of the Dogger Formation is missing. The uppermost units of the Dogger Group (Ifenthal, Variansmergel and Wutach Formation) are generally < 15 m thick, which suggests that they are most likely missing across the entire cautionary area. The Hauptrogenstein on the other hand increases from 30 m near Brugg to nearly 150 m near Wangen a.A. In the eastern part of the cautionary area, the presence of the Hauptrogenstein is thus not guaranteed, while further west it should be present but with reduced thickness.

The remaining delimited area is shown in Figure 6.11. Large areas in the south western (backshoal deposits) and north eastern part of the SMB (foreshoal deposits) were excluded. In the remaining area, the Hauptrogenstein is assumed to be in the required depth–temperature interval and thus potentially suitable for geo-methanation.

The Hauptrogenstein does not lie at the top of the *Dogger layer*, but the overlying Ifenthal Formation is only < 15 m thick, which is below the depth resolution of the base maps in Appendix A (distance between depth contours = 50 m). Thus, the depth values shown in Figure 6.12 are taken directly from Figure A.5. The thicknesses of the Hauptrogenstein are taken from Chevalier et al. (2010).

Faults are present across most of the area of interest. Only in the Lake Neuchâtel/Yverdon-les-Bains area is there a large area without known faults unfaulted area present. Two major anticlines have been mapped there. Elsewhere a number of much smaller anticlines are known, often running parallel to nearby faults. This association indicates that the faults are thrusts and the folds are the corresponding ramp anticlines.

6.7 Etiollets Formation

The Etiollets Formation is contained within the *Upper Malm layer* of GeoMol (Table 3.1). The layer also contains a large number of other limestone formations, many of which act as local to regional aquifers. However, they are primarily fracture and karst aquifers and have thus been excluded for geo-methanation considerations (Chapter 4.1.8).

Figure 6.11: Map of the Hauptrogenstein showing where the Dogger layer occurs in the correct depth interval for geo-methanation (all colours) and how this area was further constrained to show area where Hauptrogenstein is possible (dark olive) and likely (light olive). The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.

Based on our work, the *Upper Malm* layer occurs within the desired depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation across the entire SMB as a 50 to 100 km wide strip along the foot of the Jura Mountains (largely along the T-model perimeter; Figure A.6).

In Section 4.2.8, we identified the reef complexes of the Etiollets Formation as the only potential reservoir within the *Upper Malm* layer. The formation is possibly sealed by the low permeability limestones of the overlying Twannbach Formation (Tidalites de Vouglans). In order to delimit the map in Figure A.6 to only show only the distribution of the Etiollets Formation, the following steps were taken:

- (1) Exclude areas west of a line St. Cergue – Gland where the Etiollets Formation was never deposited as the basin became progressively deeper towards the SE.
- (2) Identify areas where the top of the formation is outside of the required depth–temperature interval (purple in Figure A.6). In these areas the top of the *Upper Malm* layer is missing. However, the uppermost units of the Upper Malm (Twannbach Formation) is around 140 m thick in the Geneva Basin (Jenny et al., 1995), which suggests that while these limestones are partly missing in the area in question, the underlying Etiollets

Figure 6.12: Delimited Hauptrogenstein. Top map: depth below surface to top of formation. Bottom map: stratigraphic thickness of formation and locations of known faults and anticline crest. Isopachs are modified after Chevalier et al. (2010). The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.

Formation should be present in its entirety. We thus refrained from distinguishing the two areas in the delimited map (Figure 6.13).

The remaining delimited area is shown in Figure 6.13. As the Etioletes Formation was only deposited in westernmost Switzerland, areas east of the Geneva Basin could be excluded. It is assumed that in westernmost Switzerland the reef complexes of the Etioletes Formation are in the required depth–temperature interval and thus potentially suitable for geo-methanation.

Figure 6.13: Map of the Etioletes Formation showing where the Upper Malm layer occurs in the correct depth interval for geo-methanation (all colours) and how this area was further constrained to show the areas where the Etioletes Formation is likely present (light olive). The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.

The Etioletes Formation does not lie at the top of the *Upper Malm* layer. The overlying Twannbach Formation is around 140 m thick in the area of interest. In order to obtain depth values to the top of the Etioletes Formation (Figure 6.14), 150 m were added to the depth isolines shown in Figure A.6 (distance between depth contours in Figure A.6 = 50 m). The thickness of the Etioletes Formation encountered in wells across the Geneva Basin (Switzerland and France) were taken from Jenny et al. (1995) and, for GEO-02) directly from Service Industriels de Genève (SIG). As the formation shows large lateral variations in thickness over a small area, we refrained from constructing isopachs based on the data available.

Faults are abundant across the area of interest. They primarily run WNW to ESE and

NW to SE. The faults targeted by GEO-02 show SSW to NNE orientations. No anticlines have been identified in the delimited area. Due to the recent detailed 3D seismic survey conducted within the Geneva Basin (see Chapter 3.2.1), a much more detailed picture of the subsurface geometries will be available soon.

6.8 Lower Freshwater Molasse

The Lower Freshwater Molasse (USM) is a GeoMol layer on its own (Table 3.1). It occurs within the required depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation throughout almost the entire area of the SMB. Only to the west of Lausanne and along a narrow strip parallel to the *T*-model boundary east of Solothurn, is the USM outside the required depth–temperature interval (Figure A.7). Within the Subalpine Molasse, the two main Molasse units are not differentiated in the GeoMol model and therefore this area is not further evaluated.

The proximal sandstone-poor lithofacies dominated by conglomerates is excluded as a potential gas reservoir (Figure 6.15; Matter et al., 1980, Schlunegger et al., 1996, 1997a, Kempf & Matter, 1999, Matter et al., 1999). In the remaining distal USM, each sandstone layer that is overlain by a mudstone layer constitutes a potential sealed reservoir (Section 4.2.9). Although there are innumerable such aquifer–seal pairs within the total USM, their individual thicknesses, extents and geographical distribution are not known, except for those logged in several exploration wells (marked in Figure 6.15). In the absence of detailed knowledge about its specific internal makeup, the USM is treated here as a composite, heterogeneous, internally sealed aquifer. Hence, the USM appears as both aquifer and caprock in the title of Figures 6.15 and 6.16).

The depth to the top of the USM and its vertical thickness in the desired depth–temperature interval are shown in Figure 6.16. Within this interval the USM is extremely thick, reaching up to almost 1000 m. The thickest areas within the interval are likely composed of the sandstone-dominated USM-II (the USM-II has a total stratigraphic thickness of up to 2000 m). Where the delimited reservoir is thinner, both formations (USM-I and USM-II) should be present.

Owing to the great stratigraphic thickness and shallow dip of the USM to the SE, applying the limits of $T > 30$ °C and depth ≥ 600 m results in a huge region in the map where the top of the delimited reservoir lies between 600 and 800 m depth (indicated by the ruled pattern in Figure 6.16). South eastwards from this ruled region the top of the USM is encountered at progressively greater depths, reaching almost 1600 m below the surface. However, towards

Figure 6.14: Delimited Etiolette Formation. Top map: depth below surface to top of formation. Bottom map: stratigraphic thickness of formation and locations of known faults and anticline crest. Thickness information is derived from Jenny et al. (1995) and the newly drilled GGeo-02 well (pers. comm. SIG). The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.

this deep south-eastern margin, the thickness of the unit pinches out completely in some sectors (e.g., 0 m thickness contour in Figure 6.14, bottom map), being truncated at depth by the 60 °C isothermal surface.

Figure 6.15: Map of the Lower Freshwater Molasse (USM) showing where the USM layer occurs in the required depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation (all colours) and how this area was further constrained to exclude the conglomerate-rich facies (yellow). The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.

Faults within the USM are primarily present close to the foothills of the Jura Mountains and towards the Subalpine Molasse. In both areas the NE–SW oriented faults are low-angle thrusts, whereas the indicated N–S to NW–SE faults are steep strike-slip structures. Several large-scale anticlines are known in the delimited area between Bern and St. Gallen, which represent prime exploration targets.

6.9 Upper Marine Molasse

The Upper Marine Molasse (OMM) is represented by its own layer in GeoMol (Table 3.1). It occurs within the desired depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation across a large region of the SMB to the east of Bern and south of the line Bern-Sursee – Pfäffikon ZH – St. Gallen

(Figure A.8). No information is available for the Subalpine Molasse where the Molasse units are not differentiated in GeoMol.

In order to delimit the map in Figure A.8, the proximal lithofacies dominated by conglomerates (Keller, 1989, Schlunegger et al., 1997b, Kempf & Matter (1999), Strunck & Matter (2002) are excluded (Figure 6.17). As is the case for the USM (Section 6.8), the makeup of the remaining distal OMM is poorly known, there being only a few exploration wells with publically accessible logs through the unit (Figure 6.17). In Section 4.2.10, the amalgamated sandstones of the OMM have been identified as potential reservoirs, where they are sealed by mudstone layers. Although there are innumerable such aquifer–seal pairs within the total OMM, their individual thicknesses, extents and geographical distribution are not known, except for those in three exploration wells with publically accessible logs (marked in Figure 6.17). In the absence of detailed knowledge about its specific internal makeup, the OMM is treated here as a composite, heterogeneous and internally sealed aquifer (dark olive in Figures 6.17 and 6.18).

In contrast, the eastern realm of the OMM is overlain (at a depth below surface of more than 600 m, i.e. inside the required depth–temperature interval), by the mudstone-rich Upper Freshwater Molasse (OSM). This OSM is assumed to be an effective seal and therefore the OMM in this realm (light olive in Figures 6.17 and 6.18) is assigned a higher potential for gas storage.

The top of the OMM lies at a depth of 600 to 1000 m below surface and it has a vertical thickness of up to 800 m within the critical depth–temperature interval (Figure 6.18). In the central SMB, the OMM-I can be up to 700 m thick. Thick OMM-II sequences are likely only present north of the area of interest.

Stratigraphic traps are less abundant than for the USM. Faults are limited to the area south-west of Bern as well as close to Lake Constance. Several small anticlines can be found across the area of interest as well as an extensive fold ranging from the Entlebuch area across Central Switzerland to the River Thur.

6.10 Upper Freshwater Molasse

The Upper Freshwater Molasse (OSM) is a GeoMol layer on its own (Table 3.1). It occurs within the required depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation only in the Cantons of Thurgau, St. Gallen and Zürich (Figure A.9). Within the Subalpine Molasse, the three Molasse units are not differentiated in the GeoMol model and therefore this area is not further evaluated.

Analogous to the other Molasse units, the alluvial fan lithofacies dominated by

Figure 6.16: Delimited Lower Freshwater Molasse (USM). Top map: depth below surface to top of USM (for details see Figure A.6). Bottom map: vertical thickness and locations of known faults and anticline crest. The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be likely off limits for geo-methanation projects.

Figure 6.17: Map of the Upper Marine Molasse (OMM) showing where it occurs in the correct depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation (all colours) and how this area was further constrained to exclude the conglomerate-rich facies (yellow). Also differentiated is an area sealed above by the OSM unit at depths deeper than 600 m (light olive). Dark olive shows where the OMM would need to contain sealed aquifers internally, in order to be suitable for geo-methanation. The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.

conglomerates is excluded as a potential gas reservoir (Figure 6.19). In the remaining OSM, sandstones are embedded in mudstone layers thus potentially constituting small-scale sealed reservoirs (Section 4.2.11). Although there are likely a large number of such aquifer–seal pairs within the total OSM, their individual thicknesses, extents and geographical distribution are not known. In the absence of detailed knowledge about its specific internal makeup, the OSM is treated here as a composite, heterogeneous, internally sealed aquifer. Hence, the OSM appears as both aquifer and caprock in the titles of Figures 6.19 and 6.20.

The depth to the top of the OSM and its vertical thickness in the desired depth–temperature interval are shown in Figure 6.20. The OSM generally lies between 600 and 800 m below surface with a small area north of St. Gallen where the OSM is slightly deeper than 800 m. Overall, the OSM is less than 100 m thick but can be over 150 m thick in the area north of St. Gallen.

Figure 6.18: Delimited Upper Marine Molasse (OMM). Top map: depth below surface to top of OMM (for details see Figure A.7). Bottom map: vertical thickness and locations of known faults and anticline crest. The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.

Figure 6.19: Map of the Upper Freshwater Molasse (OSM) showing where it occurs in the correct depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation (all colours) and how this area was further constrained to exclude the conglomerate-rich facies (yellow). The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.

Regional- scale faults within the OSM are only present close to Lake Constance. They represent relatively steep NW–SE trending strike-slip structures. Only a single anticline was identified in the Tannenber area, north of St. Gallen.

6.11 Uncertainties and significance of delimited aquifers

The maps presented in this Chapter are based heavily on data incorporated in the GeoMol geological model (geological horizons) and the associated T-model (isotherms). Both of these models have inherent uncertainties related to their geological input data and the processing thereof, to the inter- and extrapolation of 3D information across the entire model extent, and to the linking of the individual model sections (Allenbach et al., 2017).

Within the large-scale units defined by GeoMol, the possible distribution of aquifers and seals –as shown in the maps in this Chapter– is based on our interpretations of the literature on the subsurface geology of the SMB. Here, many points of interpretation are uncertain, as indicated by the discussion in Chapters 5 and 6. A primary uncertainty is the quantification

Figure 6.20: Delimited Upper Freshwater Molasse (OSM). Top map: depth below surface to top of OSM (for details see Figure A.8). Bottom map: vertical thickness and locations of known faults and anticline axis. The three Nagra siting regions are assumed to be off limits for geo-methanation projects.

of petrophysical properties (rock-matrix porosity and permeability, fracture porosity at formation scale, and permeability derived from borehole hydraulic tests). Information on these properties is patchy throughout the delimited reservoirs of interest, and the available information is not currently integrated into GeoMol. Our generalized classifications of certain lithofacies as aquifers and seals may therefore not be reliable across the entire delimited areas, especially as over 100 years of hydrocarbon exploration, the overall reservoir quality in the SMB has been found to be relatively poor (Leu, 2012). Porosity and permeability values encountered are generally lower than expected due to overcompaction of the sediments related to the late uplift and erosion and a complex diagenetic overprint leading to increased cementation of pores. The poor reservoir qualities and generally small volumes of porous formations enclosed by trap structures, limits the size of potential reservoirs.

Additional uncertainties are related to the locations of major faults and anticlines in the delimited reservoirs. The positions of the structures indicated in the maps in Chapter 6, have been taken directly from GeoMol. It is very likely however, that many more minor faults exist in reality. Irrespective of whether a fault is included in GeoMol or not, very little information on the properties of the fault are likely available. While the position of faults can be deduced, e.g. from seismic surveys, its permeability can normally only be determined by hydraulic testing from nearby wells which is not commonly done or at least reported. Whether the number of anticlines included in GeoMol is complete or not, is unclear. Overall, anticlines represent larger structures than individual faults and are thus harder to miss. They have also been prime targets during the hydrocarbon exploration in Switzerland and are therefore comparatively well-studied. Leu (2012) suggests that many of these anticlines are breached and this is why no hydrocarbon resources are present in the SMB. The breached traps are the result of a combination of relatively thin sealing formations and recent compressive tectonic deformation related to the formation of the Jura Mountains. Unfortunately, the author gives no information on the abundance and distribution of breached traps across the SMB.

Despite the above uncertainties, we are confident that the maps provided in this Chapter serve as useful first-order guides to the SMB in two respects. First, the areas *not* classified as "sealed aquifers" can be understood as regions where gas storage and geo-methanation are *unlikely to be feasible*, based on the current state of geological knowledge. Second, the areas delimited as "sealed aquifers" (olive shades in the maps) can be understood as regions where gas storage and geo-methanation *may well be feasible*, once more detailed subsurface information becomes available. Thus, these delimited areas in the maps should not be taken to indicate *definitive feasibility*. Steps necessary to establish definitive feasibility are discussed in the following section.

6.12 Suitability map for geo-methanation in the SMB

The potential quality of sealed aquifers deduced in this study (as expressed by their ranking in Table 5-1) can be used as a primary guide in exploring for geo-methanation sites. In addition, the chances of exploration success are enhanced where more than one sealed aquifer is present in the sedimentary stack beneath the same geographical site. At such sites a single well may permit several aquifers to be tested for their suitability for geo-methanation, thereby lowering costs as well as risks. Finally, the presence of structural traps for gas can be used as a third criterion in exploration.

Figure 6.21: Map showing relative suitability of areas in the Swiss Molasse Basin for geological gas storage under conditions required for USC-FlexStore geo-methanation (greater than 600 m deep, temperature 30–60 °C). Shades of green denote the sum of sealed aquifer formations locally present in the sedimentary stack, each aquifer being weighted by the reciprocal of its quality ranking (1, 2 or 3; Table 5-1). Blue lines show locations of the crests of known elongated dome structures (anticlines) in the subsurface, which may serve as gas traps. Areas distant from blue lines may or may not contain other unknown anticlines. Faults (not shown in this map) may also create gas traps, but less commonly than anticlines. All known faults are shown in the maps of individual reservoir units (maps in this section).

As a practical aid in exploration and in planning the use of the subsurface, a map has

been constructed summarising the geographical distribution of the above three criteria throughout the SMB, coloured according to a suitability scale (Figure 6.21). The map considers only the sealed aquifers judged to be potentially suitable, i.e., those ranked 1, 2 or 3 in Table 5.1. Examination of the number of these aquifers in the sedimentary stack at each geographical location defines 23 distinct areas: 8 with one aquifer in the subsurface, 6 with two, 3 with three, 4 with four, and 2 with five stacked aquifers. Each of these areas is assigned a numerical score corresponding to the sum of stacked aquifers, each weighted by its quality ranking. The range of the scores is then represented by a colour scale spanning from yellow-green (lower suitability) to intense green (higher suitability). The presence of anticline crests in the subsurface is denoted by blue lines in the map (taken from Figure 2-4 in Allenbach et al., 2017, as reproduced in Figure 4.13 of this report). Unfortunately, the locations of fault-bounded structural traps versus leaky faults could not be evaluated with the available information (see discussion in Section 7), and so none are shown in Figure 6.21. All known faults in each reservoir unit are shown in the preceding maps in this section.

7 Establishing feasibility of geo-methanation in the SMB

Section 6 has shown that the SMB includes several formations that may meet the criteria for geo-methanation, and that in places these formations are folded or offset by faults that may have created traps suitable for gas storage. A demonstration of the definitive feasibility of geo-methanation at one or more specific sites requires going beyond the coarse spatial resolution of the present study and conducting a dedicated exploration campaign at the kilometre scale. This Chapter outlines the main features required of target gas traps and it describes typical exploration aims and steps.

Any such campaign will require considerable investments of time and capital. However, owing to the currently incomplete knowledge of the deep SMB, there is no guarantee that these investments will result in a successful discovery. To estimate the stake at risk and to aid initial planning of an exploration campaign, this Chapter also provides a brief overview of typical exploration costs and a time schedule.

7.1 Properties of gas traps at km-scale

The various gas species (CH_4 , H_2 and CO_2) involved in geo-methanation spontaneously form a single gas phase that has much lower density and viscosity than the immiscible saline porewater in the reservoir formation. These properties of the gas phase render it highly buoyant and mobile in any sealed aquifer that has a monoclinial dip (Section 2.3). Since all the identified sealed aquifers in the SMB dip slightly to the SE, gas-trap structures (anticlinal, stratigraphic, fault-bounded or combinations thereof) will be essential to retain the gas phase in a well-defined pocket during the short- to medium-term storage periods (months to years) envisaged for geo-methanation.

Numerous anticlines and faults are indicated inside the delimited "sealed aquifers" in the maps in Chapter 6, but only in Northern Switzerland is the resolution of subsurface

knowledge sufficient to define the geometry of the traps clearly. This is the area where Nagra has performed 3D seismic surveys calibrated by several deep wells (the "Nagra reserved sites" outlined in the maps in Chapter 6 are only a part of the total Nagra investigation area, Section 3.2.1).

Figure 7.1: An example cross-section of potential gas traps 15 km ENE from Aarau, where Nagra has conducted detailed 3D seismic imaging, coring of deep wells and geological interpretation. The labelled low-angle thrust carries a ramp anticline (Chestenberg) that folds four potential sealed-reservoir units: Schinznach–Stamberg, Klettgau–SEG, Staffelegg–Beggingen and Hauptrogenstein (here the latter is shallower than 600 m depth limit for geo-methanation). The axis and crest of the fold are projected onto the surface, illustrating their relative locations if viewed in a map. Below the thrust, steep normal faults may conceivably create traps in the Dinkelberg Fm. No information is available as to whether these potential traps are closed in the third dimension outside the 2D plane of the diagram, and whether they are tight or leaky for gas. Note vertical exaggeration of scale. Diagram modified after Nagra (2008; Beilage 5.2-14).

An example geological cross-section in the Nagra investigation area is shown in Figure 7.1, where a ramp anticline above a low-angle thrust may possibly provide gas traps in the sealed Schinznach, Klettgau and Staffelegg Formations as well as the Hauptrogenstein (although at this locality the folded Hauptrogenstein lies shallower than the 600 m depth limit for geo-methanation). The cross-section also suggests that fault-bounded traps might be present in the Dinkelberg Formation, where the faults may be sealed by the overlying Zeglingen evaporites (note that, in this particular cross-section, the temperature of the Dinkelberg sandstones

is higher than the 60 °C maximum for geo-methanation, and so the Figure serves only to illustrate the trapping principle for that formation). While cross-sections with these geometries are promising, they do not show if the potential traps are closed in the 3rd dimension outside the 2D plane of the diagram. Ramp anticlines can be expected to decrease in amplitude in both directions along the strike of their crests, forming elongate domes. Purely fault-bounded traps need at least two intersecting faults to form a hydraulic barrier on the up-dip side of the reservoir. In the Nagra investigation area the information required to verify closure of potential anticlinal and fault-bounded traps is available in the 3D seismic interpretation. Comparable information is unfortunately not available elsewhere in the relevant portion of the SMB, although in Canton Geneva the interpretation of a large 3D survey is currently underway.

Whereas some promising trap structures are present in the mapped reservoirs (Figure 6.18), it is not known if they could actually retain injected gas. To our knowledge, no borehole hydraulic tests have ever been performed in the area of interest to test promising traps for their gas retentivity. Furthermore, despite the long history of oil and gas exploration in the SMB (Section 3.2), no natural gas-bearing reservoirs have been discovered so far within the depth-temperature interval pertinent to geo-methanation. Thus, there is no proof from nature that the potential traps are gas-tight over long periods. Some authors have argued that the anticlines have leaked the gas that they once contained (Leu, 2012). Others suggest that the anticlines and thrusts had not yet formed during the period when burial conditions were conducive to gas generation within the known SMB source rocks (e.g. Mazurek et al., 2006) and thus gas reservoirs never formed.

7.2 Exploration steps

Installation of a geo-methanation site at a depth of 600–1900 m in the SMB requires a gas exploration company to select one or more sites. Geological criteria are paramount, but also non-geological criteria need to be considered, such as ease of permitting and proximity to sources of CO₂ feed gas and to electricity for hydrolytic production of H₂, as described in Work Packages 5 and 6 of the USC-FlexStore Project.

As far as the subsurface is concerned, an industrial exploration campaign has three aims: (1) find a suitable closed gas-trap structure composed of a porous and permeable saline aquifer rock sealed by an impermeable caprock; (2) if, as expected for the SMB, the structure contains no natural gas cap, then create an artificial gas cushion within the apex of the trap by injecting methane; and (3) demonstrate the technical feasibility, long-term gas retentivity, and

environmental safety of the site. Initial steps deal with planning, obtaining exploration permits, possibly establishing a joint venture, and conducting an information and risk dialogue with the public and with local authorities. Further typical steps are outlined the following.

7.2.1 Site selection

Based on the present report, on the literature containing km-scale structural analyses, and on any more recent geological data, one or more target gas-trap structures should be selected. These may be traps that have already been explored to some extent. A 3D seismic survey of the priority trap is performed to define its structure and dimensions at high spatial resolution (Figure 7.2A). An existing survey of the relevant land area may perhaps be procured. For example, in the Nagra investigation areas, seismic imaging of the subsurface is sufficient to plan well sites. Otherwise, a new dedicated survey must be conducted over an area of $\geq 10 \times 10 \text{ km}^2$. Such surveys normally deploy vibrator-trucks on existing roads and set out large arrays of portable geophones. The results allow favourable drilling sites to be identified.

Figure 7.2: Illustration of exploration for a geo-methanation site and creation of a gas cap. (A) Trap structure (an anticlinal fold in this example) is identified in a 3D seismic survey. (B) A well is drilled to demonstrate that the trap contains a porous and permeable saline aquifer sealed by an impermeable caprock, and to test for the presence of natural gas in the trap. (C) In the absence of a natural gas accumulation (as expected in the Swiss Molasse Basin), methane is injected into the trap, displacing the formation water from the pores in the aquifer rock and thereby creating an artificial gas cap.

7.2.2 Site characterisation and baseline monitoring

Prior to drilling, an environmental impact study is conducted, including a survey of flora and fauna in local (sub)surface ecosystems. Monitoring using gas detectors is employed to ensure that gas injected into the target trap does not leak into and contaminate any overlying aquifers, or migrate to the surface where it could influence the biosphere, create hazards of explosion and of suffocation of wildlife and humans, and contribute to global atmospheric warming. Gas monitoring is started prior to drilling to establish the natural baseline of gas contents and emissions from rock outcrops, soils, surface water bodies and shallow aquifers at the site. This monitoring is continued during drilling, including on the well pad, and for several years after gas injection has commenced. A seismic monitoring array is also installed to record the baseline activity prior to perturbing the subsurface fluid pressure by injecting gas.

The drill pad is installed and the main well is drilled, completed for gas injection, and preferably rock cores are extracted over the depth interval of the planned gas cap. Analyses of the core combined with downhole geophysical logging allow calibration of a seismic-based 3D geological model of the gas-trap structure. Sampling of formation fluids allows characterisation of the natural microbial consortia and evaluation of their suitability for geo-methanation. Downhole gas injection tests are performed to confirm that gas can be introduced into the aquifer at the desired rates without causing unwanted formation damage or felt seismicity. Observation wells are drilled at strategic points identified in the refined structural model, in order to test fluid pressure fluctuations. Information from all possible sources is integrated in a 3D numerical reservoir model, and this is used to simulate gas injection and extraction scenarios, including consequences of the attendant pressure fluctuations and fluid–rock chemical reactions.

7.3 Creation of an artificial gas cap and medium-term monitoring

No pristine or exhausted gas caps are known in the SMB at the appropriate depth–temperature conditions for geo-methanation (Section 3.2). If new exploration fails to find gas in the trap targeted for geo-methanation (Figure 7.2B) then a sizeable gas cap (≥ 4.5 million m^3_{STP}) will have to be created in the apex of the trap structure to provide a cushion in which the CO_2 and H_2 reactants can be injected. In principle, use of Swiss-produced biomethane (biogas) for this purpose may favour acceptance of the geo-methanation technology by the public and facilitate certification of the gas yield as "green methane". In practice, the costs and supply limitations of local biomethane may preclude this opportunity.

The creation of an artificial gas cap entails displacing the existing formation water from

the aquifer within the trap by injecting overpressured methane (Figure 7.2C). An important issue to address in the planning, testing and monitoring phases of the exploration campaign is the fate of this displaced formation water. If the total connected pore volume of the aquifer is very large (e.g., of sub-regional scale), then the pressure anomaly caused by water displacement can dissipate radially from the injection point without hydrofracturing the aquifer or its caprock. If the target gas trap is relatively small and bounded by faults, then the displaced porewater may force an escape through the faults, potentially inducing seismicity if the faults are naturally close to their critical failure-stress state. Poor management of injection rates and fluid pressure may also induce hydrofracturing of the aquifer and its caprock. To facilitate successful pressure management, the injection well is normally fitted with fibre-optic detectors to monitor temperature and pore fluid pressure at various depths. One way to manage fluid pressure in the aquifer at high gas injection rates is to simultaneously extract formation water through a separate well. In this case the environmentally sustainable disposal of the saline water needs to be planned in advance and its execution monitored.

Methane can be procured and slowly injected into the trap while continuously monitoring fluid pressure, seismicity and environmentally relevant gas emissions. Injection and monitoring over a period of 6 years is proposed to ensure that the cushion gas can be safely contained and managed in the trap structure. Geo-methanation tests can proceed concurrently by injecting CO₂ and H₂ and sampling their concentration through all wells.

Favourable performance of the site can then allow sustained commercial geo-methanation to begin, possibly with drilling of additional wells to achieve the desired production rate and storage volume.

7.4 Typical time schedule for an exploration and gas injection campaign

Figure 7.3 shows a typical schedule for the steps prior to sustained commercial geo-methanation. At least six additional months would be necessary at the outset to plan the project from scratch. If the first selected site is found to be inadequate for gas storage, then the same exploration steps could be repeated at other prospective sites.

7.5 Typical costs for an exploration and gas injection campaign

An example of typical costs for an exploration campaign and creation of a gas cap is given in Table 7.1. Included are one main exploration well to be used for both injection and extraction, and two narrow-bore observation wells to be sited on the margins of the planned gas trap.

Figure 7.3: Time-schedule of typical operations to explore for a geo-methanation site and create a gas cap in a favourable trap structure. Modified after Häring et al. (2013).

Table 7.1: Typical costs to plan and explore for a geo-methanation site, to create a gas trap containing 4.5 million m³_{STP} and to monitor its integrity over a 6-year period. Included are one injection/extraction well and two narrow-bore observation wells, all drilled to depths of 2000 m. Based on information provided by Dr. Werner Leu (Geoform Geological Consulting and Studies Ltd., Vevey, Switzerland).

Phase	Activity	Cost (kCHF)	Cumul. cost (kCHF)
Project set-up	Define project organization	20	20
Site selection	Global site selection	60	80
	Data evaluation	105	185
	Storage assessment	60	245
	Apply site selection criteria	100	345
	Define a joint venture	15	360
	Permit and risk dialogue	Permit and communication	140
3D seismic exploration		2255	2755
Baseline monitoring		445	3200
Numerical modelling 1		130	3330
Installation well site	Site acquisition & drilling permits	290	3620
	Drilling/completion operations	23350	26970
	Numerical modelling 2	100	27070
	Sub-total		27070
Injection of gas	Acquire & transport gas	2000	29070
	Initial injection & monitoring	1800	30870
	Sub-total		30870
Medium term (6 years) monitoring	Monitoring after injection	5500	36370
	Well site maintenance	2600	38970
	Numerical modelling 3	200	39170
	Grad Total		39170

8 Possible conflicts of use of the subsurface in the SMB

The geological subsurface of the Swiss Molasse Basin is being used or is planned to be used for a variety of engineering and resource-related purposes. Some of these uses are well-established and widely implemented while others are relatively new and, like geo-methanation, are at the exploration stage. Nevertheless, the geological conditions (e.g. lithologies, depth intervals, structures) required for the various technologies are sufficiently well known to assess their potential for conflicts of use with future geo-methanation projects.

As part of our geological screening of the Swiss Molasse Basin, we established a catalogue of criteria which need to be fulfilled to successfully implement geo-methanation (Chapter 2). One of the main criteria is that the temperature of the formations in questions must lie between 30 and 60 °C, so that microbial methanogenesis can take place. In addition, a *minimum depth* of 600 m was defined to ensure retention of gases. Based on the variable geothermal gradients throughout the basin, the depth range in which geo-methanation is feasible varies according to geographic location and to the availability of suitable reservoirs. The potential reservoirs occur in a stack, therefore some of them are present at only 600 – 800 m depth (corresponding to either the *minimum depth* or to the depth of the 30 °C isotherm), whereas others are as deep as 1400 – 1600 m (corresponding to the depth of the 60 °C isotherm). We also established that only well-sealed reservoirs within closed trap structures are likely to be suitable for geo-methanation.

Conflicts of use primarily arise when two subsurface applications target the same potential reservoir and/or seal in the same depth range. Other conflicts may arise from the risk of leakage of injected fluids (via faults or poorly completed wells) into overlying formations that have other uses. In the following chapter we thus list the target geology and depth range for a number of subsurface utilisations. This compilation only broadly assesses the subsurface technologies that are more or less likely to be in conflict with a potential geo-methanation site. It does not replace a more detailed assessment of site-specific conflicts of use during a future

selection process. At present we see no conflict of use whereby one subsurface technology could be compromised by seismicity induced by another subsurface technology. Of course, the risks and hazards posed by induced seismicity are relevant for surface installations and for the population at large and must be evaluated for each project, but this is beyond the scope of the present study.

8.1 Infrastructure

Infrastructure or engineering projects are only of concern for a potential geo-methanation reservoir, if they reach to depths of ≥ 600 m. This is likely to be the case only in the Alps (Figure 3.2), where, due to the extreme relief, tunnels and pipelines may be installed at depths of more than 1 km (e.g. Gotthard Base Tunnel). However, the Alpine geological domain is not suitable for geo-methanation due to the abundance of fractures and poor reservoir properties of most formations (Chapter 3.1). Therefore, no conflict of use between geo-methanation and underground infrastructure projects is expected at the reservoir level. Existing underground infrastructure has to be considered during planning and developing of a site for geo-methanation, similarly to other construction sites.

8.2 Potable groundwater

Potable groundwater in Switzerland is derived from unconsolidated Quaternary aquifers at depths < 50 m. Thus, no conflict of use is likely between geo-methanation and these currently exploited shallow groundwaters. However, some mineral waters with commercially relevant salinities of less than 2.5 g/L are known rarely at depths of up to 1000 m (Waber et al., 2015). In karst regions (e.g., along the foot of the Jura mountain chain), potable groundwater may upwell from at 200–300 m depth (Waber et al., 2015). It is therefore advisable to carefully evaluate each specific geo-methanation site for any potential conflict. Moreover, in the distant future, deeper aquifers might be targeted to ensure the potable water supply, although these tend to be more saline. In order to maintain the quality of these deep potable groundwater reserves, current concepts for geo-methanation consider only formations containing groundwaters with salinities > 30 g/L (Table 2.1).

8.3 Mineral resources

A number of different resources have historically been and are currently exploited in the Swiss Molasse Basin:

- Sandstone: used as building stones
- Clay: raw material for the brick industry
- Gypsum: raw material for building materials
- Salt: raw material for the chemical industry, water treatment, road and table salt

The sandstones potentially have reservoir characteristics while the clays and evaporites could act as seals. However, for economic reasons, building stone, clay and gypsum are all exclusively quarried in open pits at the surface. These rocks also occur within the depth interval of interest for geo-methanation but while there are reserves at or near the surface which can be exploited (in Switzerland or abroad), there is no interest in exploiting deeper reserves of these commodities of low commercial value.

Salt is produced by dissolution mining along the northernmost edge of the SMB near Basel. This type of production is currently profitable down to about 450 m. There are further reserves at greater depth, including the depth interval of interest for geo-methanation. However, large quantities of salt are present at shallower depth in the Jura Mountains. It is therefore unlikely that the salt formations at depths > 600 m, which can be excellent seals for potential geo-methanation reservoirs, are compromised.

In addition to the above mineable commodities, ore deposits (e.g. Cu, Zn, Pb and U) are known to occur in many sedimentary basins worldwide. However, the geological history and small size of the SMB are not thought to have been conducive to the formation of such ores. So far, there are no geological, geophysical or geochemical indications that such deposits could exist in the subsurface of the SMB, and the geological history and small size of the SMB are considered to be unfavourable for the formation of such ores. Accordingly, no exploration for deep ore deposits has ever taken place in the SMB. In the unlikely case of discoveries large enough to warrant mining at depths greater than 600 m, a conflict of interest would arise with respect to geo-methanation.

8.4 Hydrocarbons and coal

8.4.1 Oil and natural gas

Exploration for conventional hydrocarbons in the Swiss Molasse Basin has been ongoing for around 110 years. However, only one semi-commercial gas field (Entlebuch) has been discovered despite abundant oil and gas shows in wells and at the surface (Leu, 2012).

Nearly all formations with reservoir characteristics in the subsurface of the SMB have shown traces of hydrocarbons in one or more wells. This indicates that any of the identified

potential reservoirs for geo-methanation might contain some oil or gas, especially since trap structures (anticlines and to a lesser degree fault-bounded traps) are the primary exploration target for geo-methanation. However, based on the long history of failed hydrocarbon exploration in Switzerland, it is unlikely that any encountered hydrocarbons would have commercial value. A conflict of use is therefore not expected. However, the presence of hydrocarbons can present a substantial risk for drilling operations and should always be considered during planning.

In the last 15 years, several formations have been investigated for their potential as unconventional reservoirs, i.e., for shale gas or coal bed methane (CBM). Potential shale gas formations include the Carboniferous terrigenous sediments (Pre-Weitenau Formation) and Early Jurassic marine shales (“Toarcian shales” in the western SMB, the Rietheim Member of the Staffelegg Formation in Northern Switzerland; Leu & Gautschi, 2014). Palaeozoic troughs are present or are assumed to be present beneath the Mesozoic sediments in a large part of the SMB. Similarly, the marine shales can be found across the entire SMB. A potential reservoir for geo-methanation would thus likely be in an area where potential shale gas resources are present. There is a clear conflict of interest between the two technologies: both Carboniferous and Early Jurassic shales act as caprocks for potential reservoir formations for geo-methanation (channel sandstones of the Pre-Weitenau Formation and Beggingen Member of the Staffelegg Formation, respectively). While geo-methanation relies on these two caprocks being intact, shale gas production relies on fracturing them. However, due to the large lateral extent of shale gas formations and the small volume required for a geo-methanation reservoir, a conflict of interest could be avoided by proper coordination.

The possible presence of CBM is limited to the coal seams of the Carboniferous sediments of the Palaeozoic troughs. So far, such coal seams have only been confirmed by drilling in the Weiach area. However, based on the organic geochemistry of hydrocarbon shows, carbonaceous sediments are inferred to be present in the Geneva basin (Do Couto et al., 2021) and in the St. Gallen area (Omodeo-Salé et al., 2020). Due to the small volume of coal that has been found or can be assumed to be present, the potential of CBM in Switzerland is limited and commercial production is not envisaged. Despite geo-methanation potentially targeting the same formations or overlying formations, a conflict of interest is therefore not envisaged.

8.4.2 Coal

Evidence for the presence of coal seams in the SMB is summarized in the above paragraph on CBM. As is the case for CBM exploitation, the likely small volumes of coal present, their great

depths and render profitable mining unlikely, even if the environmental concerns of burning coal could be mitigated by CO₂ sequestration. Therefore, no conflict of use between coal and geo-methanation in the Pre-Weitenau Formation or any overlying formations is envisioned.

8.5 Geothermal energy

8.5.1 Shallow geothermal: Ground source heat pumps (GSHP)

Shallow geothermal energy is widely exploited in the SMB in conjunction with heat pumps for space heating. In 2021, over 110,000 GSHP had been installed in Switzerland and by 2050 this number is expected to reach 250,000 installations. Boreholes for GSHP are typically only 120 to 150 m deep. Thus, there is currently no conflict of use between geo-methanation, but this could change in the future if deeper wells begin to be used for GSHP, as they could potentially breach the seal formation of a geo-methanation reservoir.

In a few cases, much deeper wells (500 to over 2700 m) have been used for GSHP applications. However, these are mostly instances where a failed deep well (e.g., a dry hydrothermal well) has been retroactively fitted as a GSHP. Nevertheless, in the future these deeper GSHP might become more common and then a conflict of use between such systems and geo-methanation could arise at specific sites.

8.5.2 Medium-depth geothermal: Hydrothermal energy

Medium depth geothermal in Switzerland makes use of naturally occurring warm/hot groundwaters at depths of 500 to around 4500 m (Geothermie Schweiz, 2022). Thus, they cover the entire depth range suitable for geo-methanation. They also target the same lithologies as they too rely on formations with good fluid-reservoir characteristics. However, for a commercially viable hydrothermal system, production rates of several tens of litres of groundwater per second have to be reached. In the SMB this is mostly achieved in reservoir formations where, in addition to matrix porosity and permeability, additional flow paths have been created by faults, fractures and karst features. Fractured reservoirs are likely unsuitable for geo-methanation as fractures often propagate across the overlying seal as well, creating paths for gas to escape. Therefore, conflicts of use between geo-methanation and medium-depth geothermal are foreseeable only in very porous and permeable formations.

Most of the thermal water occurrences in the SMB are concentrated in the eastern part of the Canton of Aargau (Schinznach, Baden, and Zurzach). The thermal waters are linked to major, steeply-dipping faults surrounding the Permo-Carboniferous troughs (McCann et al.,

2006). These structures permit warm basement fluids to rise rapidly from depths of several hundreds of meters. However, where such normal faults related to Palaeozoic troughs are impermeable, they may bound gas traps in the Dinkelberg Formation/Buntsandstein reservoir and possibly younger formations as well (e.g. Figure 7.1). Thus, rather than causing a conflict of use, water-conducting fault zones help to exclude areas that are unsuitable for geo-methanation and hence they delineate areas that are uninteresting for exploration.

8.5.3 Deep geothermal: Enhanced geothermal systems

Deep geothermal systems in the SMB target largely intact crystalline basement at depths of over 4.5 km. This is substantially deeper than the depth range of interest to geo-methanation. However, the wells of a potential EGS system would penetrate all Tertiary and Mesozoic strata. This could lead to a conflict of interest, if an area suitable for EGS underlies an area suitable for geo-methanation, as the integrity of the caprock would be endangered. Due to the relatively small size of potential geo-methanation reservoirs, the large vertical distance between the two reservoir depths and the fact that inclined wells may be envisaged for EGS, conflict of use should be avoidable with good project coordination.

8.6 Seasonal storage

8.6.1 Aquifer thermal energy storage (ATES)

ATES projects may target a variety of depth ranges, depending on the temperature of the injected water. For low temperature ATES (< 40 °C) the target depths are often only a few tens of metres while high-temperature ATES more commonly targets depths of 130 to 500 m. This is shallower than the minimum depth required for geo-methanation. A potential geo-methanation well could thus penetrate the reservoir and seal of an ATES reservoir. As water is less mobile, this is less critical than the piercing of a caprock of a reservoir containing gases. Careful completion of the geo-methanation well may be sufficient to circumvent a conflict. Similarly to geo-methanation, an ATES system does not take up huge volumes and it may thus be possible to avoid such a spatial interference.

Reservoirs at depths of over 1200 m have also been used successfully for HT-ATES outside of Switzerland, showing that the technology is in principle feasible in the depth interval needed for geo-methanation. The two technologies could therefore target the same potential reservoirs, but HT-ATES typically does not require a fluid trap structure. In areas where trap structures are proven or likely, priority should thus be given to geo-methanation (and

other gas storage applications). Where the integrity of the seal is not sufficient, ATEs might be a valuable alternative to make use of an area originally targeted for geo-methanation. Applying both technologies close to each other in the same reservoir may pose a conflict due to fluctuations in far-field pressure of the formation water induced by pressure control measures (injection and/or extraction of fluid).

8.6.2 Seasonal storage of natural gas or hydrogen

The suitable depth interval for seasonal gas storage is generally between 600 and 3000 m. This overlaps with the depth interval in which geo-methanation is possible. Outside Switzerland, exhausted natural gas reservoirs are favoured sites for seasonal gas storage. However, Switzerland has no known gas reservoirs, whether exploited or not, that could be re-purposed for gas storage. Injection into sealed porous aquifers containing trap structures would be an alternative. These plays are identical to those targeted for geo-methanation, thus a direct conflict of use seems assured. However, the two technologies could make use of the same reservoirs alternately, e.g. by storing the gas that is most profitable in any given year or season.

8.7 CO₂-sequestration

According to Chevalier et al. (2010), the suitable depth interval for CO₂-sequestration in the SMB is 800 to 2500 m. This largely overlaps with the depth interval in which geo-methanation is possible. The two technologies also target the same sealed reservoir formations and trap structures. A conflict of use between the technologies is therefore likely, especially as the volume of sealed reservoirs with suitable petrophysical properties in the SMB is likely limited. Whether or not to fill this limited space permanently with CO₂ or use it for seasonal storage purposes (geo-methanation but also seasonal storage of CH₄ and H₂) is a political question.

The only difference between the two technologies is the reservoir volume targeted. In order to make a significant impact on CO₂ emissions, a permanent sequestration reservoir for CO₂ needs to have a large volume (i.e., be laterally extensive and > 20 m thick; Chadwick et al., 2008). Geo-methanation, on the other hand, is a storage approach whereby the gases are injected and extracted into the same reservoir volume cyclically, requiring a much smaller overall volume. Some small sealed reservoir areas might therefore be suitable for geo-methanation while unsuitable for CO₂ sequestration. This is especially likely in reservoirs consisting of laterally constrained porous bodies within a low-porosity formation (e.g. OSM, USM, Klettgau Formation and Pre-Weitenau Formation).

8.8 Disposal of radioactive waste

The final geological repository for nuclear waste in Switzerland will be hosted in the Opalinus Clay (Dogger Group; Chapter 4.1.7) in Northern Switzerland at a depth of 400 – 1000 m (Nagra, 2022c). While the Opalinus Clay is an aquitard and therefore is of no interest as a geo-methanation reservoir, the aquitards above and below are potentially suitable for geo-methanation. The primary concern for a nuclear waste repository, however, is long-term isolation of the waste and therefore deep drilling projects are unlikely to be approved in the vicinity of the repository to ensure this. A conflict of use of the subsurface between radioactive waste disposal and geo-methanation is therefore likely.

In Switzerland, three potential siting regions for a final repository have been investigated in detail (Chapter 3.2.1). These are (from west to east) Jura Ost, Nördlich Lägern and Zürich Nordost as marked in all maps in Chapter 6. In September 2022, Nördlich Lägern was identified as the region where conditions are ideal for the safe construction and operation of a final repository. While the Nuclear Energy Law dictates that a safe distance between the (potential) repository volume and any projects targeting the deep subsurface needs to be maintained, quantitative limits on this distance are not stipulated. It is therefore not yet possible to assess whether the entire region of Nördlich Lägern will have to be excluded for geo-methanation or only parts of it. Similarly, it is currently unclear whether or not the two remaining potential siting regions will be kept as reserve sites or if deep projects (e.g. geo-methanation) could perhaps be authorized in the near future. As the region of Northern Switzerland represents the best-studied area within the SMB (i.e., with the lowest geological risk) it is the prime target for the exploration for geo-methanation. In addition, it is the area where most Mesozoic formations fall within the required depth-temperature range for geo-methanation, increasing the number of potential reservoirs for geo-methanation.

8.9 Possible conflict of use vs. chance for joint exploration?

Several underground technologies may in principle target the same sealed reservoir formations and the same depth range of interest for geo-methanation. However, most of those require conditions slightly different (highlighted in **bold** below) to those required for geo-methanation:

- Natural gas: well-sealed reservoirs with traps **where economically significant amounts of gas have accumulated**. As a gas cushion is required for geo-methanation, such traps could perhaps be used for geo-methanation after part of the natural gas has been exploited or even during gas exploitation.

- Oil: well-sealed reservoirs with traps **where economically significant amounts of oil have accumulated**. Such traps could perhaps be used for geo-methanation once exploitation has depleted most of the oil.
- Medium depth geothermal energy: reservoirs with **high enough transmissivity (often fractured reservoirs) to allow for a substantial fluid production rate**.
- Seasonal storage – ATEs: sealed reservoirs. **Traps are preferred but not crucial if the natural flow of groundwater is slow**.
- Seasonal storage – Natural gas or hydrogen: well-sealed reservoirs with traps, **regardless of their temperature**.
- CO₂-sequestration: well-sealed reservoirs with **large volume traps**.

The criteria listed in bold cannot be assessed by indirect geophysical methods from the surface. Instead, they require the drilling of wells from which petrophysical data can be collected (from wireline logs and sampling of core material) as well as hydraulic testing (e.g. pump or injection tests). Thus, a shift from focusing on the potential conflict of interest between the different technologies to joint exploration by parties with different application aims might be advisable. By doing that, the most suitable use of an encountered reservoir body could be decided on after its detailed characterisation. This could minimise exploration risk and maximise success rates of underground projects.

Several of the listed technologies are (in principle) feasible at depths greater than the maximum depth envisaged for geo-methanation in the SMB (1400 to 1600 m). However, a detailed investigation of the Muschelkalk aquifer (Stamberg Member of the Schinznach Formation) showed that the reservoir properties become unfavourable at depths > 1500 m due to compaction and secondary dolomite cementation (Aschwanden et al., 2019). As the geological formations above and below have been subjected to the same burial history, it can be assumed that, at least for the older Mesozoic units, the petrophysical properties are equally unfavourable at these depths. Therefore, more exploration projects would likely be targeting the depth interval between ca. 500 and 1500 m, making coordination between potentially conflicting projects more vital.

An additional issue which renders conflicts of use more likely and coordination between projects more important is the degree of exploration maturity (i.e., knowledge of the subsurface) in different regions within the SMB (Chapter 3.2). Overall, exploration maturity is relatively low, imparting a high risk of failure or underperformance to new projects. In order to avoid this, areas which have been studied in greater detail represent more interesting potential targets. In the SMB these areas are primarily in NE Switzerland, which for several decades has been explored for a deep repository for nuclear waste and the Geneva Basin, which

has seen extensive geothermal exploration in recent years. In these areas, the geometries and, to a degree, reservoir properties of different formations are better constrained than in the rest of the SMB. This strongly reduces the exploration risk for new projects, irrespectively of the technology. Northern Switzerland is also the only area where, due to the gentle SE-dip and relatively weak burial compaction of the pre-Tertiary strata, the Mesozoic and Palaeozoic sediments are sufficiently shallow and porous for geo-methanation and for many of the other geo-resource technologies. On the other hand, possible conflicts of use in NE Switzerland are exacerbated by the presence of three potential siting regions for a nuclear waste repository, the occurrences of the highest heat flow and largest abundance of thermal waters in the basin, as well as the only explored Palaeozoic trough (with potential for fluid reservoirs and coal resources).

9 Outlook

9.1 Other promising exploration regions

The information basis available to us did not allow for meaningful investigations outside the area of the SMB covered by the GeoMol temperature model (dotted line in maps in Chapter 6). However, further exploration is encouraged in the Sub-Alpine Molasse (blue area in Figure 6.21). Unfortunately, its internal structure is complex and not well defined, and it is not included in the GeoMol model. However, a comparison with Austria is suggestive. The tectonic setting of the large natural gas reservoirs discovered and exploited in Salzburg is comparable to that of the Sub-Alpine Molasse in Switzerland. In addition, the Tabular Jura Mountains (Cantons of Basel-Landschaft and Aargau) could to be considered in detail as the formations have been less tectonically deformed.

9.2 Possible further studies to support geo-methanation

Our understanding of the composition and the properties of the subsurface of the SMB are based on a relatively small amount of data which are unevenly distributed (heavy focus on Northern Switzerland and the Mesozoic formations over the Tertiary ones). This results in a relatively high exploration risk, especially outside the well-studied areas. Within the well-studied areas, potential conflicts over the utilisation of the subsurface might arise (Chapter 8). The best solution to solve these issues would be an SMB-wide exploration campaign as recently proposed in Swiss Federal Parliamentary Motion 20.4063, to increase the data on the subsurface of the SMB and generally reduce the exploration risk. However, the costs and sheer size of such an undertaking are prohibitive. An alternative is to define a number of smaller areas of interest, which are then explored in detail rather than conducting a basin-wide exploration programme. These areas would ideally fill in blanks on the exploration map of Switzerland (Figure 3.5) and cover both the Mesozoic and Tertiary units. Another approach would be to re-evaluate and re-compile all existing subsurface data, regardless of the original motivation for their acquisition, to create a basis for all kinds of underground technologies. To be effective

this would require obtaining rights to make private data (e.g. old wells and seismic data) publicly available for compilation.

A further option are detailed studies on individual formations and their aquifers, such as the work on the Muschelkalk Group by Aschwanden et al. (2019a,b), Adams and Diamond (2019) and Adams et al. (2019), or the rock-typing approach by Rusillon (2016) for the reef complexes in the GGB. These studies do not necessarily have a specific technological application in mind but focus on understanding the geological history of a single formation. Such studies should include assessment of depositional facies, diagenetic and burial history as well as the evaluation of petrophysical properties to allow for better inter- and extrapolation across the SMB. Studies evaluating the different formations of the Molasse deposits are especially crucial. These units make up large volumes of the sedimentary filling of the SMB but are very poorly studied. They also show geometries which appear well suited to seasonal storage of both gases and fluids (e.g. hot water).

Another area of research which can be done largely using existing data is defining structures (faults, folds) in more detail. Structures had to be simplified in order to be incorporated into GeoMol. However, understanding their real complexity is crucial in assessing their potential to act as traps. Thus, a re-evaluation focusing on the genesis of families of structures in the areas of interest to this study would be beneficial to further exploration for geo-methanation but also for other storage applications in the subsurface (e.g., seasonal gas or hot water storage, CO₂ sequestration; Section 8.9).

9.3 Open question: Geo-methanation up to 90 °C?

For this study, we adopted a temperature range of 30 to 60 °C as a limiting condition for geo-methanation, based on the experience at the Lehen site in Austria and the related laboratory experiments performed by BOKU (Section 2.1.2). However, geo-methanation at higher temperatures (i.e. up to 100 °C) is known to occur commonly in nature. Recent results from BOKU suggest that temperatures above 60 °C might even be advantageous for USC-type geo-methanation. At these temperatures, microbially mediated acetogenesis (whereby CO₂ and H₂ are converted to acetate, CH₃COOH, instead of methane) seems to be inhibited and thus methane production is increased (pers. comm. A. Loibner and H. Konegger).

In theory, it would be possible to re-map the distribution of all potential reservoir formations using an upper temperature limit of 90°C (isotherm already included in *T*-model of GeoMol). This would substantially increase the delimited areas for all formations towards the south and west of the SMB. However, there are a few reasons why this might not be beneficial.

The first is that the exploration maturity of the SMB is in general relatively low (Section 3.2). The best explored areas, where the reliability of geological information is highest and the exploration risk lowest, are in the northern (to north eastern) SMB (Figure 3.5). This is the reason why many of the interesting formations have been stratigraphically studied and formally defined only in this area (e.g. Figure 3.1), while no formal definition exists further afield (c.f. Section 4.1.5 and 4.1.6). Therefore, expanding the screening to temperatures up to 90 °C would increase the area where geo-methanation is theoretically possible but would also strongly increase the geological uncertainties and thus increase exploration risk, especially in the southern SMB where the number of wells is low (Figure 3.4).

Increasing the temperature would not only increase the geographical area where geo-methanation is possible but also the depth range at which the formations are of potential interest. The disadvantage brought by increasing depth is that formations generally become tighter, i.e. lose porosity and permeability due to increased burial. A well-studied example is the Stamberg Member of the Schinznach Formation (Section 4.1.4 and 4.2.4; Aschwanden et al., 2019). In Riehen (BL), the formation is transmissive enough to allow for the production of nearly 20 L/s of geothermal water from 1500 m depth. Similarly, at Schlattigen (TG), 6 L/s are produced from 1200 m depth. At Triemli (ZH), the same formation showed negligible transmissivity at a depth of 2700 m. As most of the formations are already closer to the cautionary porosity value than the positive value (Table 5.1), increasing the depth would likely render more formations and/or areas unsuitable for geo-methanation based on the petrophysical properties. Together with the increased geological risk, the high uncertainties with respect to petrophysical properties makes these deeper zones high risk targets for future exploration. In addition, drilling to and operation at greater depths is costlier. This would need to be taken into account as part of the economic viability scoping calculations.

10 Summary and conclusions

In order to evaluate the geological units in Switzerland for their suitability for the USC-FlexStore technology, this report first defines geological criteria required for successful geomethanation. The criteria (presented in Chapter 2) are based on the experience of project partner RAG at the pilot site in Lehen (Austria; WP3), on information from project partner BOKU (WP1) regarding activity of methanogenic microbes, and on best-practice principles from the literature on geological storage of CO₂. The resulting set of criteria for reservoir formations suitable for gas storage concern properties governing its gas storage capacity (thickness, volume, depth range, rock matrix porosities), gas injectibility and production (rock-matrix permeability and fracture distribution) and microbial activity (temperature interval, ranges of pH and salinity of groundwater). Equally important are criteria that govern gas retention in the subsurface such as minimum reservoir depth, presence of an impermeable caprock sealing the reservoir formation and of trap structures such as anticlines, changes in depositional environment resulting in intercalated reservoir rocks (= stratigraphic trapping) and seals or impermeable faults.

In view of these criteria, our consideration of the geology of Switzerland and of the availability of information on its subsurface led us to discard the following regions from study: the Folded Jura Mountains, the Tabular Jura Mountains, the Sub-Alpine Molasse and the Alpine realm. Thus, the present study deals exclusively with the remaining geological realm known as the Swiss Molasse Basin (SMB). This coincides geographically with the Swiss Plateau, where the majority of the Swiss population lives and works.

In Chapter 3 the geology of the SMB and the past and present exploration campaigns of the subsurface are described. Overall, the SMB consists of a sequence of sedimentary rocks of Palaeozoic, Mesozoic and Cenozoic age atop the crystalline basement. The SMB has been explored for hydrocarbons mostly since the second half of the 20th century, for sites suitable for disposal of radioactive waste since the 1980s, and more recently for geothermal energy, thermal energy storage and geological sequestration of CO₂. Despite this activity, the exploration maturity of the SMB is generally low and highly heterogeneous. Besides a geographical

bias of information density towards northern Switzerland, there is also a clear bias towards the Mesozoic sediments rather than the Palaeozoic or Tertiary ones. A key information source for the present study is the GeoMol digital model of the anatomy of the SMB, which defines the three-dimensional (3D) disposition of horizons separating major geological units (mostly at the stratigraphic Group level). This model, constructed and made available by the Swiss Federal Office of Topography (Swisstopo), includes major faults and fold crest, and is linked to a 3D temperature model of most of the SMB.

Chapter 4 presents a compilation of all relevant information on the geological units within the Swiss Molasse Basin from published literature. This includes data on the lithology, geographical distribution, thickness, petrophysical properties (porosity and permeability) as well as in-situ groundwater compositions. In addition, we attempted to assess how homogeneous or heterogeneous all of these characteristics are within a unit, both laterally and vertically. Based on this, we classified each unit in terms of its potential to act as a gas reservoir or as a seal in general, irrespective of the specific requirements of geo-methanation. We identified 12 units with reservoir properties.

In Chapter 5 the list of criteria assembled in Chapter 2 were applied to rank each of the identified reservoir formations for their suitability for geo-methanation, taking into account the state of knowledge of the formations. A ranking scale of 1 to 4 was applied, where 1 denotes "potentially suitable for geo-methanation" and 4 denotes "likely unsuitable for geo-methanation". This step led to exclusion of two fracture- and karst-based aquifers (crystalline basement and Upper Jurassic/Lower Cretaceous limestones), as these do not permit containment of gas within a predictable zone over the required time periods. The remaining units were ranked as follows:

- 1 Sandstones of the Triassic Dinkelberg Formation
- 1 Dolomites of the Triassic Schinznach Formation – Stamberg Member
- 2 Sandstones and dolomites of the Triassic Klettgau Formation – SBEG Members
- 2 Oolitic limestones of the Jurassic Hauptrogenstein,
- 2 Channel sandstones of the Oligocene/Miocene Lower Freshwater Molasse (USM)
- 2 Beach sandstones of the Miocene Upper Marine Molasse (OMM)
- 2 River-channel sandstones of the Miocene Upper Freshwater Molasse (OSM).
- 3 Sandstones of the Carboniferous Pre-Weitenau Formation
- 3 Limestones of the Jurassic Staffelegg Formation – Beggingen Member
- 3 Limestones of the Etiollets Formation

Chapter 6 presents basin-scale maps for each of the units ranked 1 to 3, showing where they occur within the required depth–temperature interval according to the 3D geological and temperature models. Most of the Mesozoic units fall within the target range only along the foot of the Jura Mountains and/or in Northern Switzerland. The Tertiary strata fall within the desired depth–temperature interval away from the Subjurassic Zone to the south and across the central SMB. In addition, for each unit, the depth to the formation, the thickness of the formation and any fractures and folds affecting the unit were mapped. These maps show three key results: (1) Areas *not* classified as "sealed aquifers". These should be understood as regions where gas storage and geo-methanation are *unlikely to be feasible*, based on the current state of geological knowledge. (2) Areas delimited as "sealed aquifers". These should be understood as regions where gas storage and geo-methanation *may well be feasible*, once more detailed (km-scale) subsurface information becomes available, particularly regarding gas traps. (3) Sites within the delimited reservoirs where anticlines are known to exist. These are favoured traps for gas storage but their closure and gas retentivity are unknown and cannot be deduced from the literature. Exploration costs and risks are lowered by drilling in areas where several potential reservoir units are present in the subsurface, stacked one upon the other. Based on this principle, the colour-coded map in Figure 10.1 shows the most suitable areas for geo-methanation exploration in the SMB. The colour scale reflects the number of potentially suitable sealed aquifers in the subsurface, each weighted by its quality ranking. Priority exploration targets are defined where the most suitable areas (darker greens) coincide with the known presence of anticlines (blue lines).

Chapter 7 outlines the future steps required to establish *definitive feasibility* of geo-methanation in the SMB. This will entail new exploration campaigns focussed at the km-scale on one or more of the potential gas traps shown in our maps. These campaigns should conduct seismic surveys (preferable in 3D), drilling of new wells including their coring and logging, and hydraulic testing of the traps. This will prove whether gas can be injected, extracted and retained in the traps according to the technical requirements of commercially viable geo-methanation sites. The chances of discovering a natural gas cap in the SMB are low and therefore an artificial gas cap will likely need to be created to serve as a pressure cushion. This would require injection of ≥ 4.5 million m^3_{STP} into the trap. Such a campaign targeted at a first potential trap structure is estimated to take approximately 12 years to complete and would cost approximately CHF 39 million (*indicative estimate*). If the first campaign fails to demonstrate a suitable geo-methanation site, then each further exploration attempt could entail sim-

ilar investments of costs and time. There are numerous options to reduce costs and time, including entering joint ventures, procuring existing geophysical surveys, re-evaluating previously explored structures, and drilling into structures that enclose more than one prospective sealed aquifer. However, even after several attempts, there is no guarantee that the investments would yield in a successful geo-methanation site.

Figure 10.1: Map showing relative suitability of areas in the Swiss Molasse Basin for geological gas storage under conditions required for geo-methanation (greater than 600 m deep, temperature 30–60 °C). Shades of denote the sum of sealed aquifer formations locally present in the sedimentary stack, each weighted by its quality ranking. Future wells drilled through several aquifers have higher likelihood of finding suitable reservoirs. Gas trap structures are essential for successful geo-methanation: blue lines show locations of known elongated dome structures (anticlines) that may serve as traps and are therefore priority exploration targets. Areas distant from blue lines may or may not contain anticlines. Faults may also create gas traps but less commonly than anticlines - see maps in Chapter 6 for fault locations.

Chapter 8 discusses potential conflicts of use of the subsurface in the SMB. Several of the underground technologies discussed may in principle target the same sealed reservoir formations and the same depth range of interest for geo-methanation. However, most of those technologies require conditions slightly different to those required for geo-methanation, e.g.

high transmissivities for hydrothermal systems, presence of oil/gas for hydrocarbon exploitation. These conditions, however, cannot be assessed by indirect geophysical methods from the surface. Instead, they require the drilling of wells to assess in-situ conditions, as is the case for geo-methanation. This suggests that, rather than trying to avoid potential conflicts of interest, entering into joint exploration ventures with parties with different application aims could minimise exploration risk and maximise success rates of underground projects.

In a final outlook, Chapter 9 addresses other topics arising from our study. (1) Further exploration is encouraged in the structurally complex Sub-Alpine Molasse. Unfortunately, its internal makeup is not well defined and it is not included in the GeoMol model. However, a comparison with Austria is suggestive. The tectonic setting of the large natural gas reservoirs discovered and exploited in Salzburg is comparable to that of the Sub-Alpine Molasse in Switzerland. The Tabular Jura Mountains also warrants detailed consideration. (2) Suggestions are provided for additional scientific and exploration studies that could be undertaken to support implementation of gas storage and geo-methanation in the SMB in general. (3) Methanogenic microorganisms are known to flourish at temperatures at least up to 90 °C in some environments, opening the possibility that geo-methanation could be implemented at greater depths in the SMB than considered in the present study. However, the literature shows that porosity and permeability in the SMB units decrease rapidly with depth of burial, implying that little will be gained by the costlier enterprise of drilling deeper.

11 References

- Adams, A. and Diamond, L.W. (2019) Facies and depositional environments of the Upper Muschelkalk (Schinznach Formation, Middle Triassic) in northern Switzerland. *Swiss Journal of Geosciences*, 112, 357–381.
- Adams, A., Diamond, L. W., & Aschwanden, L. (2019). Dolomitization by hypersaline reflux into dense groundwaters as revealed by vertical trends in strontium and oxygen isotopes: Upper Muschelkalk, Switzerland. *Sedimentology*, 66(1), 362-390.
- Allenbach, R., Baumberger, R., Kurmann, E., Michael, C. S. & Reynolds, L. (2017) *GeoMol: Geologisches 3D-Modell des Schweizer Molassebeckens – Schlussbericht*. Bundesamt für Landestopographie swisstopo, Bern, p. 128.
- Aschwanden, L., Diamond, L. W., & Adams, A. (2019a). Effects of progressive burial on matrix porosity and permeability of dolostones in the foreland basin of the Alpine Orogen, Switzerland. *Marine and petroleum geology*, 100, 148-164.
- Aschwanden, L., Diamond, L. W., Mazurek, M. & Davis, D. W. (2019b) Creation of Secondary Porosity in Dolostones by Upwelling Basement Water in the Foreland of the Alpine Orogen. *Geofluids* 2019, 1-23.
- Berger, J.-P., Kälin, D. and Kempf, O. (2010) Swiss Molasse lithostratigraphy, 8th Swiss Geoscience Meeting, Fribourg, Nov. 19–20, pp. 127.
- Berger, J.-P., Reichenbacher, B., Becker, D., Grimm, M., Grimm, K., Picot, L., Storni, A., Pirkenseer, C., Derer, C. and Schaefer, A. (2005) Paleogeography of the upper Rhine Graben (URG) and the Swiss Molasse basin (SMB) from Eocene to Pliocene. *International Journal of Earth Sciences*, 94, 697-710.
- Büchi, U. and Bodmer, P. (1983) Der Tiefenverlauf der seismischen Geschwindigkeiten in den Molassesedimenten des schweizerischen Mittellandes. *Bulletin Vereinigung Schweizer Petroleum-Geologen und -Ingenieure* 49, 3-13.

- Chadwick, A., Arts, R., Bernstone, C., May, F., Thibeau, S., & Zweigel, P. (2008). Best practice for the storage of CO₂ in saline aquifers-observations and guidelines from the SACS and CO₂STORE projects (Vol. 14). British Geological Survey.
- Chen, Y. and Cheng, J. J. (2007). Effect of potassium inhibition on the thermophilic anaerobic digestion of swine waste. *Water environment research*, 79(6), 667-674.
- Chevalier, G., Diamond, L.W. and Leu, W. (2010) Potential for deep geological sequestration of CO₂ in Switzerland: a first appraisal. *Swiss Journal of Geosciences* 103, 427-455.
- Diamond, L. W., Wanner, C., & Waber, H. N. (2018). Penetration depth of meteoric water in orogenic geothermal systems. *Geology*, 46(12), 1063-1066.
- Do Couto, D., Garel, S., Moscariello, A., Bou Daher, S., Littke, R., & Weniger, P. (2021). Origins of hydrocarbons in the Geneva Basin: insights from oil, gas and source rock organic geochemistry. *Swiss Journal of Geosciences*, 114(1), 1-28.
- Gander, P. (2004). *Geologie und Hydrogeologie der Oberen Süsswassermolasse – Dokumentation des aktuellen Kenntnisstandes*. Nagra Arbeitsbericht NAB 04-04, Nagra, Wettingen, p. 70.
- Garefalakis, P., & Schlunegger, F. (2019). Tectonic processes, variations in sediment flux, and eustatic sea level recorded by the 20 Myr old Burdigalian transgression in the Swiss Molasse basin. *Solid Earth*, 10(6), 2045-2072.
- Gygi, R. A. (2013). *Integrated stratigraphy of the Oxfordian and Kimmeridgian (Late Jurassic) in northern Switzerland and adjacent southern Germany* (Vol. 104). Birkhäuser.
- Häring M. O., Leu W., Zappone A. and Diamond L. W. (2013) Road map to a CO₂ injection test in Switzerland. In Mazzotti et al., *Roadmap for a Carbon Dioxide Capture and Storage pilot project in Switzerland*. Report for BFE contract SI/500827-01 prepared for Swiss Federal Offices for Energy and Environment, 21 pp.
- IEA-GHG. (2009). *Development of storage coefficients for CO₂ storage in deep saline formations* (118 pp). Technical study report 2009/13. Stoke Orchard (UK): IEA Greenhouse Gas R&D Programme.
- Jenny, J., Burri, J.P., Muralto, R., Pugin, A., Schegg, R., Ungemach, P., Vuataz, F.D. & Wernli, R. (1995). *Le forage géothermique de Thônex (Canton de Genève): Aspects stratigraphiques, tectoniques, diagénétiques, géophysiques et hydrogéologiques*. *Eclogae Geologicae Helvetiae*, 88(2), 365-396.

- Jordan, P. (2016). Reorganisation of the Triassic stratigraphic nomenclature of northern Switzerland: overview and the new Dinkelberg, Kaiseraugst and Zeglingen formations. *Swiss Journal of Geosciences*, 109(2), 241-255.
- Jordan, P., Pietsch, J. S., Bläsi, H., Furrer, H., Kündig, N., Looser, N., ... & Deplazes, G. (2016). The middle to late Triassic Bänkerjoch and Klettgau formations of northern Switzerland. *Swiss Journal of Geosciences*, 109(2), 257-284.
- Jordan, P. and Deplazes, G. (2019). Lithostratigraphy of Consolidated Rocks expected in the Jura Ost, Nördlich Lägern and Zürich Nordost Regions. *Nagra Arbeitsbericht NAB 19-14*, Nagra, Wettingen, p. 188.
- Keller, B. (1989). *Fazies und Stratigraphie der Oberen Meeresmolasse (Unteres Miozän) zwischen Napf und Bodensee*, PhD, Bern, 302 pp., University of Bern
- Keller, B. (1992). Hydrogeologie des schweizerischen Molasse-Beckens: aktueller Wissensstand und weiterführende Betrachtungen. *Eclogae Geologicae Helveticae* 85, 611-652.
- Keller, B., Blasi, H.-R., Platt, N., Mozley, P. and Matter, A. (1990) Sedimentäre Architektur der distalen Unteren Süsswassermolasse und ihre Beziehung zur Diagenese und den petrophysikalischen Eigenschaften am Beispiel der Bohrungen Langenthal. *Nagra Technischer Bericht 90-41*, Nagra, Wettingen, p. 129.
- Kempf, O., & Matter, A. (1999). Magnetostratigraphy and depositional history of the Upper Freshwater Molasse (OSM) of eastern Switzerland. *Eclogae Geologicae Helveticae*, 92(1), 97-103.
- Kempf, O., Matter, A., Burbank, D. W., & Mange, M. (1999). Depositional and structural evolution of a foreland basin margin in a magnetostratigraphic framework: The eastern Swiss Molasse Basin. *International Journal of Earth Sciences*, 88(2), 253-275. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s005310050263>
- Kuhlemann, J., & Kempf, O. (2002). Post-Eocene evolution of the North Alpine Foreland Basin and its response to Alpine tectonics. *Sedimentary Geology*, 152(1-2), 45-78.
- Lahusen, P. H. (1992). Hydrocarbon exploration in the Swiss Molasse Basin. *Eclogae Geologicae Helveticae* 85, 707-714.
- Leu, W. (2012). Swiss oil/gas exploration and lessons learnt. *Swiss Bulletin für angewandte Geologie* 17(1), 49-59.

- Leu, W., & Gautschi, A. (2014). The shale gas potential of the Opalinus Clay and Posidonia Shale in Switzerland-A first assessment. *Swiss Bulletin für Angewandte Geologie*, 19(2), 95-107.
- Matter, A., Homewood, P., Caron, C., Rigassi, D., van Stuijvenberg, J., Weidmann, M., and Winkler, W. (1980). *Flysch and Molasse of western and central Switzerland, Exc. Guidebook No. 126A, 26th Int. Geol. Congr. Schweiz. Geol. Komm. Wepf and Co. Publ., Basel*
- Mazurek, M., Hurford, A. J., & Leu, W. (2006). Unravelling the multi-stage burial history of the Swiss Molasse Basin: Integration of apatite fission track, vitrinite reflectance and biomarker isomerisation analysis. *Basin Research*, 18, 27–50.
- Meyer, M. (2000). *Le complexe récifal kimméridgien-tithonien du Jura méridional interne (France), évolution multifactorielle, stratigraphique et tectonique. Doctoral dissertation, University of Geneva.*
- McCann, T., Pascal, C., Timmerman, M. J., Krzywiec, P., López-Gómez, J., Wetzel, L., ... & Lamarche, J. (2006). Post-Variscan (end Carboniferous-Early Permian) basin evolution in western and central Europe. *Geological Society, London, Memoirs*, 32(1), 355-388.
- Moscariello, A. (2019). Exploring for geo-energy resources in the Geneva Basin (Western Switzerland): opportunities and challenges. *Swiss Bulletin für angewandte Geologie*, 24(2), 105-124.
- Nagra (1988) *Sedimentstudie - Zwischenbericht 1988: Möglichkeiten zur Endlagerung langlebiger radioaktiver Abfälle in den Sedimenten der Schweiz. Nagra Technischer Report NTB 88-25, Nagra, Wettingen, p. 487.*
- Nagra (1989). *Sondierbohrung Weiach Untersuchungsbericht Beilagenband. Nagra Technischer Bericht NTB 88-08. Nagra, Wettingen, p. 183.*
- Nagra (2008). *Vorschlag geologischer Standortgebiete für das SMA- und das HAA-Lager. Nagra Technischer Bericht NTB 08-04. Beilagen. Nagra, Wettingen, p. 439.*
- Nagra (2021a). *TBO Bülach-1-1: Data report. Nagra Arbeitsbericht NAB 20-08, Nagra, Wettingen.*
- Nagra (2021b). *TBO Trüllikon-1-1: Data report. Nagra Arbeitsbericht NAB 20-09, Nagra, Wettingen.*
- Nagra (2021c). *TBO Marthalen-1-1: Data report. Nagra Arbeitsbericht NAB 21-20, Nagra, Wettingen.*

- Nagra (2022a). TBO Bözberg-1-1: Data report. Nagra Arbeitsbericht NAB 21-21, Nagra, Wettingen.
- Nagra (2022b). TBO Bözberg-2-1: Data report. Nagra Arbeitsbericht NAB 21-22, Nagra, Wettingen.
- Nagra (2022c) Der Standort für das Tiefenlager – Der Vorschlag der Nagra. Bericht (68 pp.), Nagra, Wettingen.
- Omodeo-Salé, S., Eruteya, O. E., Cassola, T., Baniasad, A., & Moscariello, A. (2020). A basin thermal modelling approach to mitigate geothermal energy exploration risks: The St. Gallen case study (eastern Switzerland). *Geothermics*, 87, 101876.
- Pietsch, J. S., Wetzel, A., & Jordan, P. (2016). A new lithostratigraphic scheme for the Schinznach Formation (upper part of the Muschelkalk Group of northern Switzerland). *Swiss Journal of Geosciences*, 109(2), 285-307.
- Pfiffner, O.A. (2009), *Geologie der Alpen*, 1st ed., Haupt, Bern, p. 361.
- Pfiffner O.A. (2021) *The Geology of Switzerland*. In: Reynard E. (eds) *Landscapes and Landforms of Switzerland*. World Geomorphological Landscapes. Springer, Cham.
- Pfiffner, O.A., P. Lehner, P. Heitzmann, S. Mueller, and A. Steck (Eds.) (1997). *Deep Structure of the Swiss Alps: Results From the National Research Program 20 (NRP 20)*. Birkhäuser, Boston, p. 380.
- Platt, N. H., & Keller, B. (1992). Distal alluvial deposits in a foreland basin setting—the Lower Freshwater Miocene), Switzerland: sedimentology, architecture and palaeosols. *Sedimentology*, 39(4), 545-565.
- Pullan, C. P., & Berry, M. (2019). A Paleozoic-sourced oil play in the Jura Mountains of France and Switzerland. *Geological Society, London, Special Publications*, 471(1), 365-387.
- Reisdorf, A. G., Wetzel, A., Schlatter, R., & Jordan, P. (2011). The Staffelegg Formation: a new stratigraphic scheme for the Early Jurassic of northern Switzerland. *Swiss Journal of Geosciences*, 104(1), 97-146.
- Rüdisüli, M., Teske, S.L., Sidler, D., van den Heuvel, D. and Mutschler R. (2021). Demand and Supply Model - Work package 6 Intermediate Report. ERANET – USC FlexStore unpublished report.

- Rusillon, E. (2017). Characterisation and rock typing of deep geothermal reservoirs in the Greater Geneva Basin (Switzerland & France). Doctoral dissertation, University of Geneva.
- Schlunegger, F., Burbank, D. W., Matter, A., Engesser, B., & Mödden, C. (1996). Magnetostratigraphic calibration of the Oligocene to Middle Miocene (30-15 Ma) mammal biozones and depositional sequences of the Swiss Molasse Basin. *Eclogae Geologicae Helvetiae*, 89, 753–788.
- Schlunegger, F., Matter, A., Burbank, D. W., & Klaper, E. M. (1997a). Magnetostratigraphic constraints on relationships between evolution of the central Swiss Molasse basin and Alpine orogenic events. (2), 225–241.
- Schlunegger, F., Matter, A., Burbank, D. W., Leu, W., Mange, M., & Mátýàs, J. (1997b). Sedimentary sequences, seismofacies and evolution of depositional systems of the Oligo/Miocene Lower Freshwater Molasse Group, Switzerland. *Basin Research*, 9(1), 1–26.
- Sommaruga, A., Eichenberger, U., & Marillier, F. (2012). Seismic Atlas of the Swiss Molasse Basin. *Matériaux pour la Géologie de la Suisse – Géophysique* 44.
- Sommaruga, A., Mosar, J., Schori, M., & Gruber, M. (2017). The role of the Triassic evaporites underneath the North Alpine Foreland. In *Permo-Triassic Salt Provinces of Europe, North Africa and the Atlantic Margins* (pp. 447-466). Elsevier.
- Stober, I., & Bucher, K. (2007). Hydraulic properties of the crystalline basement. *Hydrogeology Journal*, 15(2), 213-224.
- Strasky, S., Morard, A., & Möri, A. (2016). Harmonising the lithostratigraphic nomenclature: towards a uniform geological dataset of Switzerland. *Swiss Journal of Geosciences*, 109(2), 123-136.
- Strasser A., Charollais J., Conrad M. A., Clavel B. Mastrangelo B. (2016) : The Cretaceous of the Swiss Jura Mountains: an improved lithostratigraphic scheme. *Swiss Journal of Geosciences*, 109(2), 201-220
- Strobel, G., Hagemann, B., Huppertz, T. M., & Ganzer, L. (2020). Underground bio-methanation: Concept and potential. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 123, 109747.
- Strunck, P., & Matter, A. (2002). Depositional evolution of the western Swiss Molasse. *Eclogae Geologicae Helvetiae*, 95, 197–222.

- Thury M, Gautschi A, Mazurek M, Müller WH, Naef H, Pearson FJ, Vomvoris S, Wilson W (1994) Geology and hydrogeology of the crystalline basement of northern Switzerland – synthesis of regional investigations 1981–1993 within the Nagra radioactive waste disposal programme. Nagra Technical Report NTB 93–01, Nagra, Wettingen, p. 473.
- Vollmayr, T., & Wendt, A. (1987). Die Erdgasbohrung Entlebuch 1, ein Tiefenaufschluss am Alpennordrand. Bulletin der Vereinigung schweizerischer Petroleum-Geologen und-Ingenieure, 53(125), 67-79.
- Waber, H.N., Heidinger, M., Lorenz, G. and Traber, D. (2014). Hydrochemie und Isotopenhydrogeologie von Tiefengrundwässern in der Nordschweiz und im angrenzenden Süddeutschland. Nagra Arbeitsbericht NAB 13-63, Nagra, Wettingen, p. 267.
- Waber, N., Bissig, P., Huggenberger, P., Meylan, B., Milnes, E., Schürch, M., and Walter, U. (2015). Tiefengrundwasser. Aqua & Gas 4, 32–41.

**Appendix A Maps depicting GeoMol horizons
in the correct depth–temperature interval for
geo-methanation**

Figure A.1: Map showing the Permokarbondrog layer in GeoMol trimmed to the correct depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation. This layer was used to create the delimited maps for the Pre-Weitenau Formation in Section 6.1.

Figure A.2: Map showing the Muschelkalk layer in GeoMol trimmed to the correct depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation. This layer was used to create the delimited maps for the Dinkelberg Formation (Section 6.2) and Schinznach Formation – Stamberg Member (Section 6.3).

Figure A.3: Map showing the Keuper layer in GeoMol trimmed to the correct depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation. This layer was used to create the delimited maps for the Klettgau Formation – SBEG Members (Section 6.4).

Figure A.4: Map showing the Lias layer in GeoMol trimmed to the correct depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation. This layer was used to create the delimited maps for the Staffelegg Formation – Beggingen Member (Section 6.5).

Figure A.5: Map showing the Dogger layer in GeoMol trimmed to the correct depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation. This layer was used to create the delimited maps for the Hauptrogenstein (Section 6.6).

Etiollets Formation and other Upper Malm Limestones

Upper boundary: Top Upper Malm (TUMa) or Bottom Cenozoic (BKän)
 Lower boundary: Top Lower Malm (TLMa)

Figure A.6: Map showing the Upper Malm layer in GeoMol trimmed to the correct depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation. This layer was used to create the delimited maps for the Etiollets Formation (Section 6.7).

Lower Freshwater Molasse (USM)

Upper boundary: Top USM (TUSM) oder Top Fels (TFels)
 Lower boundary: Basis Cenozoic (BKän)

Figure A.7: Map showing the USM layer in GeoMol trimmed to the correct depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation. This layer was used to create the delimited maps for the Lower Freshwater Molasse (Section 6.8).

Upper Marine Molasse (OMM)

Upper boundary: Top OMM (TOMM) oder Top Fels (TFels)
 Lower boundary: Top USM (TUSM)

Figure A.8: Map showing the OMM layer in GeoMol trimmed to the correct depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation. This layer was used to create the delimited maps for the Upper Marine Molasse (Section 6.9).

Upper Freshwater Molasse (OSM)

Upper boundary: Top Fels (TFels)
 Lower boundary: Top OMM (TOMM)

Figure A.9: Map showing the OSM layer in GeoMol trimmed to the correct depth–temperature interval for geo-methanation. This layer was used to create the delimited maps for the Upper Freshwater Molasse (Section 6.10).

Appendix B Thickness of individual members of the Klettgau and Staffelegg Formations

Figure B.1: Thickness of Klettgau-Seebi Member from wells drilled in the area of interest and adjoining areas. Line shows westernmost expansion of Seebi Member. Modified after Jordan et al. (2016).

Figure B.2: Thickness of Klettgau-Berlingen Member from wells drilled in areas adjoining the area of interest. Line shows westernmost expansion of Berlingen Member. Modified after Jordan et al. (2016).

Figure B.3: Thickness of Klettgau-Ergolz Member (focus on sandy units) from wells drilled in the area of interest and adjoining areas. The Ergolz Member is present across the area studied by Jordan et al. (2016).

Figure B.4: Thickness of Klettgau-Gansingen Member (only dolomite) from wells drilled in the area of interest and adjoining areas. Line shows easternmost expansion of Gansingen Member. Modified after Jordan et al. (2016).

Figure B.5: Thickness of Staffelegg-Beggingen Member from wells (\diamond) drilled in the area of interest and adjoining areas as well as outcrops (\circ) in the Jura Mountains. Modified after Reisdorf et al. (2011).

